

**NATURAL
ENVIRONMENT
RESEARCH COUNCIL**

**Science Programmes
Directorate**

**SCIENTIFIC SERVICES
AND
FACILITIES**

Annual Reports 1999/00

Executive Summaries

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NERC Services & Facilities Management Team - Annual Report 1999/00

1. Introduction

During 1999/00, NERC Science Programmes Directorate (SPD) provided financial support for 32 Scientific Services and Facilities (S&F), which were operated by or on behalf of NERC and/or to which the NERC community had access, as listed alphabetically in Table 1. (NB the Research Ships Unit Liaison Officer (RSUL) is resourced from the Services and Facilities Budget but support for the Research Ships Unit (RSU) itself is not included as it receives funding from NERC via different routes.) Each S&F produces an annual report to a prescribed format with a number of mandatory and optional annexes. The self-contained, summary report sections from each S&F are appended to this report on the activities and highlights of the Scientific Services and Programme Management Group (SSPMG), and the set is distributed to all Science and Technology Board, Advisory Board/Working Group and Peer Review Committee members for information and comment. In addition, it is sent to Scientific Services Steering Committee Chairpersons and Heads of individual S&F. Complete S&F reports have been considered by the respective overseeing Scientific Services Steering Committee(s), and annexes can be made available to readers on request.

2. Scientific Services and Programmes Management Group (SSPMG)

In the course of the year, SSPMG staff at Swindon working on S&F management comprised:

- Dr R L F Kay - Head of Group;
- Mr B A Robinson and Mr P W Purcell (also Head of the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility - ARSF) - scientific administrators;
- Miss M Storey (administrative officer/typist) and Mrs L Chahal (part-time administrative officer).

Financial, contract and procurement administrative support was provided by Financial and Information Systems Directorate (FISD), notably by Mrs L Lovell, Mrs L Skeats, Mrs H Jones, and Mr A Evett.

The SSPMG Head of Group and scientific administrators each acted as Contact Point for a number of individual S&F, and were responsible for:

- Facility management and direct or indirect line management of NERC staff in the cases of ARSF, Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility (ARASF), NERC RadioCarbon Laboratory (RCL), Geophysical Equipment Pool (GEP), NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC and Space Geodesy Facility (SGF));
- Oversight of contracts and/or service level agreements and financial control;
- Steering committee secretariatship and peer-review procedures;
- Programme management - notably the development of the Integrated Data System for ARSF;
- Prioritisation within, and allocation of, capital budget;
- Secretariat of the Services Review Group;
- Publicity; interface with Board and Peer Review Committees etc.

SSPMG staff were also involved in negotiations for commissioned research (mostly via NERC Thematic Programmes) and commercial contracts from which a significant proportion (c13%) of the total Services and Facilities Budget derived.

SSPMG is assisted in its management task by the Scientific Services Steering Committees (listed in Table 2), which advise on operational matters and provide peer-review of user applications. SSPMG was also represented at meetings of the assessment and/or management panels of SGF, the Environmental Flow Research Centre (EnFlo), and for the Central Laboratory of the Research Councils (CLRC) Pulsed Neutron and Muon Source (ISIS) and Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS) services, where NERC contributes as a minor funding partner.

TABLE 1: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES, RECURRENT ALLOCATIONS AND RECEIPTS DUE TO NERC 1999/2000

Acronym	Service and Location	Managing Institution(s)	Total Services' Allocation £k	Other NERC SB £k	Other Receipts £k	
1	15NSIF	15N Stable Isotope Facility, Merlewood	CEH Merlewood	46		
2	AIF	Argon Isotope Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	112		
3	ARASF	Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility, Farnborough	NERC SO	207		
4	ARSF	Airborne Remote Sensing Facility, Conington and CEH Monks Wood	NERC SO	341		25
5	BCCIL	Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory	Sheffield University	160		
6	BOSCOR	British Oceanographic Sediment Core Repository, Southampton	SOC	62		
7	CLRC ISIS	ISIS pulsed neutron and muon source, RAL	CCLRC	170	102	
8	CLRC SRS	Synchrotron Radiation Source, DL	CCLRC	130	161	
9	CMRF	Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar Facility, Chilbolton and RAL	CCLRC	30	26	
10	DSRS	Dundee Satellite Receiving Station	Dundee University	215	13	
11	EnFlo	Environmental Flow Research Centre, Guildford	Surrey University	40		
12	EPFS	Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy, Southampton	Southampton University	81		
13	GEP	NERC Geophysical Equipment Pool, Edinburgh	Edinburgh University and NERC SO	215		
14	ICPAES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy Facility, Egham	RHUL	26		
15	ICPMS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry Facility, Kingston (Service hiatus March - September)	Kingston University	90		
16	ICSF	Isotope Community Support Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	76		
17	IMF	Ion Microprobe Facility, Edinburgh	Edinburgh University	112		
18	LSCSIF	Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	62		
19	MEMF	Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility	Manchester University	56		
20	MSF	Molecular Spectroscopy Facility, RAL	CCLRC	40	60	
21	MSTRF	Mesosphere, Stratosphere, Troposphere Radar Facility, Aberystwyth and RAL	CCLRC	138		
22	NEODC	NERC Earth Observation Data Centre, RAL	CCLRC	81	33	
23	NIGL	NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory, Keyworth	BGS	698		
24	OMSF	Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility, Bristol	Bristol University	38		
25	ORADS	Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service	Oxford University	70		
26	OSCR	Ocean Surface Current Radar Facility, SOC (Service closed end-April 1999)	Southampton University	7		
27	OUUSF	Open University U-Series Facility	Open University	75		
28	RCL	NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory, East Kilbride	SUERC and NERC SO	326		
29	RSDAS	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service, Plymouth	PML	54		
30	RSUL	Research Ships Unit Liaison	NERC SO	16		
31	SGF	NERC Space Geodesy Facility, Herstmonceux	NERC SO	200		300
32	SMGF	Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility	Sheffield University	54		
	SPG Management			139		
	Steering Committees etc			31		
	TOTAL			4198	395	325

3. Management and Staff Arrangement

Most of the S&F were managed via contracts or Service Level Agreements, leaving only three under direct line-management from Swindon, namely, ARASF, ARSF and SGF. At the beginning of 1999/00, staff of the SGF (formerly known as the Satellite Laser Ranger Facility) were transferred from the Particle Physics & Astronomy Research Council to NERC, following the demise of the Royal Greenwich Observatory in Cambridge, from which the staff had previously been managed. A summary of the current management and staff arrangements is given at Annex 1.

SSPMG-managed NERC staff associated with services were:

- Dr A D Kaye (ARASF, based at MRF Farnborough);
- Dr D D Harkness, Mr B F Miller and Dr C L Bryant (RCL, East Kilbride);
- Dr S J White (NEODC and MSTRF, RAL);
- Mr M J Valiant, Mr P Kearney, and Mr A Ball (GEP, Edinburgh University);
- Mr P W Purcell (ARSF, based at Swindon) and Mr F Tadina, Mr G Osborn, and Mr C Joseph (ARSF, based at Peterborough Business Airfield, Conington).
- Dr G Appleby (SGF, based at CEH Monks Wood), and Dr R Wood, Mr P Standen, Mr P Gibbs, Mr D Benham, Mr D Walters and Mr R Sherwood (SGF, based at Herstmonceaux).

Approximately 60 other staff (summarised at Annex 1) are involved with operation of the S&F and are employed by NERC at Centres/Surveys, by other Research Councils or by HEIs.

4. Contractual Information

A table summarising current contract/SLA information, staff numbers, lead-science area, review dates, and Swindon Office contacts relating to each of the S&F budget lines is given in Annex 1. Most S&F are block-funded via contract/SLA-backed contributions to staff and recurrent infrastructure costs in return for agreed proportions of capacity (usually not the total) being made available to the NERC community following peer-review. It should be noted that where the unit-cost of service delivery is relatively high, and/or NERC is a minor customer of an externally managed operation, funding is either fully or partially on a 'pay-as-you-go' basis on grants: viz access to ARASF, EnFlo, ISIS, SRS, and Chilbolton Meteorological Radar Facility (CMRF).

5. Outturn of 1999 Services Review

The 1999 Services Review Group (SRG) recommendations have been implemented, except that ISIS and SRS direct access block-funding provisions have not been maintained at the recommended levels by Council/Earth Science and Technology Board. Also, despite the 1998 SRG recommendations, the Atmospheric Science and Technology Board decided not to allocate funds to make up for shortfalls during the first year of transition to 'pay-as-you-go' of CMRF and EnFlo. Contract or SLA renewals were negotiated for eight S&F. No new services were started during the period.

6. Financial Data

The 1999/00 NERC cash spend on 32 services was approximately £5.7M including capital refurbishment. Table 1 summarises the facilities' allocations, together with contributions from other NERC Science Budget sources (such as the Thematic and Non-Thematic Modes) as well as from external funds. Capital allocations are considered in more detail below.

With one exception (SGF, which has no direct users), the S&F are required to provide cost-allocation data attributing the real and/or notional notional costs of providing services to users. The data on individual usage, tabulated in the Annual Summary of Scientific Services 1999/00 Cost Allocations, are available on request.

7. Lead Areas

During 1999/00, each of the S&F came within the purview of an appropriate NERC Science and Technology Board (indicated via the subdivisions of Table 1 and in Annex 1). However, from October 2000, there will be a single NERC Science and Technology Board, which will cover all of the areas of the previous Boards. The title 'Lead Area' instead of 'Lead Board' has been used to reflect this transition.

8. Steering Committees

Details of the Steering Committees established and funded by SSPMG to assist in overseeing S&F and to peer-review users' applications are given in Table 2.

Other facilities received management oversight via standing committees not serviced by NERC, eg: EnFlo by the EnFlo Advisory Board, also SGF by the Satellite Tracking Applications and Advisory Committee, and ISIS by Scheduling Panel (from 2000, a NERC Steering Committee has been convened for SGF, and the NERC Panel for SRS has been transformed into a NERC Steering Committee covering both ISIS and SRS.)

9. Output and Performance Measures

Applications:

In the course of FY1999/00, the 32 Services & Facilities provided support for the following project applications:

	Total Applications	Total Supported	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	Pilot Project	Reject and R*
Total	494	429	20	146	203	39	4	17	65

NB Projects graded R*, particularly those involving students and first-time applicants, are typically improved following facility and/or steering committee advice and upgraded.

Publications:

During Calendar Year 1999, the Services & Facilities contributed, by means of collaboration, service and/or data provision, to the following publication output:

	SBA	ESTB	MSTB	ASTB	TFSTB	EO	Polar	Refereed	Non-Refereed Conference Proceedings	PhD Theses	Grand Total
Total	35	219	69	206	81	58	4	303	273	29	605

10. 2000 Services Review and Applications for New Services

The Services Review Group (SRG) is convened annually in January with an *ad hoc* membership normally drawn from Peer Review Committees (PRCs) and Science and Technology Boards (STBs), to assess and prioritise applications for new services and audit and review those existing services which have contract/SLA end-dates 15 months later. The SRG recommendations are presented for approval by the respective Lead-Boards and the PRCs advised of the outcome. This constitutes an 'Exit Strategy' aimed at continually refreshing the services portfolio to reflect scientific priorities and user needs.

This mechanism is open to any potential new service with running costs below £150kpa (not including capital; initial capitalisation cannot be supported from the services budget). Where it seems likely that more than one institution could offer a given service, a prior options exercise is conducted, possibly leading to extra bids being submitted in competition with the original bid. Applications for services where the costs exceed £150kpa are not supported from the services Infrastructure baseline and funds must be sought from an appropriate PRC or the STB.

TABLE 2: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES STEERING COMMITTEES 1999/00

Steering Committee	Facilities overseen	Chairman 1999/00, affiliation	No Meetings
Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee	ARSF, RSDAS*, NEODC*	Prof P Cross, UCL	2
Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility Steering Committee	ARASF	Dr J Pyle, Cambridge	2
British Ocean Sediment Core Repository Steering Committee	BOSCOR	Prof J Dowdeswell, Bristol	1
Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory Steering Committee	BCCIL	Prof J Grace, Edinburgh	1
Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Steering Committee	DSRS, RSDAS*, NEODC*	Prof I Robinson, Southampton (since replaced by Dr T Guymer, SOC)	1
Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy Steering Committee	EPFS	Mr A Lamb, NRSCL	1
Geophysical Equipment Pool Management Committee	GEP	Prof M Forde, Edinburgh	2
Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectrometry Facilities Steering Committee	ICPMS, ICPAES	Prof M Coleman, Reading	2
Ion Microprobe Facility Steering Committee	IMF, EEMF, MEMF	Prof I Fairchild, Keele	2
Molecular Spectroscopy Facility Steering Committee	MSF	Dr J Barnett, Oxford	2
NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee	MSTRF, CMRF	Prof C Collier, Salford	2
NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory Steering Committee	NIGL, AIF, ICSF, OUUSF	Dr A Bath, Golder Associates (since replaced by Prof N Harris, OU)	2
NERC Isotope Life Sciences Steering Committee	¹⁵ NSIF, LSCSIF	Prof J Lee, Sheffield	1 joint meeting (single committee from 2000 under chairmanship of Prof D Powlson, IACR Rothamsted)
NERC Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility	OMSF	Prof J Sargent, Stirling	
NERC Radiocarbon Facilities Steering Committee Sub committee: Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service Advisory Panel	RCL, ORADS	Prof D Keen, Coventry	1 joint meeting plus 1/2 separate meetings each (from 2000)
	ORADS	Prof K Edwards, Sheffield (since replaced by Mr A Saville, National Museum of Scotland)	
NERC Synchrotron Science Advisory Panel (NERC ISIS and SRS Steering Committee from 2000)	SRS	Prof R Cernik, DL (since replaced by Prof A Putnis, Muenster)	2
Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility Steering Committee	SMGF	Prof M Macnair, Exeter	2
Total NERC Supported			30
Other SCs not supported by NERC except by SPD representation			
ISIS Panels (see SRS above)	ISIS	Various	2
Satellite Tracking Applications and Advisory Committee (NERC Space Geodesy Steering Committee from 2000)	SGF	Prof P Moore, Newcastle	2
EnFlo Advisory Board	EnFlo	Dr J Weare, Consultant	1
Grand Total			35

Jointly overseen *

The 2000 SRG met on 18 January. Independent members were drawn exclusively from PRC chair or STB nominee, plus one PRC member from each science area. The SRG itself was chaired by Prof M Pollard (Bradford) and other members were Dr J Plane (East Anglia), Prof C Collier (Salford), Prof A Fleet (NHM), Dr C Franklin (ES, Swindon), Dr P Newton (MS, Swindon), Prof M Thirlwall (RHUL), Prof W Heal (SAC, Edinburgh), Dr D Rimmer (Newcastle), Prof F Huntingford (Glasgow), and Mr D Brown (Director Science Programmes), plus Dr R L F Kay and Mr B A Robinson (secretary) from the office. The SRG prioritised and advised on five applications for renewal of existing service contracts/SLAs, with effect from 1 April 2001, and one bid to establish a new S&F from 1 April 2000. The Services Review Group took account of: the documentation furnished by the applicant(s) in standard format; scientific, financial and other performance indicators, eg usage data; and supporting information, such as letters of support from the community and the overseeing Steering Committee. Using four equally weighted scoring criteria (relating to: need; uniqueness; actual or potential quality of service; and quality of science and training to be carried out), the SRG prioritised the applications in the order given in Table 3. Also, for each application, the table includes the scores and comments of the SRG.

The Services Review Group recommended that:

- S&F contracts/SLAs for four of the existing services considered should be renewed (Organic Mass Spectroscopy Facility, Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility, Isotope Community Support Facility and Open University Uranium-Series Facility);
- renewal should not be granted in the case of Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory due to relatively low scores and current pressure on the Services and Facilities Budget;
- a revised application for the new service (ALOMAR Middle Atmosphere Facility) be resubmitted with more information regarding *quid pro quo* arrangements, clarification of management structure and demonstration of UK need and benefit.

The SRG also endorsed the recommendation by the Director Science Programmes that NERC should develop a more strategic approach towards funding of facilities following the outcome of the second round of the Joint Infrastructure Fund. It was recommended that, in the course of 2000, a review of NERC S&F be undertaken to drive the development of a Strategic Plan covering the next 5-10 years. It was recommended that the current S&F *raison d'être* be examined in the context of the NERC Mission/Science Strategy, the need for SA&F infrastructure to underpin NERC strategic activities, the justification for centrally-funded S&F, the current portfolio's fitness for purpose, impact of the JIF initiative, funding basis for NERC access, and access to European facilities.

11. Publicity

The S&F brochure has essentially become a "virtual document" with details of access, peer-review and charging arrangements for each of the funded S&F (and also for those recognised but not funded), and is now primarily published via the NERC Website. This is continually updated and the linkages to Websites specific to each S&F are being revised and improved.

Articles and news items prepared by S&F for NERC News were as follows:

- *Isotopes as climate archives: climate and diatoms*, Dr M Leng and Dr P Greenwood, NIGL, Autumn 1999;
- *Climate conference*, Dr M Leng, NIGL, Autumn 1999;
- *Photochemistry during the solar eclipse*, Dr A Kaye and Dr H Richer, ARASF, Winter 1999;
- *A sharper image*, P W Purcell, ARSF, Winter 1999;
- *X-ray absorption spectroscopy in environmental sciences*, Dr J Cotter-Howells and Dr J Charnock, SRS, Spring 2000;
- *Core repository open day*, Dr G Rothwell, BOSCOR, Spring 2000.

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF 2000 SERVICES REVIEW GROUP RECOMMENDATIONS

Priority	Service	Scoring Criteria					99/00 SB £kpa	Est Δ £kpa	Cum Δ £kpa	Services Review Group Comments	Lead Area
		Need	Uniqueness	Service Quality	Science/ Training Quality	Rating (x)					
1	NERC Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility (OMSF), Bristol	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.00	37	+5	5	Renewal recommended. Difficult to find fault with this excellent facility, except that the service cost/capacity figures given were confusing, and should be clarified contractually by SPD.	TFS
2	Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility (LSCSIF), SURRC, East Kilbride	5.0	4.5	4.0	4.5	4.50	60	+20	25	Renewal recommended. Very important and exciting facility. Geographic distribution of users is narrow, but widening. Isotope ecology is increasingly important. The request for additional staffing is stronger for LSCSIF than ICSF. The absence of letters of support made evaluation more difficult.	TFS
3	Isotope Community Support Facility (ICSF), SURRC, East Kilbride	4.5	4.0	4.5	4.0	4.25	77	0	25	Renewal recommended. The facility has been supplying the service that is needed, by providing access to expertise and facilitating people doing the work themselves. The case for the second half of a technician was not well made, but the Group was happy to leave it up to SPD.	ES
4	Open University Uranium-Series Facility (OUUSF), Milton Keynes	4.0	3.0	4.5	4.5	4.00	75	0	25	Renewal recommended. The costs presented were considered to be high, but staffing should not be reduced. The need for the facility would fall with the increased throughput offered by plasma techniques, and the availability of a service from NIGL. Increasing the number of publications should be encouraged. The Group welcomed the support of Open University.	ES
5	Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory (BCCIL), Sheffield	4.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	3.25	160	*	25	The staffing level is not justified, but continued access to the site needs to be safeguarded. It is very important to life sciences to have these long term study sites, and Buxton should be considered in a strategic review of study sites. The facility needs to be looking broader. The overall scores are not sufficient to command any priority for an allocation from the Services and Facilities Budget for the renewal. Service staffing at the level of one man-year per year technical support would be appropriate, with other required staff transferring to funding by the University. (* Cost-neutral as previously funded from Council Headroom.)	TFS
	ALOMAR Middle Atmosphere Facility, Hovemere Ltd, Hayes, Kent	3.0	5.0	1.0	4.0	3.25	-	-	25	Resubmission recommended. At present there is too much uncertainty/risk associated with the proposed <i>quid pro quo</i> arrangements. The applicant should be invited to come back with a better proposal, containing more demonstration of need, confirmation from ALOMAR principal investigators that they wish to collaborate and contribute data, and further details of the management structure which will ensure that the UK benefits from the arrangements. Meanwhile, the aim should be to get some grant money moving through the system.	AS
TOTAL							409		25		

12. Capital Budget

The Services and Facilities Capital Budget, amounting on average to 12% of the Services and Facilities Science Budget allocation is intended to ensure that regular investment in, and replacement, of equipment maintains S&F capabilities at a high level. Bids against this fund are normally received from S&F annually in January and allocations are made even before the recurrent allocations to S&F are finalised. The S&F nested in HEIs which are eligible to apply for funds from the Joint Research Equipment Initiative and the Joint Infrastructure Fund

now have to seek funding for major capital via those routes, although the Services and Facilities Capital Budget is still accessible for emergency and maintenance needs. The allocations made from the budget in 1999/00 are listed in Table 4.

Half of the funds were used to complete payments of earlier approved major investments at DSRS (upgrade to allow reception of x-band data transmissions from the latest generation of NASA environmental satellite instruments) and NIGL (laser probe and counting multiplier array). The main new additions were funds for a second Fourier Transform Spectrometer System at MSF, a replacement spectrometer at ICPAES, and baseline investment in replacement magnetic, GPS, ground radar and seismic equipment at GEP.

13. Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF)

JIF has provided opportunities for HEI-based facilities to renew and/or expand their equipment capital base. Several of these are likely to impact on S&F in terms of increased capabilities and greater call for support via recurrent and capital budgets, possibly at the level of 5% or more of the initial JIF investment. In Rounds 2 & 3, successful bids were made by Leicester University (re GEP), UMIST (re ARASF), Reading University (re ARASF, CMRF and MSTRF) and Edinburgh University (re IMF).

14. Acknowledgements

The contributions made by members of the Steering Committees to the effective running of the S&F portfolio is particularly appreciated. Credit is due to personnel in other departments for administrative and financial assistance, and to the management of each S&F for timely provision of data pertinent to Output & Performance Measures, Steering Committee and peer-review business.

Brian Miller has retired from NERC after more than 25 years employment in, and immense contribution to the success of, the NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory. A number of other key individuals have left current S&F in order to pursue interests in other areas - notably Dr David Emery (EPFS), Prof Chris Hawkesworth (formerly Head of OUUSF at Open University and now at Bristol University) and Prof Ian Castro (formerly Head of EnFlo at Surrey University and now at Southampton University) - and best wishes are extended to them in their new endeavours. NERC support for several S&F ended during the course of the year, and thanks are due to host institutions and to staff associated with facilities for their important contributions whilst part of the team.

R L F Kay, B A Robinson and P W Purcell
Scientific Services and Programme Management Group
Science Programmes Directorate

September 2000

TABLE 4: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES CAPITAL ALLOCATIONS 1999/00 AND PROPOSED FORWARD COMMITMENTS 2000/01 AND BEYOND

Service	Items Bld 1999/00	Comments	99/00 £k	00/01 Forward Commitment £k	01/02 Forward Commitment £k
¹⁵ NSIF	Uninterruptible power supplies Autosampler, microbalance (50%) GCMS (50%)		6	34	
AIF					
ARASF					
ARSF/IDS	IDS/GPS Enhancements Racking		25		
BCCIL					
BOSCOR	Microscope		18		
CMRF	Various				
DSRS	X-band upgrade	Final instalment	145		
EnFlo	Burst Spectrum Analyser Modernisation of electronics		29		
EPFS					
GEP	Miscellaneous Geomagnetism/Positioning/ Radar/Seismology		100		
ICPAES	Replacement Spectrometer	50% Contribution	50		
ICPMS	Lab refurbishment			40	
ICSF	Carbonate preparation system		10		
IMF					
ISIS					
LSCSIF	Online furnace etc Freeze dryer and vacuum pump		13		
MEMF					
MSF	2 nd Fourier Transformation Spectrometer System		89		
MSTRF					
NEODC	Fire safe for Dundee data archive			10	
NIGL	Laser probe/triple counting multiplier array	Amount includes final instalment of LICPMMS	119		
OMSF	H/D collectors, reconditioned pump M/S upgrade		10	15	
ORADS	Rotary evaporator (33%)			3	
OUUSF					
RCL	Computer upgrades		25		
RSDAS	Replacement of workstations MODIS Data Processing		8	21	
SLRF					
SMGF	Upgrade to sequencer		16		
SRS					
Overspend carried forward			100	33	
TOTAL			763	166	0
FUNDING					
S/F Capital			559	559	559
Returned banking					
Dundee X-band upgrade			130		
¹⁵ NSIF Cashflow			16	16	
NIGL Cashflow			25	25	25
TOTAL			730	600	584

ANNEX 1: S&F CONTRACT/SLA, TERMS, STAFF NUMBERS AND STATUS, REVIEW DATES, AND SWINDON OFFICE CONTACT AT SEPTEMBER 2000

	Initials	Name	Location	Lead Area	Type	Term (yrs)	Staff	Contract Reference	Contract end-date (31 March)	Service Review Date (Jan)	Service contact
1	¹⁵ NSIF	¹⁵ N Stable Isotope Facility	CEH Merlewood	TFS	SLA	5	SSO, 0.5 SO, AO	SLA CEH Merlewood	2004	2003	RLFk
2	AIF	Argon Isotope Facility	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	5	PD + T	F14/6/35	2002	2001	RLFk
3	ARASF	Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility	MRF Farnborough	AS	Direct + PAYG	5	SSO N/A	SPG staff + MoD F3/66/669	2004	2003	RLFk
4	ARSF	Airborne Remote Sensing Facility	Swindon/Conington	TFS/EO	Direct	5	0.7 SSO, 5 misc.	SPG	2003	2002	PWP
5	BCCIL	Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory	Buxton/Sheffield University	TFS	C	3	Director, 2 T, 0.5 C	DST/26/70/07	2002 Ends	2000	BAR
6	BOSCOR	British Oceanographic Sediment Core Repository	SOC	ES	C part	5	0.5 UG7, HSO	Non-Capital element part of SOC contract	2002	2001	PWP
7	CMRF	Chilbolton Meteorological Radar Facility	Chilbolton/CLRC RAL	AS	SLA + PAYG	3	0.5 PD	SLA CLRC	2002	2001	BAR
8	DSRS	Dundee Satellite Receiving Station	Dundee University	MS/EO	C	4	8 misc.	F14/6/4/01	2002	2001	PWP
9	EnFlo	Environmental Flow Research Centre	Surrey University	AS	C	3	PD, T	F14/6/19	2001 Ends	1998 To PAYG	BAR
10	EPFS	Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy	Southampton University	TFS/EO	C	5	0.6 Pool Man., 0.2 PD, 0.5 PG, 0.4 Tech	F14/6/6 DST/26/70/04	2004	2003	PWP
11	GEP	Geophysical Equipment Pool	Edinburgh University	ES	C	3	SPTO, HPTO, PTO, 2 misc.	F14/6/24	2004	2003	RLFk
12	ICPAES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry Facility	Royal Holloway, London University	ES	C	3	0.5 PG	F14/6/8	2003	2002	RLFk
13	ICPMS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry Facility	Kingston University	ES	C	3	0.5 PD + 0.25 PD, PG, T	F14/6/91	2002	2001	RLFk
14	ICSF	Isotope Community Support Facility	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	3	PD + 0.5 T	F14/6/11/01 DST/26/70/08	2004	2003	RLFk
15	IMF	Ion Microprobe Facility	Edinburgh University	ES	C	5	2 PD	F14/6/40 DST/26/70/09	2003	2002	BAR
16	ISIS	Pulsed Neutron and Muon Source	CLRC RAL	ES	SLA + PAYG	3	N/A	SLA CLRC	2002	2001	BAR
17	LSCSIF	Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility	SUERC, East Kilbride	TFS	C	3	PD, T	F14/6/20/01 DST26/70/01	2004	2003	RLFk
18	MEMF	Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility	Manchester University	ES	C	3	1.5 misc.	F14/6/32 DST26/70/17	2002	2001	BAR
19	MSF	Molecular Spectroscopy Facility	CLRC RAL	AS	SLA	5	1.785 misc.	SLA CLRC	2005	2004	BAR
20	MSTRF	Mesosphere, Stratosphere, Troposphere Radar Facility	Aberystwyth University CLRC RAL	AS	SLA	5	0.5 SSO, 1.9 misc.	SLA CLRC	2005	2004	BAR
21	NEODC	NERC Earth Observation Data Centre	CLRC RAL	TFS/EO	SLA	5	0.5 SSO, misc.	SLA CLRC	2005	2004	RLFk
22	NIGL	NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory	BGS Keyworth	ES	SLA with BGS	5	Prof, 5 UG7, 4 SSO, 3 HSO, 2 SO, 3 T	SLA BGS	2005	2004	RLFk
23	OMSF	Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility	Bristol University	TFS	C	3	PG	F14/6/13/01	2004	2003	RLFk
24	ORADS	Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerating Dating Service	Oxford University	ES	C	3	c0.2 10 misc.	F14/6/25	2002	2001	RLFk

	Initials	Service Name	Location	Lead Area	Type	Term (yrs)	Staff	Contract Reference	Contract end-date (31 March)	Service Review Date (Jan)	Service contact
25	OUUSF	OU U-series Facility	Open University	ES	C	3	0.5 PD, 0.2 PG, 0.5 T	F14/6/47 DST26/70/20	2004	2003	RLFK
26	RCL	NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	3	UG7, SSO, HSO, 4 T, AO	F14/6/3/01	2003	2002	RLFK
27	RSDAS	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service	CCMS Plymouth	MS/EO	SLA with CCMS	5	c0.3 SSO, 2 HSO, SO, misc.	SLA with CCMS	2005	2004	RLFK/ PWP
28	RSUL	Research Ships Unit Liaison	NERC Swindon Office				0.5 HSO				
29	SGF	Space Geodesy Facility	Herstmonceaux and Monks Wood	ES/EO	Direct from 1999	5	2 SSO, 2 HSO, 2 HPTO, SO	Two-thirds of the funding is from MOD and DTI (BNSC)	2004	2003	BAR/ RLFK
30	SMGF	Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility	Sheffield University	TFS	C	3.5	PD	F14/6/48 DST26/70/66	2002	2001	BAR
31	SRS	Synchrotron Radiation Source	CLRC DL	ES	SLA + PAYG	3	N/A	SLA CLRC	2002	2001	BAR

Key: NERC staff by grade: UG7, SSO, HSO, SPTO, HPTO, SO, PTO; Post-Doctoral Research Assistant PD; Post-Graduate Research Assistant, PG; Technician, T; Clerical, C; miscellaneous, misc.

Service Contacts at NERC Swindon Office (SPG staff) by initials: Dr R L F Kay; Mr B A Robinson; Mr P W Purcell.

Other abbreviations: PAYG, 'Pay-As-You-Go' (SPG maintains single accounts on behalf of all NERC funding modes).

2.1 ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

UniS

**University
of Surrey**
Guildford
Surrey

**EnFlo Annual Report to
NERC (NSS) for the Year
April 1999 to March 2000**

Alan Robins

ME-FD/00.108

August 2000

Environmental Flow Research Centre
School of Mechanical and Materials
Engineering
The University of Surrey
Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH
United Kingdom

1. Service Objectives

The Environmental Flow Research Centre (EnFlo) at the University of Surrey comprises a large thermally stratified wind tunnel and a salinity stratified towing tank, together with a wide range of associated equipment and instrumentation. These provide a unique UK facility for laboratory scale simulation and investigation of environmental flows and pollutant dispersion. EnFlo's prime objective is to further the application of its facilities to research and training in these subjects so as to enhance the competitiveness of UK environmental scientists in both the academic and industrial spheres.

2. Overview and Highlights

The year 1st April 1999 to 31st March 2000 saw the completion of the sixth year of EnFlo's operation since it was officially opened in December 1993.

During the year, work requiring rig-time was undertaken on eleven individual grants and contracts from seven funding agencies (details are given in Annex 7). Four of the eleven were NERC grants. NERC-ROPA GR3/R9770, "Modelling dense gas dispersion in complex environments", used 14% of facility time, NERC-URGENT/UWREN Urban Meteorology Programme GST/04/2231, "Interactions between canopy and boundary layer flows", 6%, NERC GR3/11393 (joint with the University of Leeds), "Stable boundary layer flow over hills", 12%, and NERC GR3/10438, "Large eddy simulation (LES) of atmospheric flow and dispersion around buildings", 1%. The low figure for GST/04/2231 arises because all of the work was conducted in one of the subsidiary wind tunnels in the EnFlo laboratory and, as this is a relatively inexpensive facility to use, it carries a low weighting in terms of EnFlo facility time (see Annex 7 for further details). The 1% associated with GR3/10438, which is primarily a computational project, was used in providing some additional wind tunnel data for testing computer predictions. Utilisation for in-house research and development was similar to the previous year, but the level of support for Final Year Undergraduate student research projects fell from last year's rather high figure.

Of the eleven grants and contracts active in the year, two contributed to the understanding of air flow over complex terrain, three to flow and dispersion around buildings and structures, two to flow in the urban canopy and boundary layer, one to mixing processes in stratified flows, and five to atmospheric dispersion processes in general. The prime application areas were small-scale meteorology, urban air quality, local-scale air pollution and industrial safety.

Facility developments concentrated on enhancements to control systems and software to ensure more comprehensive condition monitoring and archiving, and to extend the range of experiments that can be conducted through unmanned, overnight running. The NERC NSS Equipment grant funded replacement of a Laser Doppler Anemometer Burst Spectrum Analyser and refurbishment of the wind tunnel traverse equipment were completed.

Prof. Ian Castro moved to the University of Southampton at the beginning of 2000 and Prof. Alan Robins took over as Director of EnFlo. There is no plan to fill the Associate Director position previously held by Prof. Robins, and the two sets of responsibilities

have been combined. In the short term at least, this significantly lowers our ability to generate and manage new research activities. Other changes within the University, including the closure of the Civil Engineering Fluid Mechanics Laboratory, will also affect EnFlo operations in the longer term, though precisely how is unclear at present. NERC Grant award GR3/1201C, "Aeolian deposition in dry-lands: interactions with valley topography", has moved to the University of Southampton and will not now require EnFlo facility time. Similarly, the EU (Network) Proposal, Quality & Trust in CFD, though awarded will not now involve EnFlo staff.

3. Science

All the projects were collaborative in nature and some involved considerable preliminary design, construction and commissioning of models and equipment. Most notable amongst the latter were a cooled two dimensional hill for NERC GR3/11393 (stable boundary layer flow over hills), a two dimensional cavity with surface temperature control for EU-TMR 'Access to Large Scale Facilities' (thermal effects on flow in a street canyon). Control system and software developments enhanced the effectiveness of facility access by allowing a considerable increase in unmanned overnight operations. The examples of projects undertaken in 1999/2000 are given below.

A wind tunnel investigation of the three-dimensional structure of the turbulent flow in the roughness sub-layer over an urban-type surface was conducted under the NERC-URGENT Grant GST/04/2231 (joint with the Universities of Reading and Salford). The growth of the depths of the inertial and roughness sub-layers over a flat surface covered with a regular array of three dimensional roughness elements was determined. Spatial averaging was used to remove the variability of the flow due to the individual obstacles. This showed that the spatially averaged mean velocity in both sub-layers could be described by a standard log-law, with mean zero-plane displacement, using the true roughness length and friction velocity of the surface. The spatially averaged shear stresses in both sub-layers were consistent with the shear stress deduced from the drag measurements. These results provide fundamental information for modelling urban air quality. The work continues with the study of irregular arrays of roughness elements.

The second and third projects under the EU-TMR 'Access to Large Scale Facilities' contract, undertaken by visiting scientists from EC Nantes and the University of Florence respectively, were completed in the summer of 1999. The second concerned the influence of the solar heating of building surfaces on flow in urban street canyons. Numerical work at Nantes had shown that buoyancy forces created at a downstream wall of a street canyon in cross-flow could disrupt the canyon vortex flow and considerably increase pollutant residence times. The objective was to simulate this phenomenon in the wind tunnel and quantify the dependence of flow conditions on a characteristic Froude number. Considerable preliminary work was involved in the design, construction and commissioning of a suitable wind tunnel model. The experiment did indeed reveal the anticipated changes in flow structure but at different Froude numbers than in the numerical simulations. These findings provide fundamental information for developing improved models of local-scale dispersion in urban environments.

The ICI funded project, the dispersion of fugitive emissions from storage tanks, addressed the differences between flow and dispersion in the wakes of small aspect ratio

cylindrical structures (storage tanks) and equivalent cuboids. The practical objective was to improve models for predicting the dispersion of operational discharges from tanks. How the extensive body of research concerning cuboids could be applied was not clear at the outset and part of the work was devoted to determining 'equivalent cuboids' for tanks. This was addressed because computer models used for routine air quality and health and safety purposes work with equivalent cuboids, rather than actual building shapes. Wind tunnel results identified the equivalence but showed that it depended on source height, as well as tank shape. The measurements also revealed considerable sensitivity to small scale features, such as the bund walls frequently constructed around tanks to contain liquid spills. Such effects cannot be included in the level of computer modelling employed and their consequences need to be quantified so as to set limits on the uncertainty of resulting predictions.

4. Future Developments

Changes within the EnFlo management structure and the University have been briefly outlined in Section 1. A proposal to transfer a wind tunnel from the Civil Engineering Fluid Mechanics Laboratory to the EnFlo Laboratory was developed once closure of the former had been confirmed. This was justified on the grounds that the move enhanced the capabilities of the EnFlo facilities as well as servicing teaching requirements. Performance of the tunnel will be improved as part of the move, providing a facility with a 1.07x1.37m cross-section, 9m long working section with air speeds up to 35ms⁻¹. Funding has been provided by the University and the work is scheduled to be completed by January 2001 without significant disruption to other activities within EnFlo.

Improvements to the control and monitoring systems and experimental capabilities of the EnFlo facilities will continue to improve their effectiveness and to meet specific project demands. Plans include the purchase of an additional Fast Flame Ionisation Detector System from Cambustion (£ 25 700) to double the number of channels available for wind tunnel concentration fluctuation measurement and a second acoustic Doppler velocimeter from RH Wallingford (£ 8 300) as two instruments are needed for vortex shedding and similar studies, and replacement of outdated hot wire anemometry equipment with a University of Newcastle (Australia) four channel system (£ 8 800). We also intend to make provision for the replacement (considered likely within the current year) of the Coherent Innova '70, 4 watt, argon-ion laser tube source used for anemometry and light sheet work through a tube purchasing insurance scheme (£ 10 600) that provides near-immediate replacement of a failed tube.

5. Summary of Performance Information

(i) Proposals approved in 1999/2000

GR3/12954: "Large-eddy simulation extended by extreme value theory for the prediction of dispersion, concentration threshold boundaries and field connectivity", Voke, Robins and Ledford, University of Surrey; rated $\alpha 4$ and awarded at £ 172 358 for a three year period.

(ii) Science areas and project costs

Science area: Atmospheric

Resource issues: Environmental Risks/Hazards

(iii) Publications in 1999

EnFlo research work generated eight journal papers, three book chapters, twelve reports and twenty two conference or seminar presentations.

(iv) Targets and milestones

During the year, work requiring rig-time was undertaken on eleven individual grants and contracts from seven funding agencies. Funding for these was distributed as follows: NERC, 4; EPSRC, 1; EC-TMR, 2; British Council, 1; HSE, 1; Industry, 3.

Facility availability approached 100%, excluding the periods in the year when the University was closed, though the full capability was not always available and some adjustments to the programme were necessary on a short time scale as a result. The overriding problem was intermittent loss of an adequate chilled water supply to the main wind tunnel from central University services. Remedial work was carried out and some improvement in performance resulted.

Specific targets for 2000/01 are listed below:

1. To resolve EnFlo management issues following the departure of Prof. Castro.
2. To install the ex-Civil Engineering wind tunnel in the EnFlo laboratory.
3. To host the final EC-TMR visits.
4. To host further visits from EC Nantes and the University of Florence.
5. To submit one ROPA and two standard grant applications.
6. To continue to increase overall instrumentation capabilities and scope for unmanned operation of all facilities.
7. To purchase an additional fast FID instrument, an additional acoustic Doppler velocimeter, replacement hot-wire instrumentation, and laser tube insurance.
8. To determine user demand for new facilities and instrumentation.

(v) Finance

Income of £ 28 340 was received from the NERC-NSS Contract during the financial year 1999/2000 and was used for salaries (Dr Paul Hayden, PDRA, £ 25 350) and recurrent consumable expenditure (£ 2 990). The NSS Capital Equipment award of £ 28 500 was used in replacing old laser Doppler anemometry equipment and improving the traverse mechanisms in the main wind tunnel.

The NSS Full Cash Cost for 1999/2000 was £ 58 500, the unit cost £ 2 980 per week and the NERC users rig time value £ 50 660.

The value of all grants and contracts running on January 1st was £ 728 200 for 1999 and £ 906 929 for 2000. The value of newly started grants and contracts in 1999 amounted to £ 475 243.

The NSS Service Review in 1988 recommended that NSS support for EnFlo should be reduced to zero in the two years from April 1999. Support for 1999/2000 was consequently only sufficient to maintain the 'Infrastructure' PRDA post and not the associated Technician post, and in 2000/01 only part of the PDRA post will be covered.

(vi) Service management and staffing

Prof. Ian Castro moved to the University of Southampton at the beginning of 2000 and Prof. Alan Robins took over as Director of EnFlo. There is no plan to fill the Associate Director position, previously held by Prof. Robins, and the two sets of responsibilities have been combined.

Staffing levels at the start and end of the reporting period are summarised below:

Grade	1st April, 1999	31st March, 2000
Professors	2	1
PDRA	5	3
PG Students	8	5
Technicians	3	2
Secretary	1	0

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

SCIENCE PROGRAMMES DIRECTORATE

ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH AIRBORNE SUPPORT FACILITY

ANNUAL REPORT 1999-2000

SUMMARY REPORT

Service Objectives:

The Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility (ARASF) exists to facilitate access to large atmospheric research platforms for atmospheric and environmental scientists in support of their research. This is currently provided by an access agreement with the Met. Office for use of the MRF (Met. Research Flight) Hercules C-130 aircraft. This Defence Research and Evaluation Agency (DERA) owned platform is operated by the RAF out of Boscombe Down on behalf of the MRF.

The ARASF staff of one is based at Farnborough and aims to fulfil its mission (Annex 1). That is to maximise the NERC community's access to the aircraft platform and instrumentation, in the context of competing scientific demands and weather constraints, to train airborne scientific parties, and to co-ordinate the supply of acquired data to the NERC users.

Overview of 1999-2000 Activities and Highlights:

The period from April 1999 through to March 2000 was the fifth year for the operation of the ARASF within the NSS remit. The facility now operates on a pay-as-you-go basis under the terms of the SRG (Services Review Group) renewal for 5 years commencing 1 April 1999. The ARASF pays the full cost of the C-130 aircraft time purchased from the Met. Office. The high cost of using the Met. Research Flight (MRF) has put pressure on NERC aircraft access and has caused difficulties with the planning of Thematic Programme Experiments and Responsive Mode access. All experiments within the ARASF portfolio were reviewed continuously with the MRF aircraft manager to ensure that no reasonable opportunities to fly were missed.

Support was provided by the Atmospheric Science and Technology Board to enable completion of all alpha-4 experiments that had been previously approved under the Responsive Mode remit.

The ARASF purchases time on the MRF C-130 for NERC researchers. Our access is dovetailed with the Met. Office's in-house research programme, EU contracts and other commissioned work. The MRF C-130 aircraft is programmed for an average of 500 hours per year over its 6-year maintenance cycle. NERC utilises a modest fraction of this time, averaging about 40 hours per year over the past 6 years. The high cost of the facility is the primary limiting factor on utilisation.

Flights for NERC funded projects were successfully flown for the UTLS (Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere) sub programme DCFZ (Dynamics and Chemistry of Frontal Zones) and a flight investigating small cumulus clouds over East Anglia was carried out. Although only a limited number of hours were flown specifically for NERC, the ARASF facility was involved in a number of flights. These included the European funded MAXOX (MAXimum OXidation rates in the troposphere) programme and several piggyback flights for tests of NERC funded instruments (TDLAS, PERCA, ORAC, SID, TAFTS). The initial NERC funding of instrumentation has also enabled NERC funded researchers to collaborate with other users of the C-130 aircraft, in particular, researchers from the university of Leeds have collaborated with the European STAAARTE (Scientific Training and Access to Aircraft for Atmospheric Research Throughout Europe) project. The MAXOX programme included two flights, which were supported with NERC funds: the KONVEX flight over Germany and the Eclipse flight in August 1999.

Science:

Solar Eclipse Flight

The total solar eclipse of 11 August 1999 provided a unique opportunity to study the chemical composition of the atmosphere when perturbed by a comparatively fast change in light intensity.

The flight pattern involved a number of straight and level runs along the edge of the totality line: we could not use the central line due to the presence of cloud. Successive runs were positioned slightly upstream of the wind in order to remain out of the aircraft exhaust. The peroxy radical signal, although rather noisy, was seen to fall-off as the eclipse started to occur. However, there were a couple of short periods when the liquid flow in the instrument failed and therefore there is not a continuous trace from the UEA PERCA instrument. The data from the UEA NO_x (NO and NO₂) has now been processed and the fall-off in the NO signal during the eclipse is quite apparent.

In summary, the NO and peroxy radical data followed the expected fall-off and recovery during the eclipse. However, the data is near the detection limits of the instruments and hence any time difference between the timing of the eclipse and the timings of the fall-off in NO and peroxy radicals is difficult to pinpoint. Therefore, rate coefficients for the reactions cannot be gained accurately. However, it is clear that the data does not show any significant deviation from the rate coefficients measured in laboratories. The data set demonstrates the low detection limits and high sensitivity of these techniques. As such this data will be useful as an example in any instrumental papers describing these techniques.

The photolysis rate of ozone ($j(O^1D)$), leading to excited state oxygen atoms, was measured during the eclipse. Periodic fluctuations in this rate, and hence in the UV flux, were observed during and after the eclipse. Earlier studies have attributed fluctuations in UV light, following an eclipse, to wave-like disturbances in the stratosphere caused by the cooling of the atmosphere during the eclipse. However, this has yet to be proven. Studies are currently underway to determine whether the $j(O^1D)$ data can be explained by changes in the ozone column abundance or by simpler influences such as the presence of cloud.

The PERCA Instrument and Model Calculations:

The UEA PERCA (Peroxy Radical Chemical Amplifier) is a developmental instrument built by Tim Green and Stuart Penkett, for use on aircraft. It was initially developed in order to measure the sum of the hydroperoxy radical (HO₂) and organic peroxy radicals (RO₂). The dominant organic peroxy radical is the methyl peroxy radical (CH₃O₂), which is formed in the photo-oxidation of methane and larger hydrocarbon molecules.

Species that react readily, with a wide range of compounds, are difficult to measure, in part because they are generally found in low concentration, but also because of their tendency to react on instrument inlets. Inlet problems are particularly difficult to overcome on aircraft due to turbulence, physical restrictions (which may effect inlet materials or instrument position) and rapid changes in air mass composition (e.g. air may be dry one minute and saturated the next). In the spring MAXOX campaign the PERCA instrument was found to show little or no signal due to peroxy radicals. However, modifications to the inlet, before the summer campaign, led to an improvement in the radical signal.

The expected concentrations of the radicals, HO₂ and CH₃O₂, can be estimated from simple photochemical models. Claire Reeves from the University of East Anglia has developed models appropriate to the study: observed concentrations of water vapour, O₃, CO, peroxides, HCHO and NO, along with estimated concentration of CH₄ and the observed photolysis rates $j(O^1D)$ and $j(NO_2)$ have been used to calculate concentrations of HO₂ and CH₃O₂. The PERCA signal is found to show close agreement with the CH₃O₂ radical mixing ratios, simulated with this method. However, the HO₂ levels are not reproduced.

This agreement suggests that the inlet system for the PERCA instrument on the C-130 effectively destroys the more reactive HO₂ radicals before they reach the chemical amplifier; whereas the CH₃O₂ radicals are efficiently passed through the inlet. It is therefore thought that the PERCA is reliably measuring CH₃O₂ and that the calculated values of both HO₂ and CH₃O₂ are accurate. The sum of CH₃O₂+HO₂ can be used to calculate the ozone production rate: one of the primary objectives of MAXOX.

Future Developments:

The status of the C-130 platform has been uncertain for some time. The high cost of operating this aircraft, and the transition of the Met. Office to a Trading Fund, has lead to the search for alternative lower cost options.

A community bid was submitted to the JIF (Joint Infrastructure Funding) initiative in April 1999 to provide the UK research community with a state-of-the-art atmospheric research platform. This bid was successful and, at present, negotiations are underway to enable tender documentation to be finalised during the summer of 2000.

The new aircraft will be a joint facility shared by the Met. Office and the NERC community on an equal basis.

Summary of Performance Information:

(i) numbers and percentage of Alpha-Graded proposals supported

Nineteen hours of C-130 time were provided in support of 5 dedicated flights flown during the year in support of Alpha-4 graded science. As in previous years, requests for aircraft time were in excess of actual availability. In addition to this access was gained to over 100 hours of aircraft time on a collaborative basis.

During the year 13 applications for aircraft time were received. Six applications were peer reviewed at Alpha 4 grade with an additional 5 at Alpha 3. One application given an R*, while an application for an MSc training flight was endorsed by the steering committee, but not given a science grade.

(ii) percentage distribution and costs of projects

Funding	PI	Institution	Cost	Percentage
UTLS	Browning	University of Reading	£55,650	30%
NSS	Jonas	UMIST	£32,625	18%
CWVC	Choularton	UMIST	£32,900	18%
NSS	Richer	ITE	£20,200	11%
NSS	Law	Cambridge	£17,200	9%
Support of user community and future applications			£26,500	14%

(iii) Publications for the Calendar Year

12 refereed publications were published during the year with 17 additional non-refereed publications being produced. One PhD was awarded during 1999, which made extensive use of data collected by the facility and a dedicated flight that took place during 1997.

All of the publications supported Global Climate Change work, with seven refereed and seven non-refereed publications relating to pollution and waste.

(iv) Targets & Milestones

There were no specific targets set for the service during the period under review, beyond those relating to the ARASF Mission or required by Scientific Services Policy.

(v) Financial Details

Total cost of providing the NERC community with access to a large aircraft facility for the year was £185,000. This cost covered the purchase of 18.8 hours of MRF C-130 access at £6300 per hour, £140,000. The cost of the MRF facility includes aircraft support personnel, installation and data support. Additional NERC personnel and support for the facility amounted to £45,000.

(vi) Service Management & Staffing

ARASF personnel account for one of the two full-time NERC posts at the Met. Research Flight. The NERC Scientific liaison at MRF post was created in 1992 to facilitate collaborative research between NERC and the Met. Office. With the formalisation of the ARASF service within NSS, the role became that of Head of Facility. This post (Band 5S) is managed through Science Programmes Directorate at Swindon Office.

A second post, which is line managed through ITE Edinburgh (Band 6S), is maintained by NERC under contract from the Met. Office to provide Atmospheric Chemistry support. There is no official interaction between these two posts, although in reality a close working relationship is required because of the overlap of responsibility and user communities.

The SRG review concluded that additional staff would be required to maintain a suitable standard of service if the flying programme envisaged by the Thematic Programme and Responsive Mode support was realised. The staff has been stretched during the past few years, and the provision of additional staff resources are being arranged for the coming year.

The Services Review Group reviewed the facility in January 1998, on the basis of pay-as-you-go funding for aircraft time. This bid was well received, being given a straight alpha-5 rating by the committee. The renewal was for 5 years starting 1 April 1999.

CHILBOLTON ADVANCED METEOROLOGICAL RADAR

ANNUAL REPORT TO NERC 1999/2000

1. Service Objectives

The Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological radar is the main UK test bed for the development of advanced meteorological radar techniques. Working with the Met Office and radar meteorologists in the UK, new techniques are developed which could be used operationally in future ground-based or spaceborne radar systems. To build new today the antenna system would cost around £10M, but the original robust construction of the facility gives a considerable asset to exploit in a new century.

2. Overview and Highlights

The Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar is the main component of the facilities at the Chilbolton Observatory owned and operated by the Radio Communications Research Unit of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. The site is near Andover in Hampshire. The facility provides access to the research community for experiments in meteorology, hydrology and environmental sciences. The system is a 3 GHz radar which can transmit both vertical and horizontal polarisations and has a Doppler capability. Mounted on a 25 m antenna, this system is the world's largest fully steerable meteorological radar. The facility is considerably enhanced by the positioning of a Dopplerised 94 GHz radar on the rim of the dish.

1999/2000 was the first year of 'Pay-as-you-go' at Chilbolton. This meant that NERC support was cut to provision of a NERC Liaison officer at 0.5 man years per year, and users of the system needed to pay for observations using grant money. In fact, there were still 5 applications, only one less than last year. Overall, NERC observations fell from 150 hours last year to 81 hours this year, but routine cloud measurements were also made using cloud radar and lidar which contributed to user's needs.

2.1 European Space Agency Cloud Observations

During the year, the European Space Agency technical organisation ESTEC continued its interest in the site and a new 2 year cloud observations contract is presently being finalised. The recent data gathered at Chilbolton was a crucial part of the science case in the bid for selection by ESA of the Earth Radiation Mission, ERM. The mission would be to fly a radar and lidar on the same platform in space to obtain global information on the vertical characteristics of cloud. Although the ERM was ranked in third place at the meeting held in Granada in October 1999, a recommendation was made for work on ERM to continue perhaps in collaboration with the Japanese Space Agency, NASDA.

2.2 New data acquisition system

A new data acquisition system was installed on the radar this year which allows much greater flexibility in the signal processing. This allowed the implementation of a spectral width

parameter required by users as a way of identifying turbulence and also quantifying its strength. The system was implemented in parallel to the existing system to ease development and to prevent disruption to other programmes.

2.3 Storm Observations

The storm of 19 May 1999 caused widespread flooding in the Thames Valley region, with a considerable amount of fire damage caused by lightning. The Chilbolton radar observations of the event are shown on the left revealing multiple cores to the storm. Mark Blackman of RAL's Chilbolton group took the observations along to Central TV News the following evening which ran about 10 minutes of material on the storm.

The BBC's 'Essential Guide to Weather' programme filmed in May and broadcast 6 minutes from Chilbolton on 30 August 1999. Filming also took place at Chilbolton on 25 June for the BBC's tornado week showing shots of the dish, control room and some archive Chilbolton tornado data.

3. Science

3.1 Cloud cover

Data from the 94 GHz radar have shown that the way that clouds are represented in models is inadequate and this could have a large impact on climate models. Generally, if there are no gaps looking vertically the models define cloud layers as directly above each other. If there is a certain vertical separation, then the clouds are given a random position in the grid box. This has a big impact on precipitation formation in the box and the radiative effects of cloud cover. In fact the results show that even with no vertical gaps the cloud tops are often pushed away from the cloud bottoms and an analytical expression has been derived to describe this.

3.2 Supercooled layers

Supercooled water layers have been identified at Chilbolton. They form in distinct layers several hundred metres thick that provide a strong signal for lidar, but because of the small droplet size are undetected by radar when ice is present. They will be much more important in determining the radiative properties of the cloud than any ice that may be around. They will

also impact glaciation and precipitation processes. Currently, atmospheric forecast and climate models usually assume a simple ratio between ice and liquid water content that varies only with temperature. If supercooled water layers are common there is a need to improve their representation in models.

3.3 Turbulence in the presence of weather fronts

Prof K A Browning and research assistant Dr. D Chapman from Reading University carried out observations of the nature and distribution of shearing instability and turbulence in frontal shear zones. This leads to a better understanding of the effect of mixing on the structure of frontal zones and the role of the large-scale flow and thermodynamic fields in generating turbulence. These results will be used to validate current and future developments in the mesoscale versions of the Met Office Unified Model. Turbulent billows are a candidate mechanism for chemical mixing between air masses at fronts.

4. Future Developments

A Joint Infrastructure Fund bid led by Reading University was successful and will significantly upgrade the facilities at Chilbolton with the addition of a new 35 GHz radar, a clear air radar and refurbishment of the focus cabin. A 35 GHz radar has been missing this year after the French system enjoyed in previous years was returned to its owner. The ability to make observations at two cloud radar frequencies is vital for microphysical cloud measurements. The installation of a lower frequency system at around 1250 MHz will allow clear air radar measurements and open up new research area. Strong interest has already been expressed in urban boundary layer measurements with this system.

5. Summary of Performance Information

5.1 Applications

During the year 5 applications were made to the Steering Committee. One of these has been graded and observations taken, whilst the others are for observations next year. Five applications from the previous year continued this year and formed the bulk of the work. Thus 6 applications ran on the facility this year and their peer review grades by the Steering group were as follows,

Grade	$\alpha5$	$\alpha4$	$\alpha3$	$\alpha2$	$\alpha1$	β	R	Total
Applications	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	6

The facility supported 100% of all applications received and 100% of all alpha graded science. Two of the $\alpha5$ projects were in support of NERC thematic programmes.

5.2 Percentage distribution and costs of projects

The split of activity in the NERC Science areas was 75% in Atmospheric Science and 25% in Earth Observations, with a 50:50 split for projects across environmental risks and global

change ENRIs. A breakdown of costs against Science areas and ENRIs is given in annex 5 of the appendix.

5.3 Publications for the calendar year 1999

There were 5 refereed journal papers/book chapters, 14 conference papers, 8 conference abstracts and two theses. Distribution across science areas excluding the theses was 6 in Earth Observation and 22 in Atmospheric Science.

5.4 Use v Capacity

To calculate facility capacity: 247 working days per year at 8 hours each gives 1976 hours available. The radar log for the last 12 months shows that 393 hours of radar data were taken which represents 20% of the time, because the system generally only operates during appropriate rainy conditions. NERC observations formed 81 hours of the observations which was 20% of the total usage.

The spread of use across the NERC projects was as on the left. The figure shows radar minutes used for the weather fronts project, the new weather fronts project, cloud observations, surface refractivity and internal R and D. For the way this fits into the whole portfolio of work on the radar, see the appendix.

There were 319 hours of downtime of which 117 hours were unscheduled and due to faulty elevation metadyne brushes. Routine maintenance of the drive system of the 25 steerable dish highlighted a potentially serious problem with the brushes and commutator in the metadyne unit of the servo drive system. These were therefore removed and refurbished by a contractor. Upgrades to the servo system are being done to prevent future unscheduled downtime.

5.5 Financial Details

The total estimated annual running costs for Chilbolton are £240K. The NERC income in 99/00 was £61,125 including £30K paid by NERC for a Liaison officer at half-time.

The Full Cash Cost for the Service in 1999/00 was £67,525. The unit FCC costs used were £8/radar minute and £300 per 1% of user support time.

5.6 Service management and staffing

1.65 person years as below,

Name	Job	Grade	Person-years per annum
Amos D M	Student	Band 9	0.417
Bennett J L	Workshop Assistant	Band 8	0.1
Goddard J W F	Head of Facility	Band 3	0.037
Kilburn C A D	NERC Liaison	Band 5	0.8
King D T	Electrical installation	Band 6	0.1
Ladd D N	Operations manager	Band 4	0.1
Threlfall E	Workshop	Band 6	0.1

ANNUAL REPORT
for the
NERC MESOSPHERE-STRATOSPHERE-TROPOSPHERE RADAR (MSTR)
FINANCIAL YEAR 1999/2000 (APRIL - MARCH)

1. Service Objectives

The Mission of the NERC Mesosphere Stratosphere Troposphere Radar (MSTR) Facility is to provide high quality atmospheric data products in near real-time to the UK and international scientific community in support of environmental research. The Facility also provides training and promotes good practice in the use of the data by the user community and the awareness, value and application of MST radar data. For projects which require the Radar to be operated in a specific mode, it operates procedures to enable accredited access thereby ensuring only the best science is supported.

2. Overview and Highlights

In order to achieve its Mission the NERC MSTR Facility:-

- operates and maintains the MST Radar system at Capel Dewi, Aberystwyth and associated systems at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)
- monitors and investigates the quality of the radar data output - in particular by comparison of MSTR-derived winds with those measured by the Met Office using balloon sondes at Aberporth
- routinely archives the MSTR data products with the NERC British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) thereby providing access to the data through the BADC website: www.badc.rl.ac.uk
- provides appropriate scientific and technical support to the user community including the acquisition of additional related data at the radar site
- and executes commissioned work to supplement the annual budget.

The highlights of the year have been:-

- the significant contribution that MST radar data is providing in support of the NERC Thematic Programme:- Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere/Ozone (UTLS/Ozone)
- the extensive use of MST Radar data by the European CWINDE programme and the UK Met Office which continues to demonstrate the quality and reliability of the Facility's data products compared to other European wind profilers
- the installation of LAP Radars and commissioning at the MSTR site of one of the Met Office's 915MHz

- the design, construction and commissioning of a prototype upgrade system to replace the obsolescent computer hardware/software which previously operated the radar system and carried out the data processing
- the implementation and acceptance of many significant Health & Safety and security upgrades following advice from the on-site Operations Manager and the RAL H&S executive.

3. Science

The MST Radar technique is concerned with the derivation from echo power spectra of three physical parameters of the scattering medium: the intensity of refractive index variations, the radial velocity and the velocity dispersion. The system technique provides for high resolution in time and height together with the capability for relatively continuous long-term measurement periods.

The NERC MST Radar is a ground-based 46.5 Mhz radar – radar array dimensions are 100m x 100m - which measures atmospheric characteristics in the height ranges: 2 – 20km and 70 – 90km approximately. In the lower altitude range the Radar gives measurements of horizontal wind vectors on time-scales of minutes and with a height resolution of 150metres. The NERC MST Radar is very well suited to studies of small-scale dynamics – turbulence, waves and winds – the capability of measuring directly the vertical velocity being a unique feature. It is also very valuable for the study of meso-scale phenomena such as fronts, stratosphere-troposphere exchange, atmospheric gravity waves, and to the provision of data for assessing climate numerical models and wind field derivations.

Scientific Highlights for 1999/2000

Observation of large-amplitude inertia-gravity

Inertia-gravity waves are long-period waves, generally most prominent in the lower stratosphere, where the wind vector rotates in an ellipse over a period of 8-16 hours. They are frequently observed with the MST radar, especially after the passage of jet streams. These waves are of importance for the stratospheric circulation because they carry momentum up from tropopause level (where they are generated) to the middle stratosphere. Normally, a particular inertia-gravity wave event over Aberystwyth lasts about 24 hours, but in July 1999 an extraordinary event was observed which lasted 5 days. The easterly wind component over this time is shown in the Figure below, and clearly shows descending phase fronts which are one of the hallmarks of inertia-gravity waves. It appears that this wave was generated by a highly curved jet stream: a paper describing the event has been submitted to J Geophys Res.

Observations during the 1999 solar eclipse.

The MST Radar was operated in Mesosphere mode for a period of three days around the time of the solar eclipse to support a research project investigating possible effects of the eclipse on the earth's upper atmosphere - including gravity waves.

4. Future Developments

Developments and plans for the forthcoming year and beyond include:-

1. The production of full system documentation - hardware and software - for the upgraded MST Radar system.
2. Documentation of all algorithms used in the derivation of MSTR data products provided at the BADC website.
3. Support of the international project - "An Experiment to Investigate Gravity Waves, Mixing and Filamentation in the Tropopause Region" - which will also involve the Egrett, an Australian high-altitude atmospheric research aircraft which will overfly the MST Radar envelope.
4. Purchase, installation and commissioning of a new surface met station at the Capel Dewi site with data being deposited in near real-time on the BADC website.
5. Incorporation of data from the Met Office LAP system onto the BADC Website.
6. Appointment of a Project Scientist for the MST Radar Facility with primary responsibilities for research and development of the MST radar system in collaboration with the scientific community.
7. Incorporation of an optical isolator in the radar control system to prevent future possible lightning damage.

5. Summary of Performance Information

The MST Radar Facility acquired data on behalf of the scientific community for a total period of 8169 hours in 1999/00 and this represents 93% of the projected availability during the year. These data are compiled in appropriate formats on the BADC website and are available to the user community on the following day. The annual percentage availability of data for 1999/00 was less than for previous years mainly due to two severe electric storms, one of which occurred on Christmas eve. The MSTR operations staff - Ken Slater and Tony Olewicz - commendably spent several days of their Christmas leave period repairing the system which had been damaged by power surges resulting from a lightning strike such that it was operational again by the Millennium eve.

In addition to the provision of data for the scientific community, quasi real-time data were supplied every 3 hours under a commercial contract to the UK Met Office - both for operational forecasting and scientific use.

In addition to the MST Radar wind data, comparison of these data with 6-hourly radiosonde data from Aberporth were also made available on the BADC website - these data are now updated on a weekly basis. The radiosonde data were supplied by the UK Met Office to a level of 99.7% of annual capacity.

Surface wind data from nearby Frongoch were also collected continuously - one minute averages - and similarly recorded on the BADC website for the user community. These data are also updated on a weekly basis and the annual recovery rate was 95.6%.

Targets and Milestones:

During September all the field relays were checked and repaired as necessary - a unique system for replacement of switch insulators in each relay has been developed in-house which is proving to be both more reliable and significantly cheaper than the manufacturer's repair.

Influence of humidity on MST radar vertical echoes

The variation in power of VHF radar vertical echoes has been investigated as a function of atmospheric humidity. The echoes are greatest in air of moderate (30-70%) humidity, and least in very dry or near-saturated air. Compared to moderate humidities, the standard model for radar echoes, based on potential refractivity, over-predicts the echo power at high relative humidity by ~10 dB. It is proposed that this is due to the effect of precipitation in suppressing small-scale humidity gradients. A model, which assumes complete suppression, under-predicts the observed power drastically, showing that precipitation can only remove a part of the small-scale structure in refractivity which is caused by fluctuations in humidity. A paper describing this study has been submitted to Radio Sci.

Observations of streamers in the troposphere and stratosphere using ozone lidar and MST Lidar measurements have been used to depict the passage of three mesoscale ozone disturbances in the troposphere and stratosphere. In the troposphere, two small fold-like structures were shown beneath, and at the edge of, streamers of high potential vorticity in ECMWF analyses. MST radar measurements at the same time show that one of these folds was actively turbulent, causing mixing of stratospheric and tropospheric air. In the stratosphere, a streamer of low-latitude air drawn into a filament by a breaking Rossby wave event was observed crossing the radar site. A paper describing these studies has been submitted to J Atmos Chem.

Turbulence in tropopause folds

Case studies demonstrate that tropopause folds may be recognised in radar and ozonesonde data as ozone-rich dry layers coinciding with a layer of high wind shear. The latter property is crucial for it allows the radar to track the fold as it advects overhead, rather than providing just a snapshot as the sonde passes through. A search was made through the database of ozonesonde and MST radar measurements available at Aberystwyth since 1991 to ascertain how many of these folds were turbulent. Turbulence can be detected by the radar as an enhancement in spectral width after correction for beam broadening. Out of 244 ozonesonde profiles, 25 folds were found. Of these, 16 (about 2/3) showed turbulence at some time during the passage of the layer of enhanced wind shear through the radar beam. Using the static stability measured by the sonde, the spectral width may be converted to turbulent dissipation rate.

Observations of stratospheric air entering the circulation of a polar low.

Dry air descending within the circulation of a polar low was observed to give a striking signature in the echo return from an upward-looking VHF radar. Data from this radar, along with weather radar data, satellite imagery and output from limited-area and mesoscale versions of the Met Office Unified Model, are synthesised to depict the mesoscale structure of the weather system. The polar low had a compact vortex centred near 3 km, a cold core below this level and a warm core above. Attribution of quasi-geostrophic forcing showed that on the larger scale the polar low was dominated by upper-level forcing. The detailed mesoscale analysis showed that the polar low, during its mature phase, was affected by a stratospheric intrusion that brought air from near tropopause level down to 3 km to give the striking signature in the VHF radar echo pattern. The echo pattern also suggested that thin tongues of this stratospheric, or near-stratospheric, air were penetrating slantwise down a further several hundred metres into the shallow cloud constituting the southern end of an archetypal cloud head. It is argued that this was a locally important region of mixing between air originating near the tropopause and the boundary layer. In more general terms, the study demonstrates the ability of the operational mesoscale model to represent various small-scale features. The study also helps in developing the interpretation of the patterns of clear-air radar echo observed with VHF radar.

Plots of vertical wind data since 1990 have been added to the BADC website as requested by the community and also, MST Radar/Met Office Radiosonde comparative wind data are now added to the webpages on a weekly basis.

All MST Radar data products are stored in near realtime on the BADC website and it is from this site that customers obtain information regarding the Facility and/or acquire data to meet their scientific objectives. In 1999/2000 there were in excess of 40,000 hits on the MST Radar web pages and this included over 13,000 hits from the UK academic community. There were almost 8,000 cases of downloading of MST Radar data and a total of 690 host computers from UK academia accessed information from the MSTR site on the BADC of which there were 26 hosts which carried out specific data downloading. UK Universities which are making significant use of MST Radar data include:- Reading, Aberystwyth, Heriot-Watt, Birmingham and Sussex.

Following an internal review in 1998, there were several perceived risks to the continued successful operation of the MST Radar Facility due to the increasing age and potential obsolescence of the operating and data processing computer hardware/software of the existing system. Consequently it was decided to implement a project to upgrade the system by the replacement of these old systems with modern computers and associated software.

This modernisation programme - including design, construction and prototype commissioning - commenced in early 1999 and the Project Engineer who has carried out virtually all the work is Ken Slater.

In essence, the old PDP11 operating control computer and software together with the Vax data processing computer and software, has been replaced with a new operating/data acquisition system which runs on a PC under Windows NT4. During the development of the system it became apparent that the new 500MHz computer with 20Gbyte hard disk had sufficient speed/capacity to be able to carry out all the data processing previously carried out by the Vax computer at the same time as managing the radar data acquisition processes. There was therefore no need for an additional computer as first suspected.

Following the design and construction of interface cards and installation of graphics display software, the complete prototype system was finally installed in late February and has been working successfully since then. It is planned to incorporate full redundancy in this new system by the installation of a duplicate system at the MSTR Facility site at Capel Dewi.

Finance:

The cash budget allocated to the MST Radar for 1999/2000 was £120.3k.

The cash spend by the MST Radar for 1999/2000 was £156.6k but £30k of this was offset by income from the data supply contract with the UK Met Office. There was therefore a small overspend of £6.3k for the MST Radar in 1999/2000.

The Full Cash Cost - including notional NERC overheads and capital rental - for the MST Radar for 1999/2000 was £146.8k and this has been cost allocated to all scientific customers accessing its data during the financial year. However it is not possible, as yet, to apportion different unit costs for different MST Radar data products and, hence, the derived unit cost for each data retrieval has been calculated as £2,039. These costs are all attributable to Atmospheric Sciences.

Service Management and Staffing:

The Facility staff and levels of commitment in support of the MST Radar in 1999/2000 were:-

Project Manager: Dr Stuart White	0.50 manyears
Project Engineer: Mr Ken Slater	1.00 manyears
Site Manager: Mr Tony Olewicz	1.00 manyears

6. Further Information

- Annex 1: MST Radar Mission Statement
- Annex 2: MST Radar Publications List
- Annex 3: MST Radar Site Operations Report
- Annex 4: MST Radar Inventory
- Annex 5: Terms of Reference of the NERC Atmospheric Research Facilities Steering Committee

NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

MOLECULAR SPECTROSCOPY FACILITY (MSF)

ANNUAL REPORT

1 APRIL 1999 – 31 MARCH 2000

Space Science and Technology Department
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton, Didcot
Oxon OX11 0QX, U.K.

FRONT COVER IMAGES

	<i>Left</i>	<i>Centre</i>	<i>Right</i>
<i>Upper</i>	Urban air pollution measurements by the University of Oxford and National Physical Laboratory using FT-IR spectroscopy require quantitative spectral data on the pollutant species recorded in the laboratory under controlled conditions at the MSF	High-resolution infra-red absorption cross-sections of pure benzene vapour, an important urban pollutant, recorded at the MSF by the University of Oxford	Deriving meteorological and climate data from atmospheric emission observations by the Met. Office ARIES FT-IR instrument from the Hercules C-130 aircraft uses high-quality data on water vapour and carbon dioxide recorded at the MSF
<i>Middle</i>	Annually-increasing area of Arctic polar stratosphere encountering the low temperatures at which polar stratospheric clouds form, from model calculations by the University of Leeds	The properties of polar stratospheric clouds, observed in the Arctic during much of the 1999/2000 winter, and their impact on ozone chemistry are investigated using a range of spectroscopic instruments	Distinct spectral signatures of sulphate aerosol and mimic polar stratospheric cloud particles from laboratory studies by the University of Oxford, RAL, and the University of Leicester provide essential data for remote sensing
<i>Lower</i>	The impact of short-wave absorption by the atmosphere on global climate is investigated by the University of Reading and RAL using high-resolution spectroscopy and an automatic solar-tracker	Model calculations of short-wave atmospheric transmission have highlighted the importance of oxygen and nitrogen absorption	Monitoring a range of pollutant gas and aerosol particle emissions using spectroscopic techniques is important in developing effective transport systems and reducing pollution in the urban environment

1. SERVICE OBJECTIVES

The Molecular Spectroscopy Facility (MSF) provides unique laboratories and equipment for broadband and high-resolution spectroscopic studies by the UK environmental science community. Briefly, the MSF includes Fourier transform and miniature spectrometers for measurements of the infrared, visible, and ultraviolet absorption, emission, and scattering properties of solid, liquid, gas/vapour, and aerosol samples using a range of sample cells. Spectroscopic data, essential to a number of key NERC science and technology areas, covering the wavelength range from 30 μm to 180 nm, at spectral resolving powers of up to 1 part in a million, and time resolutions as high as 5 μs are acquired and distributed by the MSF. The MSF has been supported through NERC Scientific Services since April 1997.

2. OVERVIEW AND HIGHLIGHTS

This report covers NERC's usage in the period 1 April 1999 to 31 March 2000, which has been an extremely productive year in terms of the number of projects supported, generation of high-quality data, and extensive development of the Facility to meet NERC customer requirements.

The second Fourier transform spectrometer (FTS), a Bruker IFS 66v/S instrument (see photo on left), was successfully installed at the MSF in December 1999 and, after thorough testing by MSF staff, was made available for use by NERC customers starting in January 2000. The key features of the new instrument are full wavelength coverage from 30 μm to 180 nm, vacuum operation, and portability. MSF staff completed interfacing this instrument to new and existing sample cells, allowing simultaneous measurements using both FTS instruments. Three miniature fibre-optic CCD and diode-array spectrometers were acquired and evaluated for environmental science applications including aerosol studies, pollution monitoring, and remote sensing. The PC-based data acquisition systems were customised for simultaneous, automatic measurements using all three spectrometers with split- and bifurcated- optical fibre connections.

A new large-volume, coolable, aerosol cell, and associated aerosol generation, cooling, vacuum, and cooling systems were designed, built, and tested. The cell was essential to a number of measurement campaigns by Oxford and Leicester Universities, and RAL, in which the chemical and physical properties of aqueous sulphate, nitrate, PSC-mimic particles generated in the laboratory were determined. The photo below shows the MSF aerosol experiment comprising the 1-metre high cell, aerosol generation and cooling systems, and data acquisition PC's.

MSF staff collaborated with PIs on all of the NERC projects supported. The very nature of the NERC-supported experiments carried out at the MSF requires the work to be conducted in a collaborative spirit; the running and usage of the Facility is not a turn-key operation. As well as contributing to customers' new proposals, MSF staff were also directly involved in the NERC-science community through being PIs on NERC- and EU- funded projects that made use of the MSF. Data resulting from many MSF studies were made available during 1999/2000 to international agencies including NASA and ESA, and distributed world-wide to scientists via the HITRAN/GEISA-IASI molecular databases and the MSF Internet server.

3. SCIENCE

The achievements of the MSF in supporting excellent, peer-reviewed environmental science through provision of sophisticated equipment, qualified scientific and technical personnel, customer training, and instrument development are highlighted below in descriptions of three NERC-funded research projects which made use of the Facility during 1999/2000. Full details of all nineteen NERC projects supported by the MSF during 1999/2000 are given in Annex 10.

Absorption Cross-Sections of Near-Infrared Bands of Oxygen – University of Reading/Observations of the Near-IR and Visible Transmittance of the Atmosphere: Application to Shortwave Radiative Forcing - Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. In these projects, current problems in our understanding of short-wave radiative forcing of climate are addressed by the powerful combination of near-infrared and visible observations of the atmosphere from the ground using Fourier transform spectrometry and sophisticated atmospheric radiative transfer

calculations at Reading. Laboratory studies using the MSF have provided valuable temperature-dependent cross-section data on broadband absorbers such as the collision-induced absorption by oxygen/nitrogen mixtures at 1.06 and 1.27 μm . Upgrades of the short-pathlength absorption cell and comprehensive safety assessments by MSF staff enabled the Reading group to extend measurements on pure oxygen to pressures as high as 5 atmospheres. Analyses of these data are leading to a better understanding of climate processes, and will help validate a simple oxygen absorption model (see figure on left) developed by MSF staff.

Photolysis Quantum Yields and Photoabsorption Cross-Sections for Bromine Nitrate – University College London/University of Reading. Bromine nitrate is an important species in the stratosphere because it takes part in catalytic cycles that lead to ozone destruction. In order to fully understand the role it plays in the stratospheric ozone budget, it is essential to accurately determine its absorption cross-section. Measurements were made at the MSF on the temperature-dependence of the UV absorption in the 250-400 nm range for pure BrONO_2 vapour, and also for the chlorine-containing stratospheric species ClONO_2 and OClO . The studies utilised the new UV spectroscopy facility to extend the measurement range to 220 nm, and a coolable glass cell previously developed by ICSTM London and MSF staff for studies on another highly-reactive stratospheric species, reactive nitric acid vapour. The studies complement other NERC-funded projects, also supported by the MSF, which are providing remotely-sensed data on the distributions of bromine radical species and upper atmosphere ozone. Example data derived from the UV measurements on BrONO_2 are shown below.

Weak Lines in the Water Vapour Spectrum: An FT Study of the Visible and Near-IR - ICSTM London. There is a significant discrepancy between modelled and observed atmospheric absorption even for the clear sky. Statistical analysis provides a prima facie case that some of the missing opacity is due to weak absorption lines in the visible and near-infrared water vapour spectrum that are not included in the atmospheric models. The central part of this project is to make new laboratory measurements of very high sensitivity using the Bruker Fourier transform spectrometer and long pathlength absorption cell (LPAC) at the MSF to observe these lines and quantify their contribution to atmospheric absorption. Using the new set of 'White' optics for the LPAC, coated for >99% reflectivity in the 700-1100 nm region, and customised detection systems the ICSTM researchers were able to extend the optical path-length for broadband high-resolution spectroscopy to over 800 metres. The installation and calibration of humidity sensors

in the LPAC by MSF staff allowed the absolute amount concentration of water vapour to be determined to high accuracy. Newly-identified weak water vapour lines are indicated in a high-resolution spectrum plot shown on the left. Collaboration with the NERC-funded theory group at University College London is already generating a much-improved database on water vapour and resolving the short-wave atmospheric absorption problem.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

During 1999/2000 funding was successfully obtained from the NSS capital budget for state-of-the-art vacuum upgrades to the LPAC and other optical systems. The design and installation of these new oil-free systems will be carried out by MSF staff early in 1999/2000 so that the improvements benefit the maximum number of NERC-funded customers. Other development targets already identified (and funded) to meet customers needs include far-infrared spectroscopy upgrades which will be utilised by Queen Mary and Westfield College, London to record long-pathlength, temperature-dependent spectra of water vapour for remote-sensing applications. Enhancements to the temperature, pressure, and humidity data acquisition/control systems and improved Internet-based data distribution will benefit all MSF customers. Laser safe areas will be set up in the MSF to allow customers to utilise laser devices in their studies.

5. SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

(i) *Numbers and Percentage of α-Graded Proposals Supported* - Seventeen new applications for MSF time were reviewed by the MSF Steering Committee (MSFSC) during 1999/2000, and a further 2 applications were received. Nineteen projects involving nine institutions holding NERC grants and/or studentships were supported during the 160 days purchased by NERC. The distribution and percentages of MSFSC and NERC peer-review committee (PRC) grades for the reviewed and supported projects are as follows:

New Application MSFSC Grades									
α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*	R	Other	Total
1	13	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	17
Supported Application MSFSC Grades (+PRC Grades)									
α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*	R	Other	Total
(+1)	10 (+4)	1 (+1)	0	0	0	0	0	2	19

New Application MSFSC Grades

Supported Application MSFSC Grades

For six of the seven supported projects that were accepted prior to the adoption of the MSF by NSS, peer-review committee (PRC) grades are given instead. The duration of each project at the MSF ranged from two days up to three weeks, with a total of 32 visits to the MSF.

(ii) *Percentage Distribution and Cost of Projects* - The percentage distribution and cost of projects according to science area and NERC ENRI's are as follows:

ESTB		ASTB		MSTB		TFSTB		EOEG		SBASG	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
0	Nil	50	62.05	0	Nil	0	Nil	50	62.05	0	Nil

Biodiversity		Env. Risk /Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resource Management		Pollution & Waste		Other	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
0	Nil	25	31.03	25	31.03	3	3.72	22	27.30	25	31.03

(iii) *Publications Arising from MSF Usage for 1999* - User feedback and literature searches identified 8 refereed journal publications, 10 non-refereed publications/reports/conference proceedings, and 11 presentations at international conferences. The publications identified relate to NERC Science and Technology Board areas as:

	EO	Marine	T/F	Arch	Earth	Atmos
No. Pubs.	13	0	0	0	0	16

(iv) *Targets And Milestones* - During 1999/2000 the total MSF capacity available for supporting the NERC community (given the level of funding received from NERC) was 75% of capacity (213 working days) or 160 days. This was used completely in support of NERC projects.

	Customers	Facility Development	Planned Downtime	Instrument Downtime	Total
No. Days	140	15	3	2	160

(v) *Financial Details* - The NERC budget for the MSF during 1999/2000 was as follows:

	Full Economic Cost	Unit Cost (Daily Rate)	Recurrent	Capital
£k	213.47	0.776	124.10	89.37

(vi) *Service Management and Staffing* - The MSF is staffed by a full-time scientist and a full-time technician who are essential to ensure customers conduct their experiments using the complex, sophisticated MSF equipment safely and effectively. In financial year 1999/2000 NERC funded 75% of these posts (i.e. 1.5 staff years), and 7.5% of that of the Facility manager.

2.2 EARTH SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

**NERC RESEARCH USING PULSED
NEUTRON SCATTERING AT ISIS**

A.D. TAYLOR

**1999 – 2000 Annual Report to NERC
on the ISIS service supported through
the NERC/CCLRC Service Level Agreement.**

**Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
CCLRC
Chilton, Didcot, OX11 0QX**

June 2000

SUMMARY REPORT FOR FY 1999/2000

1. Service Objectives

The service provided by ISIS in supplying pulsed neutrons and muons for NERC-approved research is defined in the Service Level Agreement (SLA) operating under the Umbrella Agreement between NERC and CCLRC. In summary, CCLRC provides beam time on the ISIS instruments as well as associated scientific, technical and administrative services to advance NERC's research which requires the use of neutron and muon beams.

2. Overview and Highlights

The ISIS Facility is a source of pulsed neutrons for the study of the structure and dynamics in condensed matter. Neutrons, which are scattered by the nucleus of an atom, are a unique probe in that they have wavelengths comparable to interatomic spacings, yielding information on structure, and energies, which are similar to atomic and electronic processes in materials, which give rise to information on dynamics. By contrast with reactor sources of neutrons for diffraction and spectroscopy, pulsed neutron sources collect data in time-of-flight using large, fixed detector arrays. The whole of the diffraction pattern is collected simultaneously at a constant resolution allowing rapid data collection times to be achieved for studies of thermal expansion and phase transitions. Pulsed neutrons can uniquely access the extremely high values of wavevector transfer which is important for studies of glasses/liquids and allows the decorrelation of the Debye-Waller factor from site occupancy in the study of cation ordering in mineral phases. Furthermore, the advantage of fixed geometry instrumentation is that specialised sample environment can be more easily designed and this advantage is particularly exploited in the area of high-pressure crystallography where pressures up to 30GPa have been achieved. Simultaneous measurements of the axial and radial diffraction pattern from cylindrical samples positioned at 45° to the incident beam can be made with fixed detectors placed at $\pm 90^\circ 2\theta$. This geometry has been exploited to study natural ultramafic rocks under uniaxial load with the future possibility of moving to triaxial load cells and carrying out simple in-situ rock mechanics.

3. Science

The NERC science programme at ISIS has traditionally been in mineralogy and we first highlight two examples which illustrate the use of high pressure and rapid data collection.

Silica is a model system among materials that are important in both geological and the physical sciences. It exhibits a rich phase diagram, containing both stable and meta-stable phases, and, because of its importance, it is necessary to understand and characterise new silica phases. It is well-known that the cristobalite polymorph undergoes a pressure-induced phase transition at ~ 1.5 GPa to a monoclinic structure. Data collected on HiPr has deduced the crystal structure of this phase for the first time. Previous work using XRD had inferred that the phase transition occurred as a displacive instability of the ambient temperature tetragonal phase with the soft mode identified using group theoretical methods. Dove and co-workers, using both empirical model and electronic structure calculations with considerations from group theory, have refuted these deductions. A high-pressure structure was derived from the modelling studies and was subsequently confirmed by the high-pressure powder neutron diffraction measurements as being derived by a displacive distortion of the high-temperature aristotype phase of cristobalite.

Lawsonite, with the chemical formula $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, occurs in high-pressure, low-temperature metamorphic rocks, it has a high water content of ~ 11 wt% and, for a hydrous phase, a comparatively high density of ~ 3.1 gcm⁻³. Lawsonite may be responsible for the

transportation of water into the earth's mantle via subduction zones. In order to improve the understanding of the mechanisms driving the phase transitions in lawsonite, which involve changes in H-bonding, the temperature variation of the lattice constants and structure have been investigated using a perdeuterated sample on HRPD. From data collected in small temperature increments from 2K to 500K, Carpenter and co-workers have shown that anomalies in the lattice parameters exist indicating phase transitions at 145K and 273K which are in good agreement with specific heat capacity data. The lattice parameter data, analysed in terms of the spontaneous strain, showed almost Landau-like behaviour throughout the temperature range. Below room temperature the behaviour was found to be tricritical and below 145K could be fitted with a 2-4-6 potential. This behaviour allowed the interpretation of atomic displacements as being continuous for framework oxygen atoms and one of the deuterium atoms. More discontinuous behaviour was observed for the structurally distinct deuterium atoms.

A more recent development has been the growing realisation that neutron diffraction can provide unique information in the field of rock physics. Covey-Crump and collaborators have used the ENGIN instrument to obtain information on strain partitioning between orthopyroxene and olivine under an applied uniaxial load using the lattice parameters of the two phases to act as internal strain gauges. The fixed geometry of ENGIN with large detector banks at $\pm 90^\circ 2\theta$ simultaneously allows the measurement of axial and radial strain from the rock core which can then be compared to the bulk properties derived from strain gauges attached to the sample. Initial results from a lherzolite suggest that the strain is homogeneously distributed between the two phases as the volumetric strain as a function of applied load for the two phases approximately overlies one another.

4. Future Developments

Plans to replace the ISIS pre-injector with a radiofrequency quadrupole (RFQ) are well advanced and will improve the linac efficiency. The Second Harmonic RF project, which aims to increase the ISIS operating current from $200\mu\text{A}$ to $300\mu\text{A}$ is well into its R&D phase, with hardware currently under construction. There is a continuous programme of development on the ISIS neutron and muon instruments, supported by funds from the Research Councils, the Joint Research Equipment Initiative and International Partners. The timescales for the major developments are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ISIS Instrument Development Programme

5. Summary of Performance Information

5.1 ISIS Accelerator and Instruments

The productivity of ISIS continues to increase from year to year and F.Y. 1999/2000 was its most successful year to date. This is exemplified by Figure 2 showing the annual integrated current delivered by ISIS from its inception.

Figure 2. ISIS Annual Integrated Currents

The instrument suite has now reached saturation; see Figure 3 showing the ISIS layout. Instrument downtime is typically only a few percent, though when compounded with moderator failure this increases to 4.2%. Failure of experiments due to instrument loss time remains rare.

Figure 3. Instrument Layout in the ISIS experimental hall.

There is an active programme of instrument refurbishment and currently the detector complements on HRPD and SXD diffractometers are undergoing major upgrades. There is also a substantial and continuous investment in new sample environment equipment. The next new instrument (ENGIN X) will share the same beam port as HRPD and future instruments can only be accommodated by replacing old instruments. This was necessary for the first time this year when LAD was replaced by GEM.

5.2 User Programmes

The ISIS selection panels received 10 experimental proposals from 6 NERC groups in 1999/2000; details are provided in Table 1.2 in Annex 1. Of the 31 days requested, 29 days were allocated in this peer review process, a remarkably high success rate in comparison with other programmes.

User satisfaction is gauged through a survey in which all users are requested to comment on the whole range of services provided during their stay at the laboratory. This covers the technical and scientific advice they receive, their views on the suitability of the equipment provided, and other more general services such as food and accommodation. The results of the latest available data are shown in Figure 1.1 in Annex 1; scientific and technical support are consistently outstanding. These surveys are particularly helpful in informing management on the areas which require priority action.

5.3 Publications

In calendar year 1999, there have been 9 refereed publications all within the NERC Science Area, Earth Science and Technology; see section 1.6 in Annex 1.

5.4 Financial

The NERC Neutron and Muon Programme at ISIS is funded on a unit cost basis; in F.Y.1999/2000 this was £11,823 per instrument day. The total annual funding was £272,097; details of how this was allocated are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Cost Allocations at ISIS, F.Y. 1999/2000.

University/Institute	Department	Name of User (Surname First)	NERC Ref No	Unit 1	Unit 2	£'s
Cambridge	Earth Sciences	Redfern Dr S A T	GR3/11741	3		35469
Cambridge	Earth Sciences	Redfern Dr S A T	GR9/4038	3		35469
Open University	Earth Sciences	Palmer Dr D C	GR9/4497	1.5		17735
U.C. London	Geol. Sciences	Wood Dr I G		5		59115
Cambridge	Earth Sciences	Carpenter Dr M A		4		47292
Cambridge	Earth Sciences	Redfern Dr S A T		6.514	2,486	77017
RAL, CLRC	ISIS	Knight Mr K S		0	7	0
						272097

Synchrotron Radiation in UK Natural Environment Research.

Fourth report to NERC on work supported by the NERC/CCLRC Service Level Agreement: the period April 1999 - March 2000.

July 2000

**Daresbury Laboratory,
CCLRC,
Warrington WA4 4AD**

DIRECTOR'S INTRODUCTION

The NERC programme using the SRS continued to be highly successful in 1999/2000. The studies enabled by synchrotron radiation currently lie in earth and terrestrial/freshwater science, but previous projects have included atmospheric science and there is strong potential to impact on marine science and science-based archaeology: the SRS and future synchrotron radiation sources thus are likely to play an important part in NERC's fulfilling its wide-ranging mission.

Recognising the past successes and future potential, the 1999 NERC Services Review awarded the SRS the second-highest ranking of all NERC's 34 services, with a recommendation for increased funding. It was a great disappointment, therefore, that the Earth Science and Technology Board has not been able to follow that recommendation, and it is doubly disappointing that changes in access mechanism by the EPSRC - the majority user of the SRS - have had serious knock-on effects in cutting the total use made of synchrotron radiation in the UK. The Office of Science and Technology have now taken up the challenge of ensuring that best use is made of the country's shared central facilities whilst also ensuring that their delivery is efficient and cost-effective.

The long-awaited decision on the site of DIAMOND, the successor to the SRS is welcome in that the project should be able to move forward but also poses problems with the enforced long-term transfer of synchrotron radiation expertise from Daresbury Laboratory to the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. NERC-supported scientists should be major users of the SRS during its remaining seven (or more) years of life and look forward to exploiting the even brighter beams from DIAMOND in the future. The agreed funding of 'Envirosync', a multi-collaborator project for UK environmental scientists to visit and carry out experiments at other SR sources world wide, will permit the NERC community to be well-prepared to define instrumental and experimental requirements for the future of the SRS and DIAMOND, and thus to confront the environmental challenges in NERC's mission.

Professor David Norman
Director, Synchrotron Radiation Science

NERC Synchrotron Research Programme for 1999-2000.

1. Service Objectives. The main purpose of the NERC/DL Service Level Agreement (SLA) is to provide synchrotron beamtime *via* a 'direct access' arrangement, mainly for research student training, new users, technique development and exploratory experiments in new research areas. The last three categories are aimed at providing a foundation for 'normal' research grant applications. It is clear that virtually all aspects of the highly successful environmental and Earth sciences synchrotron research programme have depended initially on the availability of 'direct access' funding. The continuation of this type of funding is crucial over the next few years as it will be a flexible and cost-effective way of supporting the planning, design and development of the new 'state of the art' environmental research facilities to be provided on the new synchrotron.

2. Overview and Highlights.

2.i. Context. The natural environment research work at the SRS currently impacts on three of NERC's five environmental and natural resource issues through which it focuses its research activities. The largest synchrotron research area, 'Molecular Environmental Science', is concerned with molecular scale investigations of minerals, soils, colloids, waters, and plant and animal matter, as well as 'contaminants' introduced by human activity. The other main area is the study of deep crust and mantle processes using *in situ* experiments at controlled T and P in specially designed reaction vessels. The NERC-funded programme is firmly established.

2.ii. Direct access. In December 1998, DL applied to NERC for a 3 year extension of the Block Grant to continue direct access to the SRS from 1999 to 2002. This proposal was very highly rated by the NSS Services Review Group and recommended for funding at the level of about £200K rising to £233K per annum. Despite this success, the period 1999/2000 involved significantly less beamtime because funding provided by NERC for direct access was substantially reduced following a decision of the EST Board to phase out support over 3 years. This severe cut coincided with an increase of charges (to £6000/day), and with the total amount of direct access time allocated by DL being reduced to fall in with EPSRC's ticket policy wishes.

2.iii. Community. NERC-supported work continues at the forefront of molecular environmental and mineral physics research with groups at the Universities of Aberdeen, Bristol, Manchester, Leeds, Liverpool John Moores, Nottingham, Oxford, and Natural History Museum, London. Research student training plays an important part in the research programme (Annex VIb).

2.iv. Research areas. These are summarised in Annex IIIa, with background information on equipment and techniques. Scientific reports from the NERC synchrotron research community are given in Annex V for projects supported by direct access and 'tickets'. This year, reports are included for work carried out by UK synchrotron researchers at leading 3rd generation sources abroad (Annex Vc). Such work shows how the home-based environmental research programme is likely to evolve when the new UK source comes on-stream in 2006-7.

2.v. Highlights. The main success was the JIF award to Professor D.J. Vaughan and Manchester colleagues for establishing a Centre for Molecular Environmental Sciences: synchrotron research plays a major part in this programme. Also noteworthy was the appearance in *Science* of a paper by NERC student N. Chinnery and his supervisors on an *in situ* study of '10 angstrom' phase stability at high pressure showing that it is a possible hydrous mineral in the upper mantle.

3. Science highlights.

3.i. Hydrated iron oxides as radionuclide and toxic element sorbents. Mineral surfaces are extremely important in limiting the mobility and bioavailability of toxic metals. An ongoing project at Daresbury involves assessment of natural attenuation schemes which might be cost-effective means of site remediation. Recent work has shown that the hydrated iron oxide goethite sorbs

5.ii.a % distribution and costs of projects (includes both tickets and direct access).

Earth Sci		Atm Sci		Mar Sci		Terr Fw Sci		Earth Obs		Sci B Arch	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
77	286	-	-	-	-	23	72	-	-	-	-

5.ii.b % distribution and costs of all projects according to ENRIs.

Biodiversity		Env Risks/Haz		Global Change		Nat Res Man.		Pollution/waste	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
-	-	15	64	-	-	39	84	46	210

5.iii. Publications and presentations for calendar year 1999 (annexes VI c, d; VIII).

Journal papers with 1999 dates are listed in annex VIc and total 25 (21 minus upper atmospheric physics papers). Four Ph.D. theses were submitted and approved in 1999-2000.

Summary data including NERC science areas [23 refereed (2 non-refereed) papers] :

	Earth Sci	Atm Sci	Mar Sci	Terr Fw Sci	Earth Obs	Sci B Arch
No.of Pubs.	18 (2)	4	-	1	-	-

Conference contributions are listed in annex VI d and total 21.

5.iv. Targets and milestones.

5.iv.a. *Envirosync.* Researchers are planning to visit appropriate state-of-the-art third generation synchrotrons to carry out new types of experiment, to gain experience and to expedite plans for the design of environmental beamlines on the NSP. A paper describing the environmental requirements on the NSP has recently been submitted to NERC and OST.

5.iv.b. *Service level performance indicators are given in Annex VIIc.* Storage ring and station reliability is summarised below:

Reliability of source and dipole magnets	Reliability of source and wiggler magnets	Minimum beam lifetime of 15 hours	Reliability of station equipment
90%	85%	95%	95%

5.iv.c. *User satisfaction data and other output performance indicators.*

Questionnaires. Users assessments summarised here are from the whole synchrotron community (Annex VIIa and b). % of high satisfaction ratings are given below:

April – October 1999, AP33.		October 1999 – April 2000, AP 34	
Lab as a whole	Station	Lab as a whole	Station
73%	81%	83%	85%

Honours. Dr Alison Pawley received the 1999 Hey Medal of the Mineralogical Society of Great Britain and Ireland. Professor Vaughan was elected President of the European Mineralogical Union.

5.v. *Financial details.* The cost of beamtime for the reporting period is £6000 per day. Note that the synchrotron runs for 24 hrs, 7 days a week. The NERC SLA annual payment of £130K covered 22 days access in DL periods AP33 and 34, however 26 days of direct access beamtime were provided by DL. Note that tightening up of arrangements for allocating direct access time has led to a very significant cut in the beamtime 'subsidy' provided by DL for the environmental programme (37 days in 1998/99). Nominal costs per research area are in 5ii.a and b, above.

In addition to direct access time, 'tickets' awarded on NERC grants have been used by Drs Pawley and Henderson (GR3/11181, 11723), Wogelius and Vaughan (GR3/11979), Bailey (GR8/03654) and Cotter-Howells (GR04513).

5.vi. *Daresbury staff contributions and collaborations.* Experimental facility managers advise on preparation of applications as necessary. Important collaborative research continues with Dr S.M Clark (high-pressure and *in situ* experiments) and Dr F. Mosselmans (specialist XAS experiments). Professor Cernik (Assistant Director, DL) administers the Environmental Science programme on behalf of the Director and also has acted as Chairman of the ESSAP.

Figure 1. Time-resolved energy-dispersive XRD data for the formation of goethite from '2-line' ferrihydrite at 120°C and pH 13.7. The minimum in the background hump is due to data from 2 detectors being combined. The presence of Al slows down the reaction kinetics.

Figure 3. Soft X-ray images of frozen hydrated *Chlamydomonas* cell. S = X-ray absorbing spheres, F = flagella, C = chloroplast, P = pyrenoid. Tuning the radiation shows that the spheres are oxygen rich. Such spheres are not observed by TEM. The image shown combines two frames.

Figure 2. Structure of monoclinic, high-pressure lawsonite at 120 kbar and 25°C viewed: (a) along [001] and (b) along [010], also showing the direction of shearing associated with the phase transition. Octahedra: chains of Al-O₆; dark tetrahedra: Si-O₄; red spheres: Ca; and green spheres: O in H₂O.

NIGL Annual Report 1999-2000

ANNUAL REPORT
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL
ISOTOPE GEOSCIENCES LABORATORY FACILITIES

for the period
1ST APRIL 1999 to 31ST MARCH 2000

Prof R Parrish, Head NIGL

2 May 2000

NERC/IF/190

Overview

The NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory is one of the largest and most comprehensive environmental geoscience isotope laboratories in the United Kingdom. NIGL has both stable and radiogenic isotope analytical facilities, including the new generation of plasma ionisation multi-collector instruments. The objective of NIGL is to provide comprehensive training and state of the art research involving isotope measurements on topics in the environmental, life and geosciences, and to promote good practice in the use and interpretation of the data. The research programme serves UK universities and it underpins the core programmes of the British Geological and British Antarctic Surveys, and other NERC institutes.

During the year, 23 new projects were approved by the NERC Isotope Geosciences Facilities Steering Committee and a further 7 by the BGS-NIGL programme committee. A total of 121 projects were worked on during the year, most of a multi-year nature. A total of 33 UK PhD student received training during the year. The programmes that are in highest demand continue to be U-Th-Pb geochronology, stable isotope measurements in support of palaeoclimate research, and pollution research using the new plasma ionisation instrumentation. Commissioned income has increased substantially compared to previous years, mainly for projects in geochronology and heavy metal pollution research.

Research carried out during the year yielded many exciting results. Diatom oxygen isotope analysis was developed and applied to reveal changes in palaeoclimate regimes in terrestrial lakes; NIGL is the only UK laboratory with this capability. Using laser micro-sampling, NIGL has developed a U-Th-Pb method of dating to rival the best techniques otherwise available for in situ dating, and applied this to the erosion of the Himalaya. The new plasma ionisation instruments were used to reveal the Hf isotopic evolution of the world's largest Archaean craton, the Superior Province of southern Canada. Major progress has been made in using new isotope techniques to reveal patterns of heavy metal mobility in soils from contaminated urban sites, in conjunction with electron microprobe studies. More information on these and other highlights is contained within this report.

The instrumentation at NIGL has been upgraded with the delivery of the second plasma ionisation Axiom multicollector mass spectrometer and a 266nm laser sampling system, and with the rebuilding of one of its older stable isotope instruments. All other instruments continue to perform adequately, but two of the stable isotope and one thermal ionisation mass spectrometer have required extensive maintenance and standardisation, and need to be replaced within the next few years. Success in awarding of EU-TMR and NERC URGENT thematic grants has allowed NIGL to attract several additional post-doctoral researchers. One senior scientific position was converted to a support scientist.

In 1999 a 5-year review of NIGL was conducted, which endorsed a further 5-year mandate. The expert scientific review group made a number of recommendations that have been incorporated into the new NIGL strategic plan, a detailed 5 year forward plan adopted by both the BGS Board and the ESTB in 2000. NIGL was integrated into the new structure of the British Geological Survey, effective 1 April 2000, though retaining a large degree of autonomy and overall control of the budget.

Selected Science Highlights.

Work was conducted on >100 projects during the year in a great breadth of topics involving life, environmental and geo-science. In this main body of text for the annual report, only a few of the highlights will be reported; other project highlights are listed in annex 4.

West Greenland palaeoclimate. Western Greenland has numerous lakes which have enormous potential for palaeoclimatic reconstructions. The records derived from lakes are complimentary to those derived from ice and marine cores in that the lakes are reflecting regional climate variability and varying precipitation. Such alternative proxy records are necessary because the ice-core records show limited variability during the Holocene. Oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) isotope records from laminated sediment cores show that apart from inferred wetter periods around 7500-8500 and 5000-6000 years BP, this area has always been drier than today. An extremely rapid change in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data started at around 7500 years BP suggests a marked arid phase causing substantial evaporation and lowering of lake levels. Our data suggest that at a regional scale climate was quite dynamic in the early Holocene, perhaps representing an interplay between changing ice masses and processes in the Davis Straits. (*with University of Liverpool and University of Copenhagen*).

Attenuation of ammonium pollution. Ammonium (ammonia at higher pH) is a major toxic by-product of landfill degradation. Bacteria can transform ammonium to harmless nitrogen gas, but there is little information on the 'natural' occurrence of this process. A joint study with the BGS therefore examined the $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ ratios of ammonium and nitrate in water within and surrounding a completed domestic landfill site in chalk in Cambridgeshire. In part of the landfill and immediately surrounding chalk $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ ratios in nitrate were higher than those in the ammonium. Modelling of the likely effects of isotopic fractionation suggested that this could only be explained by a process of nitrification and denitrification. The study has therefore provided valuable preliminary evidence of natural bacterial attenuation of ammonium pollution. (*with BGS*)

Tin isotopes in archaeological materials. A small-scale pilot study into the use of Sn isotopes in archaeology attempted to assess whether tin isotope variation could be useful to science-based archaeology. The data collected on the Plasma 54 during this pilot study represents the highest precision and most accurate Sn data obtained in any laboratory by either PIMMS or TIMS methods and shows evidence for variations in Sn isotopic compositions within archaeological artifacts. This opens up the prospect for using Sn isotopes to provenance archaeological bronze artifacts and investigate ancient trade routes. (*with University of Oxford*)

Development of capability for *in situ* U-Th-Pb dating on a micro-scale. NIGL has used its new laser ablation micro-sampling device attached to the Plasma Ionisation Multicollector Mass Spectrometers to develop a rapid and precise technique to date tiny regions in crystals such as zircon and monazite. This method can produce a high precision (<2-3%) U-Th-Pb date on regions as small as 30 micro-meters within these crystals. This advance allows our methodology to be widely applied to the dating of tectonic and erosional processes and compete successfully with the much more widely used and expensive ion microprobe techniques pioneered by the Australian National University. (*NIGL staff and an 1851 Commission Fellow*)

Patterns of erosion in the Himalaya of south Asia. An important problem in the earth system is to understand the tectonic and metamorphic events associated with the Asia-India collision, and their impact on topography and erosion. Recent work has elucidated the age of Eocene intrusive and metamorphic events in the Karakoram-High Himalaya (Hunza, Pakistan; Mt. Everest, Nepal), and uncovered a previously unknown Jurassic episode of crustal melting in the Hindu Kush that affected the southern margin of Asia prior to India-Asia collision. A detailed study of the erosion of the Himalaya in India has revealed that detritus from the early Miocene Himalayan metamorphism does not appear in the foreland record until the latest Miocene, about 10 Ma following the principal metamorphic events. This suggests that vigorous uplift and erosion of the range accelerated in Late Miocene time. (*with universities of Oxford, Cambridge, Leicester and Edinburgh*).

Summary of Performance Information and Publications

STUDENT TRAINING AND RESEARCH

A total of 33 UK PhD students were supported on approved projects. Most of these are NERC funded studentships (including CASE). Fifteen other visitors received training or visited during the year from overseas. Annex 3.2 contains details of all students, post-doctoral researchers and visitors to NIGL, with the titles of their project research and institute affiliation. These are also classified according to the NIGL facility that is most relevant.

PROJECT GRADING AND PROGRESS OF PROJECT WORK

In the 99-00 year, the Isotope Geoscience Facilities Steering Committee approved 23 new proposals for work to be conducted at NIGL, out of 32 submitted proposals (see table below). Annex 3.1 contains details of proposal applications received during the 99-00 year. A table of progress on existing projects is part of Annex 3.5.

Grading of proposals 1999 - 2000

Proposals	α -4	α 3/4	α -3	α -2/3	α -2	α -1/2	α -1	PILOT	R*	CASE	TOTAL
Applications graded:	2	5	8	4	2	0	1	1	5	4	32
Applications accepted:	2	5	8	3	0	0	0	1	0	4	23

NOTES: R* implies that resubmission was invited.

PUBLISHED OUTPUT

Staff of NIGL were involved in the publication of 53 refereed research papers (international journals and book chapters). A further 4 non-refereed publications were produced, in addition to numerous internal reports. These are listed in Annex 3.4.

SUMMARY OF TIME ALLOCATION DURING 1999 - 2000

A summary of time spent on various activities is listed below.

Category	Half-day units NIGL NERC staff ¹	Half-day units Non-NERC staff ²
NIGLSC approved active projects ³	2,022	379
Institute core programme projects	485	22
NERC+EU approved grants	843	242
Commissioned projects	366	28
Approved in house projects	186	0
Essential equipment maintenance	559	39
Sub-total devoted to project science	4,461	710
Administration, marketing, public relations, project planning, technique development, QA/QC/H&S, leave	5,301	481
Total time	9,762	1,191

¹ Includes staff supported on science budget and including a NERC grant supported scientist

² Includes students, visitors, BAS staff, and post-doctoral researchers supported by non-NERC funds

³ A breakdown of TAR units according to facilities has not yet been completed as of 28 April 2000.

The modest increase over the previous year in the proportion of total staff time spent on administration is related to increased effort in Health and Safety procedural compliance, and to an increased burden of BGS administration and management procedures.

NERC RADIOCARBON LABORATORY

Annual Report - 1st April 1999 to 31st March 2000

Executive Summary

1. Service Objectives

The NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory (RCL) is part of the Carbon Geodynamics Group based at the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC), East Kilbride. It provides carbon isotope analyses for research carried out by members of staff at Higher Education Institutions, NERC Centre/Surveys and any other persons who are eligible to be awarded NERC Research Grants and/or Training Awards. Commissions and repayment work are also accepted.

2. Overview and Highlights

The RCL has enjoyed a successful year, with no significant periods of downtime and with turn-round times being similar to, or better than, last year. This was achieved despite two instances when members of staff were absent for extended periods due to ill-health or maternity leave. The technical staff is to be commended on their willingness to provide cover during such periods of absence and their ready acceptance of reallocated duties and responsibilities.

The smooth running of the laboratory was ensured by the supervision of Professor Fallick, and the advice and scientific guidance available when required, from Dr Harkness (employed on a part-time basis as Head of Carbon Geodynamics).

Following an application to the **Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF)** by a consortium of the RCL, SUERC, Universities of Glasgow and Edinburgh funding of *ca* £3.9M was awarded in November 1999 for "**An Accelerator Mass Spectrometer Facility for ¹⁴C and Cosmogenic Isotope Analysis Applications**". Good progress has been made since then in both the new building and accelerator procurement fronts. Location of the AMS facility close to the RCL will strengthen collaborative links with the RCL's existing users and attract new collaborators to the facility. Development work will be made easier, and training opportunities made available, for a new generation of Earth and environmental scientists.

A major highlight, under the heading **Communicating Science to the Public and Publicity activities (ANNEX O2)**, was filming at the RCL for a programme produced by 3BM Television in the series "Catastrophe", on the eruption of the Krakatoa volcano, and which was transmitted by Channel 4 during July 1999. This required collaboration with Professor Haraldur Sigurdsson, University of Rhode Island, on the dating of samples from the vicinity of Krakatoa volcano (funded at commercial rates by 3BM).

The NERC/EC funded project (GR/09/03389 & SMT4-CT98-2265) **Fourth International Radiocarbon Inter-comparison (FIRI)**, involving European collaborators and Prof E M Scott (Glasgow Univ.), Dr G Cook (SUERC), Dr Harkness and Dr Bryant (RCL) is progressing as planned. A paper entitled "Sample requirements and design of an inter-laboratory trial for radiocarbon laboratories" was presented at the **8th International Conference on Accelerator Mass Spectrometry**, Vienna, Austria during September 1999.

3. Science

Three EC funded projects undertaken by CEH institutes have involved the RCL in the AMS and radiometric analyses of samples from sites throughout the EU and extending into the Czech Republic.

IFE Windermere - PROTOs: PROduction and Transport of Organic Solutes - effects of natural climatic variation. An EC commission under Framework IV (ENV4-CT95-0010) co-ordinated by Dr E Tipping required the analysis of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in different soil horizons and in adjacent streamwater from sites in Norway, Germany, Spain and the UK to provide an insight into the sources of DOC and rates of production.

ITE Merlewood - MEMO: Effects of Afforestation of Agricultural Land on Heavy Metal Mobility in Soils. An investigation of the effects of land management systems necessitating the analysis of soil and soil water samples from Swedish and Scottish sites.

ITE Merlewood - CANIF: CARbon and Nitrogen In Forest Soils. An EC funded project (ENV4-CT95-0053-CEC) involving European partners: UK partners, Dr A F Harrison, ITE and Dr Harkness at RCL. The results of this project, now completed, are to be included in a book chapter (in prep.) "Annual carbon and nitrogen fluxes in soils along the European forest transect, determined using ^{14}C -bomb", Harrison, A E, Harkness, D D, Rowland, A P, Garnett, J S and Bacon, P J.

This commissioned and collaborative work is a result of the RCL's long-standing interest in carbon flux studies and the applications of "Bomb ^{14}C " as a tracer. Each project required input by the RCL staff during the preparation of reports, data analysis and interpretation.

One salient highlight of the broader research programme (illustrated in Fig 1, from Huang *et al* 1999 in the *Soil Science Society of America Journal*) was the demonstration that saturated alkanes (aliphatic hydrocarbons) in British upland soils are significantly older than total organic carbon (TOC): the ^{14}C contents of aliphatic hydrocarbons reflect the age of a passive-fraction of carbon.

4. Future Developments

Much of the RCL's future developments will be closely linked to the successful JIF bid for the AMS facility. Planned developments include a capability in compound-specific isotope analysis (CSIA) whereby individual compound classes, rather than bulk organic matter, are dated. A new dedicated low blank line for target preparation from small samples is also envisaged.

RCL staff will become more involved in collaborative work and students and scientists will be encouraged to visit the laboratory. The former is already being addressed, with applications having been made to NERC for Research Grants to fund collaborative projects and a number of proposals for EC funding being discussed which involve the RCL (ANNEX M4).

5. Summary of performance information

Responsive Mode Programme: Support Provided

The NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory Steering Committee (RCL-SC), under the Chairmanship of Professor Mike Walker (until June 1999) and subsequently Professor David Keen (ANNEX M2), assigned scientific priorities to requests for NERC funded dating via the responsive mode programme. It reviewed 63 applications (ANNEXES M5 i) and ii)) of which nine were graded R* and required the submission of additional information before grading and allocation of analytical support. Eight were rejected and nine submissions were accepted "in-principle" ie forewarning the

facility and the committee of projects that were likely to request dating support when the project got underway. Thirty-six (ie 57% of total) were provided with dating support which committed the RCL to the provision of 638 ¹⁴C measurements (442 by the AMS technique and 196 by radiometric counting); one application for two dates was considered to be a "Pilot Study". Distribution of the support provided, as a percentage of alpha graded science is summarised in Table 1. Throughout the year a grading at $\alpha 2$ was set as the threshold level for full financial support; no applications fell between this grade and outright rejection. It is intended to raise this threshold above $\alpha 3$, primarily by encouragement of higher quality applications, although bids for a small "service" component of a larger project can only rarely attract highest grades.

Table 1: Number and % by a-grade of applications and no samples by analysis method

Alpha grade	No of Projects	% Applications supported	Numbers of analyses provided	
			AMS	Radiometric
a5	1	3	25	0
a 5/4	4	11	70	0
a 4	2	5	5	20
a 4/3	1	3	18	0
a 3	21	57	291	143
a 3/2	5	14	20	26
a 2	2	5	11	7
		100	440	196
Pilot Study	1	3	2	0
TOTALS	37	100	442	196

Reasons for rejecting each of the eight applications graded "reject" are given in ANNEX M5 ii).

Of the applications received (ANNEX M5 iii)) and graded a-science or R* (additional information having been requested but not yet provided), 33% were for studentship projects with funding for these being evenly spread between NERC awards (11) and non-NERC (10). For those 25 projects that were not student-based, 44% (11) were NERC funded and 56% (14) funded by Universities and/or other sources.

Publications during 1999

Publications (ANNEX M6) with RCL staff as authors/co-authors totalled 10, of which eight were in the science areas ES/TFS and two TFS. The distribution of publications arising from NERC-funded support, provided during and prior to 1999, was seven ES/TFS (including 1 PhD thesis), two ES/MS, three ES, one MS, two MS/TFS.

Targets and Milestones

The annual maximum analytical capacity of the radiometric programme is *ca* 350 analyses and that of the AMS programme *ca* 1000 analyses, although such output could only be sustained for a short while without compromising the overall service quality unless additional scientific staff resource were provided. Use of the radiometric programme was *ca* 57% and the AMS programme *ca* 60% of this maximum capacity. In part this reflects processing of non-routine samples and time consuming pretreatments.

Staff development and training (ANNEX M9) was primarily with the requirement for administrative cover for the AMS programme during Dr Bryant's period of maternity leave and the phased transfer of Mr Miller's duties. Other formal training was associated with the need for IT training courses as a result of the RCL's IT responsibility being transferred to Glasgow University Computing Services.

Finance

Annual spend was within the allocated budgets (ANNEX M8) and summarised in Table 2. Earned income, totalling £46,270, consisted of i) Responsive Mode Income £32,010 (AMS only), ii) Commissioned Income £9,000 (AMS £3,000 and Radiometric £6,000), and iii) Commercial Income £5,260 (to SUERC and reinvested in the facility).

Table 2: Approved Budget, Expenditure and Income 1999/2000

	Approved Budget (£k)	Expenditure (£k)	Income (£k)
Cash Costs Direct to NERC	72.44	71.37	-
Glasgow Univ./SUERC	341.17	297.18	-
Earned income	-	-	46.27

Costs and distribution, of projects supported and reports issued, by NERC Science Area and NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues (ANNEXES M5 i) and O1) are summarised in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Applications supported

Estimated cost (using FCC of £444) £283272					
ENRI	FCC	%	Science Area	FCC	%
Biodiversity	£12728	4.5	ES	£85544	30
Risks/Hazards	£444	0.2	AS	nil	nil
Global Change	£162800	57.5	MS	£66156	23
Pollution/Waste	£25752	9.1	TFS	£12661	45
Nat Resource Mgt	£81548	28.8	EO	nil	nil
			SBA	£4958	2

Table 4: Reports issued

Total cost (using FCC of £444) £349871					
ENRI	FCC	%	Science Area	FCC	%
Biodiversity	£46161	13	ES	£129796	37
Risks/Hazards	£8125	2	AS	£666	0.2
Global Change	£196899	56	MS	£43068	12.3
Pollution/Waste	£41647	12	TFS	£157102	45
Nat Resource Mgt	£57039	16	EO	£666	0.2
			SBA	£18574	5.3

Service Management and Staffing

Management and staffing (ANNEX M9) consists of Prof A.E. Fallick (Director SUERC), Dr C.L. Bryant (5S), Mr B.F. Miller (5S), Dr M.H. Garnett (PDRA), Mrs M.L. Hastings (Grade 4), Mr W.A. Chalmers (Grade E), Mrs M.B. Currie (Grade E), Mr C.D. Murray (Grade E) and Mr F.M. Elliot (Grade D).

Dr Bryant and Mr Miller are NERC employees, Dr Garnett and the technical and administrative staff are employed via the NERC/Glasgow University contract. Dr Harkness (Senior Research Fellow), is employed on a part-time basis by Glasgow University and, as Head of Carbon Geodynamics Group, is available for advice and guidance.

NERC GEOPHYSICAL EQUIPMENT POOL

Annual Report (April 1999 – March 2000)

NERC Geophysical Equipment Pool
Grant Institute
Department of Geology and Geophysics
University of Edinburgh
West Mains Road
Edinburgh EH9 3JW

<http://www.glg.ed.ac.uk/gep/>

GEOPHYSICAL EQUIPMENT POOL (GEP)
Department of Geology & Geophysics, University of Edinburgh
ELEVENTH ANNUAL REPORT (April 1999 - March 2000)

SUMMARY REPORT

1. Service Objectives

The GEP maintains a pool of modern, serviceable, land-based geophysical instrumentation in support of peer-reviewed science projects across a broad spectrum of earth and environmental sciences, e.g. in seismology, geodesy and ground radar.

2. Service Overview and Highlights

Currently, the GEP holds geomagnetic and seismological sensors and recorders, global positioning system (GPS) receivers and ground penetrating radar systems (GPR) with a replacement value exceeding £2.5M. The pool is managed by the University of Edinburgh, via a contract due for renewal in 2004.

Key achievements include: the design and implementation of interface circuitry, bringing the Narod magnetometer into service; extensive in-house revision to the GEP website, offering detailed information to the widening customer base; and the novel design of test instrumentation to enable rapid and thorough testing of instrument cabling demanded by the busy loan schedule.

3. Science

In geomagnetism, in 1998 the GEP provided a set of high-precision data logging instruments to detect Sprites at stations across North America (reported in NERC News, above). Sprites are electromagnetic energy emissions from strong lightning flashes, and their detection allows triangulation on the location of the lightning discharge. The Pool Manager, Val Valiant was involved in station installation. For a 15 minute period in July a remarkable map of thunderstorm activity was created, which will contribute to our understanding of storm development.

In seismology, the results of major fieldwork in Iceland making use of GEP recorders and data loggers, have been appearing in the press. Iceland was created by melt from interaction between the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and the Iceland plume. It's crust is anomalously thick for an oceanic region, but disagreement existed as to exactly how thick, and the implications for melt production in the mantle and crustal temperatures. The experiment showed conclusively that the crust is 25-40km thick, at the upper end of values anticipated. The implications are a high rate of melt production but sub-solidus temperatures in the crust.

In ground-penetrating radar, the British Antarctic Survey has been measuring radar reflections from within ice sheets. Since these surfaces are accepted as representing layers of isochronous deposition of snow they can reveal much about the dynamics of ice flow. For the first time they have established the presence of features related to local anomalies in vertical strain rate in ice. Such local anomalies have major implications for the interpretation of palaeoclimate records from ice cores collected in their vicinity through their influence on estimated ice accumulation rates

In geodesy, the determination of crustal strain in Greece from GPS measurements continues. Current work includes using GEP Ashtech receivers reoccupying stations of a military triangulation survey in northern Greece carried out in the 70's and 80's. Preliminary results indicate that northern Greece is experiencing relatively little strain compared with central Greece, which would be consistent with the distribution of active faulting and earthquakes in the region.

4. Future Developments

The GEP is purchasing Leica530 series, high resolution GPS receivers to supplement its holding of geodetic equipment. Reading and Nottingham Universities will immediately deploy these in Sicily in an international project to improve radar interferometry measurements of ground deformation.

Following a successful JIF bid by a consortium of UK universities, SEISUK, purchasing is now underway for a substantial quantity of state of the art broadband and short period seismic recorders and sensors. The GEP is involved in this process, and the equipment should be integrated into the pool in three years time.

A meeting of geomagnetic community members is being held to investigate a realignment of the community's research efforts towards TEM (Transient Electromagnetic Method). The purchase of TEM equipment is a likely outcome for the pool.

5. Summary of Performance Information

(i) Loan Applications & Reports

Highlights:

28 new applications were received in FY 1999/2000.

10 applications were scheduled to start in 2000/1 or beyond.

75% of the applications reviewed were rated at alpha 3 or above *

62.5% of all projects reviewed this year were funded by NERC

47 loans were supported by GEP, including projects reviewed in earlier years.

21 scientific reports were received and reviewed by the steering committee

29 equipment reports were received and considered by the steering committee.

* This figure includes the reassessment of former R* rated applications

Peer Review Grading	C	R*/R	β	$\alpha1 + \alpha2$	$\alpha3$	$\alpha4$	$\alpha5$	Total Applications Received 1999/00
Number of Applications	0	4	0	3	15	6	0	28

64% of applications out of 28 in total for 1999/00, were received in support of student training and research projects.

(ii) Percentage distribution of projects

<u>Thematic Profile - (ENRIs)</u>	Profile %	1999/0	<u>Science Profile</u>	Profile %	1999/00
Biodiversity	3.3 %	1	Earth Sciences	43.3%	13
Environ. Risks/Hazards	43.3 %	13	Atmospheric Sciences	0.0%	0
Global Change	20.0%	6	Marine Sciences	0.0%	0
Natural Resources	23.3 %	7	Terrestrial & Freshwater	30.0%	9
Pollution & Waste	0.0%	0	Earth Observation	3.3%	1
Other	10.0 %	3	Polar Sciences	13.3%	4
			Other/Archaeology etc	10.0%	3

(iii) Publications for the calendar year

Following a trawl to customers, 24 publications were received in 1999.

(iv) Targets and Milestones

Improvements to equipment : The Narod magnetometers are now fully interfaced with their dataloggers and 'in-service'. The GEP has also recently purchased Leica 520series, high resolution GPS receivers to supplement its holding of geodetic equipment. An example of the optimisation of equipment usage is the recent joint purchase of the high power PE100 radar system by BAS and the GEP. It is deployed in the Antarctic between October and March and is available to GEP customers during the northern summer months.

Usage versus Capacity: is an important indicator of productivity. Sixty percent (60%) of equipment is estimated to be available for loan during the year after deductions have been made for scheduled maintenance, and modifications etc. This figure is used to derive the 'hire-charge' of £15.26/unit/week that underpins the 'cost allocations' exercise and the usage/capacity figures. Because of the continuing high demand for equipment, **the Pool has recovered costs of £579.4k against a FCC of £458.4k. This represents an actual usage of 76% against a 5-year mean of 68%.**

Customer/Staff training : In the area of customer/staff training, this year, the GEP sponsored a short course on ground radar data acquisition and interpretation under the auspices of the Geol. Soc. London's EIGG. 'Hands-on' training for GPS and radar equipment is also provided by equipment manufacturers or 'in-house' at Edinburgh. GEP staff attended H&S seminars and 'awareness' courses and, on the technical/management front, they were represented on Access, UNIX and PRINCE courses.

User Satisfaction : The level of satisfaction felt by our users is assessed via an 'Equipment Loan and Project Review' form that is completed at the end of a loan. It provides immediate feedback on equipment problems and a 'taste' of how a project has progressed. The reports and the comments therein are reviewed by the GEP Scientific Advisory Comm. at their biannual meetings. Prior to every Service Review (and previous Science Management Audits) a more detailed questionnaire is circulated.

(v) Finance

The GEP received a Capital Award of £170k this financial year. £91.2k was spent and a further £48.7k committed. Two Leica geodetic GPS receivers plus fifteen replacement laptop computers were purchased this year. The latter provide the interface between the user and most of the GEP equipment. The GEP and BAS jointly purchased a third radar system. Further delays in the delivery of the broadband seismometers are expected with funds carried over to FY 2000/1.

The recurrent allocation in FY 99/00, including salaries and overheads was £205k. The overall budget was in surplus by £1.7k due to a lower than expected T&S commitment. The University of Edinburgh (UoE) overheads include the salary of a computing officer and a part-time secretary. Overheads are charged on NERC salaries at 20%. The casual labour budget partially supports the UoE employed Modern Apprentice.

Cost-allocations are compiled each year against individual borrowers. The GEP has recovered costs of £579.4k against a FCC of £458.4k.

Equipment Losses : Part of the PE100 radar system was lost on a direct flight from Johannesburg to London. The GEP purchased replacement parts to support a BAS project whilst an insurance claim was being pursued by Birkbeck College. The equipment was eventually found.

(vi) Service management and staffing

There are four full time technical staff, a trainee 'Modern Electronics Apprentice' and a part time secretary.

NAME	Per Annum	Started
Mr MJ Valiant - SPTO - NERC	100%	1985
Mr Paul Kearney - HPTO - NERC	100%	1989
Mr Alf Ball - PTO - NERC	100%	1987
Mr Alan Hobbs - Computing Officer - UoE	100%	1998
Mrs Rosemarie Bland - Senior Secretary -UoE	50%	1997
Mr Colin Kay - Modern Apprentice/Technician - UoE	100%	1999

6. Miscellaneous

The Astronomical Society of Edinburgh has a 3yr lease on two buildings at the GEP's field test site. Work is currently underway to install their 8" reflector telescope.

List of Available Annexes

- Annex 1 Mission Statement
- Annex 2 Scientific Advisory Group
- Annex 3 Equipment Inventory
- Annex 4 Future Developments
- Annex 5 Summary of Performance Information

- Annex 6 Publications for 1999
- Annex 7 Targets and Milestones
- Annex 8 Finance
- Annex 9 Service Management

ANNUAL REPORT (1999-2000) OF THE OXFORD RADIOCARBON ACCELERATOR DATING SERVICE

1. SERVICE OBJECTIVES

ORADS (the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service) carries out dating for projects approved by NERC, as a part of the operation of the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Unit (ORAU). The Unit specialises in archaeological dating, which encompasses a wide range of issues, such as different materials and burial environments, and complex relationships between the dateable event and the archaeologically significant date.

2. OVERVIEW AND HIGHLIGHTS

Radiocarbon dating is applicable to organic material that has survived over the last 50,000 years. The use of accelerator mass spectrometry (the AMS method) permits samples containing 1 mg of carbon and smaller to be dated to an accuracy of about ± 40 years. Choice of each sample is critical, necessitating selection at archaeological, biostratigraphic and chemical levels. In particular, chemical purification methods must be employed to minimise the effect of environmental contamination on the measured date. ORAU has developed over 20 different procedures for this.

Most ORADS projects are for science-based archaeology, but include some environmental projects using ORAU's expertise in the chemistry of bone dating - such as dating the occupation of identified species of frogs and newts in caves after the last Ice Age. The archaeological projects vary enormously, from establishing the earliest occurrence of "anatomically-modern Man" in Europe to providing a detailed chronology for the phases of a Saxon settlement.

Dating information is vital to the building of archaeological and environmental historical knowledge, and therefore to most of the research in these subjects in the HEIs supportable by NERC. For the most part, ORADS manages numerous proposed individual projects judged worthy of support. An additional, usually lesser, source of projects is as part of Research Grant Awards. ORADS is able to co-ordinate projects, so that the chronological framework of the whole is greater than all the parts.

There have been a number of specific developments at ORAU this year highlighted here.

Joint Infrastructure Fund Project

Last year ORAU bid successfully for funds from the JIF fund (through NERC). Work is now underway to purchase and install a new AMS system to replace the old one that has been the mainstay of the laboratories operations over the last 20 years. The instrument has been designed and ordered from HVEE and details of the extension to house the instrument are being finalised with our architects. Delivery is expected in early 2001 with measurements starting by early 2002.

ISO-9002 and Other Methodological Developments

Following extensive preparations last year, ORAU was accredited to the ISO-9002 standard at our first audit by the BSI in November 1999. This development has helped the operation of the laboratory, ensuring systematic scrutiny of all aspects of the measurements made.

Plot of 112 quality control samples measured during 1999; the plot shows the deviations in standard errors from the expected value, with the solid line showing the theoretical distribution.

All chemical methods used have been reviewed and carefully documented. New techniques have also been developed: a new method for bone samples (using ultrafiltration with detection of impurities by UV absorption/fluorescence and analysis of C/N ratios and amino acid data); an improved combustion technique; improvements to wood preservative extraction methods.

A new small sample combustion system (in-house designed and built), enabling measurements to be made on samples with sizes down to 30µg was used for the first time on NERC samples last year, dating lipids extracted from peat.

IT Support to the Research Community and General Public

A new version of 'OxCal', a statistical package for the calibration and analysis of radiocarbon dates, was released this year. This is used by scientists throughout the world working in this field, including many of those working on NERC funded projects. ORAU's WWW site has also been completely redesigned this year. This gives information to scientists, and the public at large, on radiocarbon dating in general, and the Oxford lab (including the NSS) in particular.

Record throughput at ORAU

Overall, this has been a record year for throughput at ORAU with over 2000 submitted samples being AMS dated, about a half of these being also chemically treated at Oxford. Our response time (from sample to measurement) has, none-the-less, reduced slightly to just over 4 months. This is in part due to the success of the new in-house designed automatic target changing mechanism installed at the end of last year.

New AMS sample changer designed at ORAU

3. SCIENCE

3.1 Projects supported by ORADS

These accounts highlight four of the dating projects (listed in Mandatory Annex 5) which have been undertaken using the provision for ORADS projects within the overall NERC allocation.

Late Neanderthals and the Lagar Velho 'hybrid'. ORADS has dated a number of samples pertinent to Neanderthal extinction, usually organic items from European Middle Palaeolithic assemblages. Recently, ORADS has begun the direct analysis of small samples of Neanderthal bone, which are beginning to throw light upon the pattern of Neanderthal extinction. ORADS also measured samples from the grave of the child burial from Lagar Velho rockshelter, Portugal, which has received considerable attention due to several anatomical features that suggest the boy was a Neanderthal/modern human 'hybrid'.

Pleistocene human remains and mid-Upper Palaeolithic burials. Remains of *Homo sapiens sapiens* from Early Upper Palaeolithic contexts are surprisingly rare. ORADS has dated a number of samples from either isolated bones of modern humans (probably not reflecting burials) and complete skeletons (deliberate burials). The results indicate that burial was not practised by the earliest modern humans in Europe. ORADS has, in addition, dated several famous 'ceremonial burials' of mid-Upper Palaeolithic age.

The early human occupation of America. A number of South American sites appeared at face value to indicate human settlement prior to that universally agreed at c. 13,000 BP. A number of samples clearly indicative of human activity were dated from six potentially early sites in Chile and Argentina. None of the resulting ages pre-dates 11,000 BP. Thus, the results would appear to demonstrate that claims for a pre-13,000 BP arrival of modern humans in the Americas cannot be substantiated.

The Oxygen Isotope Stage 3 project. This is an international collaborative venture, of which ORADS is an integral part, directed from the University of Cambridge. A major element of the project is to construct a chronological database for faunal change and interpret human dispersal against this. The scope is European, and ORADS has been measuring climate-specific faunal indicators for the Russian region, for which the database of convincingly-dated samples was relatively poor. In addition to the concerns of the project itself, the results are pertinent to wider issues of megafaunal extinction in the mid Upper Pleistocene.

3.2 The Research Environment

Radiocarbon Dating should include a continuous R & D programme in order to improve the quality of results. Over the years, accuracy, time-range and cost of a date have been improved, mainly by attention to operational details. The reliability of a date depends mainly on chemical procedures, and particular effort continues on this (see Overview and Highlights), and especially on methods to monitor the presence of isotopic contaminating impurities. In addition, certain specific research projects have been supported. Finally, the importance of maintaining a critical and intelligent feedback-loop between research, results and methodology must be stressed.

Specific compound dating from lipids extracted from cooking potsherds. In collaboration with the Bristol Organic Geochemistry Group (GR9/03609 and GR3/10641) the ability to extract and purify single lipids such as palmitic acid using repetitive gas chromatography is being developed. Results show that reliable dates on potsherds can be obtained, but that puzzling questions remain when the highest accuracy is sought. The method should be extendable to other sources of preserved lipid, such as sediments.

Radiocarbon dating of insect remains base on chitin. This NERC funded Research Grant (GR3/11412) is investigating how insect remains can be chemically purified so that compound-specific dating may be done. Chitin is hydrolysed and purified by HPLC to glucosamine. The problem of Maillard reactions with cross-linked protein is recognised and being addressed at present.

Feed-back and the wider laboratory context. In particular a better understanding of the relationship between stable isotope values and the chemical homogeneity of sample material is being gained from interrogation of our accumulating database. It should be added that the Research Lab for Archaeology and the History of Art (RLAHA) now supports an active stable isotope group, which overlaps in many different ways with radiocarbon dating.

In a wider context still, the RLAHA also carries out research in the uranium-series dating of bone (which has common elements in dating and the diagenesis of bone), and in luminescence dating.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The main development efforts for next year concentrate on the planning and preparation for the new AMS facility funded through JIF (see Overview and Highlights). There is also continued work on improvements to methodology and quality control to ensure that the highest possible precision will be attainable when the new AMS comes on-line. In addition, a feasibility study is being made on (a) on-line gas feed to the ion source for the measurement of extremely small samples, and (b) on repetitively collected CO₂ samples resulting from GC-combustion systems (as used in GC-C-IRMS).

5. SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

5.1. Numbers and percentage of α -graded projects supported

ORADS' work is essentially to provide dates for peer-reviewed projects. An administrative summary of projects is given below, with fuller details in Mandatory Annex 4. The primary 'output' is both to communicate dates to submitters and to publish dates.

Grade	Projects considered	Dates allocated
α 4/5	1 (3%)	30 (16%)
α 4	4 (12%)	72 (39%)
α 3/4	1 (3%)	10 (5%)
α 3	6 (18%)	35 (19%)
α 2/3	2 (6%)	34 (18%)
α 2	1 (3%)	4 (2%)
α 1	1 (3%)	1 (<1%)
R and R*	17 (52%)	

Summary of 33 applications received of which 16 were approved for a total of 186 dates

5.2 Percentage distribution and cost of projects according to Science Areas

All projects this year fit into the SBA science area - 100% (£86k). Projects have implications for a mixture of ENRIs. Proportion of work relevant is approximately: Biodiversity 30% (£25.8k), Global Change 50% (£43.0k) and Natural Resource Management 20% (£17.2k).

5.3 Publications

There were 22 publications by ORAU staff (20 peer-reviewed). There were 8 publications arising from ORADS projects (6 peer-reviewed).

5.4 Targets and Milestones

The number of samples externally submitted for dating through ORADS last year was 209 (funded capacity 250). 194 samples were dated (using weightings for failed samples etc). The backlog of ORADS sample rose by 26 to 74 reflecting a high proportion of late submissions. The waiting time has dropped slightly to 4.2 months. The median error term for all dates on material younger than 2000 years was 37 (similar to last year). See Mandatory Annex 7 for more detail.

ORAU is deeply involved in the training of D.Phil. (typically 1-4). It also acts as host and source of advice and guidance to numerous students in other Departments (Geography, Earth Sciences and Archaeology). In addition, a new M.Sc. Course in Archaeological Science has been started in 1999, for which the Unit provides formal and practical teaching, while student projects in the M.Phys. course involve the use of the AMS system during the Summer weeks.

There is an important role for the Unit, as acknowledged experts in radiocarbon, in providing a general education to students and others. This can cover advice to members of the public (including several TV programmes), as well as help in the planning of academic dating projects.

5.5 Financial Details FY1999/2000

Taking a three-year average, ORADS has dated 232 dates per year, which should be compared to our average funded service capacity 217. Average usage is therefore still over 100%.

Full Economic Cost to NERC £86k Unit Cost £344/date (250 capacity)

Capital allocation £2.6k

5.6 Service Management and Staffing

The service is funded on a per-date basis. It uses the staff of ORAU as needed to perform this work: Director (Univ. Lecturer), Deputy Director (Univ. Res. Lecturer), 2 PDRA's, 5.5 technical staff and 1.4 administrative staff.

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

Contract No. F60/G18/02

BOSCOR

**BRITISH OCEAN SEDIMENT
CORE REPOSITORY**

THIRD ANNUAL REPORT

Covering period

1st April 1999 - 31st March 2000

Head of Service : R.G. Rothwell

Assistant Curator : D.E. Gunn

**British Ocean Sediment Core Repository
Southampton Oceanography Centre
Empress Dock
Southampton
SO14 3ZH**

THIRD ANNUAL REPORT

1. SERVICE OBJECTIVES

BOSCOR is a NERC facility located at the Southampton Oceanography Centre set up to provide long-term storage of sediment cores collected by NERC ships and NERC-funded researchers under controlled conditions to ensure optimum preservation. BOSCOR is designated the UK national repository for deep-sea cores and its mission is to promote secondary usage of this material amongst the scientific community. The core collection currently consists of 676 sediment cores, although data are held on 1184 sample stations. During the reporting period 55 cores (totalling 205 metres), derived from cruises and NERC thematic programmes, were added to the collection (see Annex 11).

2. OVERVIEW AND HIGHLIGHTS

In the reporting period, 7 researchers from 7 institutions (including 5 researchers from overseas) sampled BOSCOR cores taking 255 individual samples. In addition, 15 users from 8 institutions used BOSCOR's multi-sensor core logger (MSCL) to log 21 cores with a combined length of 642.5 m, including 5 cores and 1 borehole (together totalling 442.9 m) from outside collections. In total 28,900 individual measurements were made of bulk density, p-wave velocity and magnetic susceptibility and 2000 spectrophotometer spot measurements. In addition, a further 38 individuals (including 6 from overseas institutions) contacted BOSCOR for area sample searches and advice/information on curatorial matters and multi-sensor core logging. User details, broken down by user group, are presented in Fig. 1 for the last three reporting years. When averaged, the number of samples distributed compares favourably with other repositories. Sample distribution figures for the core repository at Scripps Institution of Oceanography, San Diego, California, and BOSCOR are given in Table 1.

BOSCOR has also played an important role in training and eight Ph.D. studentships, and several M.Sc. and undergraduate projects in the School of Ocean and Earth Science (SOES) at the University of Southampton have relied on core material held by the repository (see Annex 6, iii).

Figure 1: Breakdown of BOSCOR usage during 1997-98, 1998-99 and 1999-2000 according to user group.

Table 1		
	No. of cores	No. of samples distributed
Scripps Inst. Oceanography	6,500	723 (1997) ¹ 1224 (1998) ¹ 893 (4 year av. 1995-98) ¹
BOSCOR	676	1310 (97-98) 632 (98-99) 255 (99-00) 732 (3 year av. 97-00)

¹Source: Scripps Institution of Oceanography - Geological Collections: Sediment cores and rock dredge hauls. Handout distributed at the meeting of the International Core Curators Group at the Ocean Drilling Program, College Station, Texas, 5-8 October 1998.

The EUROCORE Concerted Action (an EU-funded project to set up a central access searchable Internet database of cores held by European institutions), coordinated by BOSCOR is now in its second year. The EUROCORE project has combined with another EU concerted action called EUMARSIN (EUropean MARine Sediment Information Network) to form a joint project called EU-SEASED. EU-SEASED has an overall budget of about 1.5 million ecu and brings together a consortium of national geological surveys and sediment core repositories to populate the database. Metadata on all BOSCOR's holdings have now been entered onto the EU-SEASED database and a sample trawl for other UK data was initiated in October 1999 and so far metadata on over 28,000 additional stations have been received.

The BOSCOR searchable database, containing basic metadata for all the samples held within the BOSCOR repository, has been produced as a CD-ROM. The database will be mounted, together with a totally revamped BOSCOR website, onto the Internet during the second quarter of the year 2000.

Close collaboration has continued with industry, particularly with GEOTEK Ltd., a leading-edge company in non-destructive core logging techniques. BOSCOR has collaborated with GEOTEK in developing new sensors for the multi-sensor core logger (MSCL). The line-scanning camera added last year is now functional and images are now being downloaded. The spectrophotometer has now been integrated with the logger, making it the first logger in the world to have the facility to make high-resolution quantitative colour measurements. During the year the spectrophotometer has been extensively used by users to make spot measurements (over 2000 in all). An Olympus BX50 polarising research microscope for users was purchased with funds gained from the January 1999 NSS Capital Round.

3. SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

- Researchers using BOSCOR core material have continued to gain a greater understanding of sedimentary processes operating in the deep sea and have gained insights of special relevance to the hydrocarbon industry. For example, detailed analysis of BOSCOR cores has allowed correlation of the sedimentary sequence in the Agadir Basin with that from the Seine and Madeira Abyssal Plains in the NE Atlantic. Here, individual turbidites from different sources have been correlated across three interconnected deep-water basins across a distance of 1200 km. This work has provided a unique view of a regional large-scale deep-sea

depositional system and is of interest to the hydrocarbon industry as it shows that individual turbidites can show highly variable sand body architecture in intraslope basins with multiple sources.

- Researchers have also used BOSCOR cores to intensively study sediment wave formation around the Canary Islands. The data reveals that the sediment waves are generated by turbidity currents. This is important for hydrocarbon exploration as turbidity current-formed sediment waves in the subsurface can produce highly variable reservoir architecture in channel-fill or channel-overbank facies.
- A novel use of BOSCOR's multi-sensor core logger during the year was to carry out acoustic measurements on saturated wood samples. This work was part of a project looking at using acoustic profiling to detect sunken wrecks buried under the sediments on the seafloor.
- BOSCOR continues to make an important contribution to the NERC RGGE (Rapid Global Geological Events) Special Topic. A further 388 metres of Kimmeridgian hard rock core from the REGGE boreholes were logged using the BOSCOR MSCL system during the reporting year.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The BOSCOR core store is now close to capacity. A case has been drawn up for extending the store. Two options were costed by quantity surveyors: one for doubling the core store capacity (costed at £ 347 k, estimated lifetime 5-10 years of acquisition) and one for tripling capacity (costed at £ 470 k, estimated lifetime 10-15 years). Both options have been put to the NERC's ESTB for consideration for recommendation.

Following the view of the BOSCOR SC at it's last meeting that acquisition of a digital x-radiography system for community use would be highly desirable, a quotation has been obtained from the manufacturers of the SCOPIX x-radiography equipment (£181k). In the next year avenues for funding purchase will be explored.

An improved website, incorporating on-line search facilities of the BOSCOR database, will be installed onto the World Wide Web in the coming year.

5. SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

(i) BOSCOR users (April 1999-March 2000)

No. of users (samples)		No. of users (MSCL)		No. of users (other)*	
UK	Non-UK	UK	Non-UK	UK	Non-UK
2	5	12	3	32	6

*Other includes data searches on request, supplying core data on request, requests for technical information and use of BOSCOR photographic facilities

(ii) Percentage distribution according to NERC's environmental and natural resource issues (sample and logging requests only)

Biodiversity	Environ. Risk And Hazards	Global Change	Natural resource Management	Pollution & Waste
0%	35%	59%	6%	0%

(iii) *Publications for the calendar year*

User feedback and literature checks identified a total of 9 refereed publications engendered by service support. Under-reporting of publications may be a problem, and the figure given is likely to be a minimum. Non-refereed publications/conference proceedings are not listed but number around 20. BOSCOR staff produced 1 refereed publication, 1 item in a conference proceedings volume and 2 commissioned research reports.

	Earth Sciences*	Marine Sciences	Atmos. Sciences	Ter/Fresh Water Sci.	Earth Observ.	Polar Science
Number of publ.	9	0	0	0	0	0

*Marine geology/geophysics has been included under 'Earth Sciences'

(iv) *Targets and Milestones*

The Minolta spectrophotometer is now fitted and interfaced with the MSCL logger and automated colour logging is working well. The core image camera is now operating and acquiring images. A proposal for a test-bed for the design, construction and evaluation of new sensors has been developed.

(v) *Financial details*

Full cash cost	Recurrent Alloc.	Capital Expend.	Revenue
£ 80.37 k	£ 21.22 k	£ 18.40 k	£ 2.64 k

(vi) *Service Management*

BOSCOR is currently staffed as follows:

Service Head	Grade 7 @ 50% (based SOC)
Data Manager/Logging Specialist	HSO @ 50% (based SOC)
Curatorial Assistant	Univ. Tech. Grade A @ 20% (based SOC)

6. FURTHER INFORMATION

If required, more information can be found in the detailed annexes from which the above items were extracted. These are available from Services & Facilities on request.

NERC ICP-MS Facility, Kingston University
Summary Report July 1999-March 2000
(With additional data from April 1999-March 2000)
Dr Kym Jarvis, Head of Facility

1. Service Objectives

The Facility exists to provide ICP-MS facilities to the NERC community in support of research, and undertakes research and development which is of direct benefit to, or meets the future needs of NERC science. The service is delivered in three main ways. Firstly with the provision of ICP-MS instrument time, secondly by provision of short courses, workshops and one to one training on the preparation of samples, ICP-MS instrumentation (basic to advanced) and data handling, and thirdly with an internal R&D programme in support of NERC science. The past 5 months (see foot note) have seen a steady flow of customers through the Facility from a range of NERC science areas and we continue to receive new, high-quality applications.

2. Overview and Highlights

Following the establishment of the ICP-MS Facility at Kingston University in July 1999, the main target was the commissioning of instrumentation and re-establishment of the NERC service following extensive laboratory building work. The Facility was officially 'launched' at an opening ceremony in January to which all current and past PIs were invited. Promotion of the Facility's new location has been vigorously pursued and considerable effort taken to produce an informative and attractive web site. Research and development in support of Earth, and Terrestrial & Freshwater Sciences has been undertaken principally using laser ablation for spatially resolved micro-analysis. Collaboration has been established with Professor Ashmore (Bradford), Prof Fowler & Dr Reynolds (CEH Edinburgh & Bangor) to extend previous work under the Environmental Diagnostics Programme on the use of moss bio-monitors for evaluating heavy metal accumulation throughout the UK. The internal research programme has continued to evaluate the impact of platinum, rhodium and palladium from autocatalysts on the environment. The accumulation of these elements adjacent to major roads is now firmly established, with data for 98-99 coming on-line. Current work seeks to use laser ablation ICP-MS for the characterisation of air particulate between 10-20 μ m in diameter. The association of elements in the catalyst itself may be carried through to individual particles and provide information about removal mechanisms, chemical form and hence impact on the environment.

3. Science

The following are examples of collaborative research projects currently underway and illustrate the high quality and range of science areas supported.

The degassing and crystallisation histories of magmatic rocks determined by LA-ICP-MS analysis of volcanic glasses and melt inclusion - David Pyle (University of Cambridge) -

Remote sensing coupled with the geochemical analysis of volcanic glass and phenocrysts has been used to understand the degassing of water, sulphur, chlorine and fluorine at several volcanoes, notably the Soufriere Hills, Montserrat, and Mount Etna, Sicily. Spectroscopic methods are used to measure gas species in the volcanic plume, whilst electron microprobe analyses detect the concentrations present in the melt inclusions and matrix glass of the erupted rocks. From this information, a model for degassing may be formulated. Firstly, it will help us to understand the way in which the melt evolves before eruption, as the gas species become concentrated in the melt as progressive crystallisation takes place (monitored using LA ICP MS trace element data). Secondly the processes of gas loss are studied, at various stages of the eruption (crystallisation-induced degassing in the magma chamber, degassing on decompression and eruption etc). The ultimate aim is to elevate gas monitoring at andesitic dome-building eruptions to the

Foot Note

Contract No:F14/6/16 terminated at Imperial College on 31st March 1999 and all of the Facility equipment was placed in storage while arrangements were finalised with the new host, Kingston University. The Research ICP-MS Instrument was dismantled prior to moving and stored in that state. The new contract with Kingston began on July 1st 1999. From July to October inclusive the rebuilding and refurbishment of laboratory space was carried out with completion and hand-over of the laboratory on 1st November. The VG PlasmaQuad was re-commissioned and the first NERC customer brought in on 8th November. During the following few weeks, the Surrey Research instrument was also rebuilt and, following minor teething problems, was fully operational by the end of November.

level of a predictive tool, with different gas "signatures" associated with different types of volcanic activity. This will improve hazard assessment at active volcanoes.

Identification of social organization using ICP-MS determination of trace elements in human dental enamel and bone - John Robb (University of Southampton)

This research is intended to investigate how much prehistoric people migrated or remained in one village throughout their lives. Since people absorb trace elements from the particular geological environment they live in through ground water and locally-produced food supplies, people living in different places should have differing amounts of many trace elements in their bones and teeth. Using this fact, it has proven possible in archaeological studies to trace people's patterns of movement between different geological environments. We are studying a group of about 70 Bronze Age Italians from Pompeii. By comparing the trace element composition of their long bones, formed in adulthood, and their teeth, formed in childhood, we hope to observe the extent to which males and females lived their entire lives in the area they grew up in. By doing so, we may be able to reconstruct something of the social organisation and kinship patterns of a prehistoric society.

4. Future Developments

Equipment - Kingston University and the NERC ICP-MS Facility have recently secured funding from HFFCE, TJA Solutions and NERC for the purchase of a state of the art High Resolution ICP-MS instrument. The funding will improve, upgrade and enhance the capabilities of the ICP-MS Facility and improve opportunities for national and international collaborative research. With the flexibility to carry out measurement at ultra-trace element concentrations, coupled with an ability to measure isotopic ratios, the technique is very versatile. The funding will provide a unique university (in the UK) research facility that will underpin top quality research in the earth, environmental and life sciences. The new instrument has forward geometry, is double focusing, with high transmission. The performance is different to, and exceeds that of conventional ICP-MS instrumentation. The instrument offers; ultra-low detection limits of $<0.1 \text{ pg.L}^{-1}$; isotope ratio capability, particularly for isotope tracer studies for light elements (Li, B, S, Cl); determination of radionuclides; elimination of interference effects for environmentally significant elements As and Se; high sensitivity spatially resolved laser ablation capability.

Training - In April, the Facility will launch a new advisory service for post graduate students (PIAS) who are planning to carry out some form of ICP-MS analysis as a part of their projects, or for students who wish to know more about the potential application in their field. The aim is to offer advice on sample processing, analysis and use of alternative sample presentation approaches. It will also provide the Facility with feedback on new areas of development. A number of short courses are also planned following on from the very successful Back to Basics Course which was run in December 99. The courses will address advanced aspects of ICP-MS instrumentation and application, data handling and processing, specialist laser ablation for sample introduction.

5. Summary of Performance Information

A breakdown of the projects supported during the 5 months of operation is shown in Table 1. Of the 13 projects supported, 11 are in support of PhD students and 2 for research projects (both graded $\alpha 4$).

Table 1 Number & percentages of α -graded proposals supported and distribution of science

Science Area	No	%	Grade	No	%	ENRI*	No	%
Marine	1	8	$\alpha 5$	0	0	NRM	3	23
Atmospheric	1	8	$\alpha 4$	7	54	Bio	0	0
Earth	9	68	$\alpha 3$	2	15	P & W	4	31
Terrestrial & Freshwater	1	8	$\alpha 2$	1	8	ER & H	0	0
Science Based Archaeology	1	8	$\alpha 1$	0	0	GC	6	46
Earth Observation	0	0	Pilot	2	15			
			Infrastructure	1	8			

NRM - Natural Resource Management; Bio - Biodiversity; P & W - Pollution and Waste; ER & H - Environmental Risks and Hazards; GC - Global Change;
* some projects cover more than one ENRI

Costs of projects

Science area	Cost £*	Science area	Cost £*
Atmospheric	12,285	T&F	12,285
Earth	110,561	EO	0
Marine	12,285	SBA	12,285

* costs are elevated compared with previous years because of re-location costs incurred – see below

Targets & Milestones

The NERC contact covers the costs for about 60% of Facility operation. During the reporting period, utilisation by NERC has exceeded this figure (Table 2).

Table 2 Instrument utilisation and capacity

Activity	No of days used	% of total days	% of usable days
NERC customer analysis	42	38	51
NERC R&D activity	12	11	15
Kingston University R&D activity	7	6	8
Kingston University other	11	10	13
NERC Training activity	11	10	13
Scheduled maintenance	8	7	
Breakdown	5	5	
Public holiday	9	8	
No staff available	2	2	
Minor laboratory works	3	3	
Total 1/11/99-31/3/00	110		
Total usable	83		

Targets set last year, progress and comments

- Development of laser microprobe ICP-MS for high-resolution coral stratigraphy in studies of global climate change. This project is on hold following staff changes at the Facility
- Development of calibration standards for LA-ICP-MS analysis of micro-particulate. Alternative approaches have been evaluated including the use of doped filter papers and pressed urban particulate compacts.
- PhD student workshops. A one-day course entitled 'Back to Basics: An introduction to ICP-MS' was held in December. The course, sponsored by the Geochemistry Group of the Mineralogical Society, was very successful with 24 attendees.

Targets for the coming year

- Organisation of training courses – courses in Data Handling, Laser Ablation Micro-Analysis, Advanced aspects of ICP-MS
- Installation and optimisation of new high resolution ICP-MS instrument

An example of internal R&D - Laser micro-probe analysis of minerals

Trace element zonation in silicate minerals can provide important clues to help locate areas of potentially economic mineralization. Using laser ablation ICP-MS trace elemental concentrations can be determined *in situ* in minerals such as amphibole, biotite and pyroxene. A convenient approach is to ablate thin sections (~40µm thick) of study material which have previously been analysed for major elements using an electron microprobe. However, initial LA-ICP-MS studies show that the first few pulses of laser energy are absorbed by the mineral in a fashion

that causes large areas to be 'plucked out' from the parent material. Subsequent pulses actually ablate material beneath the crystal of interest, together with slide adhesive and glass. The magnified image left

(J.Cleverley, Leeds Univ) shows a crater formed during analysis of an amphibole. Laser ablation has created a pit in the underlying glass. Clearly this sort of behaviour by minerals subject to analysis is undesirable. Alternative approaches, such as using the sample-slide parent material 'mirror' for laser ablation, are now underway and showing considerable promise. Figure right (J.Cleverley, Leeds Univ) shows normalised REE plots from two amphiboles determined by LA-ICP-MS on blocks of sample preserved after thin section making.

Publications

Publications by Facility staff, listed in Annex 6a, illustrate a continuing and consistent publication output over the past year. Publications are all in refereed journals and tend to fall into two areas, those concentrating on the development of the ICP-MS technique, and those in which the data produced is used to tackle a particular scientific problem. Seven papers (3 in Terrestrial & Freshwater Science; 4 in Earth Science) were published with a further 5 submitted for publication.

Three papers have also been published by Facility customers as a result of the work carried out at the Facility, with a further 10 in preparation or in press. A number of PIs have not responded to requests for information and so this a minimum measure of performance. 32 PhD theses were supported during the reporting period of which 6 were completed.

Financial details

The financial details are shown in Table 3. The over-spend on recurrent was a result of crate hire costs incurred during storage of Facility equipment April-June 99 inclusive. The annual full cash cost set by NERC was £159,700 with a unit full cash cost of £1389 per analytical day. This figure is higher than in previous years because of the additional costs incurred in re-establishing the Facility at Kingston University, and is expected to reduce in the next financial year. The annual gross and net revenue was £nil. There was no planned capital expenditure

Table 3 Estimated vs actual spend

	Estimated	Actual
Salaries	£43.18K	£44.66K
Recurrent	£13.50K	£20.54K
Overhead	£19.86K	£15.50K
Lab refurbishment	£40.00K	£40.00K
Total	£116.54K	£120.7K

Service Management & Staffing

Staffing level and grades are as follows:

Dr Kym Jarvis	Principal Lecturer, Head of Service	0.5 person years per annum
Dr John Williams	Senior Lecturer, R&D Manager	0.25 person years per annum
Ms Jo Greenwood	Post Doctoral Fellow	1.0 person years per annum*
Mr Karl Heinz-Offenbecher	Post Graduate Researcher	0.5 person years per annum **

* joined 1/11/99; ** joined 1/01/00

Mandatory annexes

Annex 1 Mission statement; **Annex 2** Management/Steering Committee membership and ToR; **Annex 3** Equipment inventory; **Annex 4** Future developments; **Annexes 5a,5b** Projects supported, Applications received; **Annex 6a,6b,6c,6d**. Facility staff publication, Customers publications, PhD Theses, Customer internal reports; **Annex 7** Targets and Milestones; **Annex 8** Finance; **Annex 9** Service management; **Annex 10, 10a** Facility staff presentations, customer presentations

NERC Space Geodesy Facility

Annual Report for 1999 April to 2000 March

1. Service Objectives.

The NERC Space Geodesy Facility (NSGF) exists to support geodetic and geophysical research through satellite tracking data and related products. The Facility operates a state of the art Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR) system, and permanently operating geodetic GPS and GLONASS receivers. The NSGF is registered both with the International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS) as an SLR station and Associate Analysis Centre and with the International GPS Service (IGS) as the UK IGS site.

2. Overview and highlights

The NSGF is funded jointly by NERC, BNSC and MoD. The principal UK interest in the products of the Facility are the use of GPS data from the station whose coordinates are precisely known in a global reference frame, accurate orbits of altimetry and SAR satellites determined by global SLR and GPS tracking data and SLR-monitoring of the quality of radiometric-based orbital information of the navigational satellites in the GPS and GLONASS constellations. In the highlights outlined in this section, it is made clear into which principal funding area the work lies, although it must be recognised that much overlap of interests exists and that a certain level of SLR tracking is necessary for all applications. For example the maintenance of the global reference frame and continual improvement of models of the Earth's gravity field by regular SLR observation of the *geodetic* satellites form an essential underpinning of the work that is of more direct UK relevance and which is outlined below.

2.1 Altimetry Missions. SLR tracking support for the current altimetry missions continued at a high level of priority. The ESA altimetry and SAR mission ERS-2 continues to provide high-quality observations of the ocean, land and ice-sheet heights that are placed on a global reference frame using orbits of precision about 5cm RMS determined from SLR and PRARE tracking data, supplemented by cross-over techniques. The highly successful ERS-1 failed in 2000 March after nine years of operations, during which SLR provided the only tracking support. The NASA/French altimetry mission TOPEX/POSEIDON (T/P) also continues to be a high-priority target for SLR measurements. Orbits determined using SLR and the microwave DORIS and GPS tracking systems are obtained with precision about 3 cm RMS, helped both by improved tracking coverage and by the lower atmospheric density at 1500 km compared to that experienced by ERS at heights of 850 Km. Interesting, though, is an apparent systematic radial difference of several cm between the SLR-based and GPS-based orbits for T/P, which is further discussed below. A further high-priority altimetry mission of interest to the UK oceanography community is the GEOSAT Follow-on (GFO-1) US Navy mission. GFO-1, launched in 1998 February carries four GPS receivers and a laser retroreflector array. Unfortunately the GPS receivers have experienced operational

problems, and satellite laser ranging remains the only measurement tool in use for precise orbit determination.

Future altimetric missions for launch during the next two years are JASON (T/P follow-on) and the ESA ENVISAT mission. Altimetric and SAR observations from all these operational and future satellites are being and will be used in a variety of oceanographic (e.g. sea level), solid Earth (e.g. improvement of global Digital Elevation Models) and Polar (e.g. Antarctic mass-balance) NERC-funded research in the UK.

The plot below shows the performance during the report period of the NSGF SLR system at Herstmonceux in tracking the altimetric satellites, along with other low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites, in comparison to the other stations in the global network. The system clearly is a major contributor to the global data volume.

2.2 Satellite Radar Calibration/Rapid prediction updates

During the year the German cannonball-type LEO geodetic satellite GFZ-1 was used by the Facility in a unique experiment to test the quality of various radar tracking systems. The radar data was used both to improve the quality of available tracking predictions and for independent orbital determination whose quality was checked using Herstmonceux SLR data. The experience gained during this work has also impacted via Facility staff involvement in the rapid prediction strategy being adopted by the ILRS in anticipated support of new LEO missions such as the gravity-field mission CHAMP, due for launch in 2000 July.

2.3 Ranging accuracy study

A major study of sources of potential range bias in the SLR system was completed during the year, with results presented at two sessions of the EOS/SPIE Symposium on Remote Sensing held in Florence and a paper published in the proceedings. The study investigated systematic effects in the time-of-flight measurements made using both the operational cluster of counters and a loaned high accuracy (and cost) 'standard' counter, and short-arc orbit determination techniques. Included in the work are results from the ongoing ILRS study being led by Facility staff into systematic 'bias' induced by the characteristics of the reflector arrays. That the system is extremely stable is confirmed by *independent* ILRS analyses of the global LAGEOS data as presented in the following figure showing system stability within the tracking network during the report period.

Of the 20 systems achieving the ILRS-imposed stability criterion of 20 mm, the Herstmonceux system ranks 4th with long-term stability much better than 10 mm.

3. Science

It is mainly the down-stream products of SLR data, namely accurate orbital information for the remote-sensing altimetry and SAR satellites, which are used by the NERC-funded UK community to address problems in Earth Observation and in Marine Science. These groups include those at MSSL, SOC, POL, De Montfort and RAL. Two groups which are ILRS Associate Analysis Centres, the Department of Geomatics, University of Newcastle and the Facility itself, *directly* use SLR data for orbit determination work. Several groups including Newcastle, the IESSG Nottingham and the NERC ARSF as well as many surveying groups both academic and commercial use the Herstmonceux IGS-site GPS data in their network solutions. An example of ongoing work is the use of precise ERS altimetry at the Geomatics Research Unit, De Montfort University, in a novel study to determine a new Global Digital Elevation Model by combining land

altimetry and ground-truth. An essential component of this work is accurate satellite orbital information, derived from accurate tracking data.

Facility staff are taking part in an International collaboration to monitor the accuracy of GLONASS and GPS radiometric orbits using SLR data. Results confirm that there is a radial bias of about 5 cm in the microwave orbits, and that up to 2cm of the bias can be attributed only in the GLONASS case to systematic effects due to the large reflector arrays on those satellites. The remaining bias appears to be satellite-dependent and may thus indicate a bias in the assumed location of the transmitter phase-centres. Staff are involved in a joint-Services (IGS, IVS, ILRS) study to investigate these effects.

4. Future Developments

- GPS: increase the rate to 2 Hz. Already making hourly data available. Responded to IGS call for participation in LEO tracking which demands high rate and rapid availability. Investigate purchase of new GPS/GLONASS receiver.
- Difficulty in SLR tracking during daytime in summer - camera to view laser beam in daytime.
- Prepare to support new missions - CHAMP, JASON, VCL, ENVISAT.

5. Summary of performance information

The SLR observing time used at Herstmonceux is scheduled to give best coverage to the passes of the satellites that are of particular interest to UK work, namely the altimetry/SAR and GPS/GLONASS satellites. During the year, the average ratio of time actually used to that scheduled has been about 45%. The GPS and GLONASS receivers operate continuously. Tables and graphs of the numbers of satellites tracked by the SLR system are given in Annex 5.

SLRF staff members serve on several and lead two international working groups; the details are given in Optional Annex 7. Two progress meetings were held with MoD contacts. Conferences were attended and papers presented in Florence and Nashville.

Publications - Three papers have appeared in conference proceedings. One paper using astronomical data from the Herstmonceux SLR system has appeared in *Icarus*. A further paper on SLR analyses of GLONASS observations has been submitted to a refereed Journal. Two special and four quarterly analysis reports were written for MoD.

Finances. NERC-derived FEC for the Service for the FY 1999/2000 was £364.65K. Of this, BNSC contributed £113k and MoD £86k.

Staff numbers for 1999 April 1-2000 March 31:

Direct effort: At Herstmonceux 6.0 my, at Monks Wood, Huntingdon, 1.0 my.

In addition, a research scientist from the Communications Research Laboratory, Tokyo, Japan continues a two-year CRL-funded visit and is accommodated at Monks Wood.

NERC Inductively Coupled Plasma - Atomic Emission Spectrometry Facility

Annual Summary Report 1999-2000

Dr J N Walsh

**Department of Geology
Royal Holloway, University of London
Egham
Surrey TW20 0EX**

1. Service Objectives

The NSS supported ICP-AES facility located at Royal Holloway, University of London is primarily concerned with the elemental analysis of rocks, sediments, minerals, soils and waters. Essential analytical determinations are provided for the NERC community in a broad range of research projects. The Mission Statement for the facility is given in Annex 1.

2. Overview and Highlights

Geological, biological, environmental and archaeological research projects require and benefit from the provision of reliable quantitative analytical data. Inductively Coupled Plasma - Atomic Emission Spectrometry is one of the most widely used analytical techniques for measuring concentrations of major, minor and trace elements. It is a robust analytical method capable of providing analyses for a wide range of elements in a diversity of sample matrices. NERC has provided partial financial support for the facility for several years and a large number of members of the NERC community have used the service as part of their research effort.

The facility is housed in purpose-built laboratories at the Royal Holloway, University of London campus in Egham, Surrey. During the course of this year there have been significant changes within the facility. The most important of these has been the purchase of a new optical ICP system. This system is now installed and fully operational (details of the equipment available are given in Annex 3).

NERC users also make considerable use of the associated sample preparation laboratories at RHUL. Royal Holloway, Geology Department makes no charge for the use of these laboratories and providing them represents a significant contribution towards the running of the ICP-AES facility. NERC Scientific Services provides the salary for 60% of a Postgraduate Research assistant (Scale 1B). In addition, some financial support for consumables (argon gas for the ICP, chemicals, standards etc.) and some of the maintenance costs of the ICP-AES instrument are paid for by NERC.

This summary report covers the year from April 1999 - March 2000. During the course of the year there was some disruption to the facility's activities as the new instrument was installed and the old instrument decommissioned. Nevertheless, the facility continued to provide support to 42 projects during the year in which 8229 samples were analysed for a range of major and trace element determinations. These users cover a broad spectrum of applications from the NERC community with emphasis on environmental, geological and archaeological aspects. A significant part of the facility's support is for research students. 21 of the 42 projects supported during the year were for PhD students, 5 projects were for taught Masters students and 16 projects were for academic staff.

3. Science

Geology Departments across the U K remain the single largest group of users of the ICP-AES facility and numerous projects have been completed. However, there is a wide range of projects and staff and research students from other academic Departments also form a significant group of users. All projects submitted are reviewed and graded. The Head of the facility and/or the PGRA operating the facility discuss projects with users and advise on the input that the analyses can make to the users project. Some of the projects undertaken during the year are referred to below:

7

The geochemistry and economic geology of the laterites and bauxites of the Antrim Plateau (I.Hill, Geology Dept, Queen's University, Belfast).

The ICP-AES data have been used to establish the extent to which rare earth elements can be mobilised during varying stages of chemical weathering. The Antrim lavas include excellent material for studying the stages of chemical weathering. Establishing the relations and the mechanisms for the lateritisation process has implications for understanding the prevailing palaeoenvironmental and palaeoclimatic conditions. Additionally the data help to define distinctions between the Lower and Middle Basalts within the Antrim Tertiary lavas. A further important aspect of the Antrim laterites that should be considered is their potential economic value. Although the laterites and bauxites are no longer mined as a source of iron or aluminium they are used in waste water treatment and detailed geochemical studies will assist in the economic evaluation.

This project has now yielded some significant results and these have important implications for many trace element igneous geochemical studies. In particular, it has been demonstrated that the rare earth elements and Y are relatively easy to mobilise during chemical weathering. Mass balance calculations have been used to quantify enrichment/depletion patterns and demonstrate fractionation of elements as a result of differential element mobility. The ICP-AES data demonstrate that the light rare earth elements are preferentially leached during weathering and are redistributed within the weathering profile. Chemical weathering is shown to be a mechanism that can destroy the characteristic rare earth element pattern of basic igneous rocks. The data also demonstrate the relative ease with which Y can be mobilised in the early stages of chemical weathering. The results place considerable restraints on the previously held view that these elements can be treated as 'immobile' and used as indicators of petrogenetic processes.

Late Proterozoic sedimentation and biochemical processes: Abu Mahara Group of Oman (J.Leather, Dept Earth Sciences, Oxford and Geology Dept, Trinity College, Dublin)

The dominantly siliclastic Neoproterozoic Abu Mahara Group succession in Oman is overlain by a cap carbonate unit. Detailed isotopic analysis has established $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signals and it may be possible to use these to correlate with other comparable cap carbonates elsewhere in the world. It is however essential that the degree of diagenetic alteration is established in the cap carbonate to be confident that the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signal is primary. This can be done by detailed measurement of diagenetic tracer elements (Mn, Fe, Sr, Mg, Ca and Na). This has been done using the ICP-AES facility which allows these elements to be measured rapidly in small quantities of sample material.

Palaeoceanography from cyclicity in Oligocene to Recent drift sediments from the southwest Pacific Gateway – ODP Leg 181 (G Weedon Univ of Luton/ I. Hall, Dept Earth Sciences, Cambridge)

This project is a continuation of the ODP work started last year by McCave and Hall. Large numbers of samples are analysed at the ICP-AES facility for a diagnostic suite of major and trace elements (Al, Ba, Cr, Cu, K, P, Si, Ti, V) using the small amounts of material available from the ODP Southwest Pacific Gateway drilling. The ICP data enable an element ratio time series to be established and this contributes to studies of the nutrient levels, productivity, bottom-water oxygenation levels, siliclastic component and cyclicity in the Oligocene to recent build up of the Antarctic ice sheet.

4. Future provision of ICP-AES facilities

The ICP-AES facility was reviewed by NERC Services Review Group in January 1999. The Services Review Group commented favourably on the facility's work and especially on the quality of the service provided, the value for money and the wide range of users of the facility. The Services Review Group recommended renewing the contract to support the facility from April 2000 for 3 years and this was confirmed by the Science and Technology Boards. In addition NERC agreed to contribute towards the purchase of a new optical ICP system. This instrument has been purchased and was installed in November 1999. It is now fully operational and all the service work has been successfully transferred to the new instrument. The provision of a modern simultaneous optical ICP instrument and the associated infrastructure for the NERC community is now assured until at least April 2003.

5. Summary of Output Performance Indicators

Details of the usage of the NERC ICP-AES facility are given in Annex 4. Summary Table 1 in this Annex gives information on the users of the facility during the year. Table 2 in Annex 4 gives details of the work completed showing that 8229 samples were analysed for a total of 214,818 elemental determinations during 1999-00. These numbers are for the external users of the facility. There is a significant postgraduate student use of the facility and Ph D and taught Masters student projects are identified in Annex 4 Table 2. The range of departments and institutions using the NERC ICP-AES facility shows a wide spread across the country. The total number of samples analysed is higher than the target that had been set for the facility. The unit cost of analyses was £3-40. This figure is based on the full cash cost for the year of £28,000.

Table 1 Summary of applications by peer review grade

Grade	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	Pilot	β	R	Total
Applications	-	12	19	2	-	9	-	1	43
Supported	-	12	19	2	-	9	-	-	42
Percentage of total of α applications	-	36	57	6	-				

The primary purpose of the NSS ICP-AES service is to provide elemental analytical data. This it does for a wide spectrum of the NERC community. The Head of the Facility and the PGRA discuss the projects with all applicants and offer advice and critical comments and suggestions. In addition all projects are subject to review and grading. The gradings for the various projects undertaken during the year are summarised in Table 1 above. These gradings have been approved by the ICP Steering Committee. This process should enhance the value and relevance of the research projects supported and enhance the expertise of the facility staff. It should also ensure that the ICP-AES facility resources are used as efficiently as possible. A summary is given in Table 2 below of the distribution of projects by ENRI and by Science area.

Table 2 Number and percentage of projects by ENRI and Science Area

ENRI	No	%	Science Area	No	%
Biodiversity	4	10	Marine	4	10
Environmental Risk	6	14	Atmospheric	1	2
Global Change	8	19	Earth	14	33
Natural Resource	16	38	Terrestrial & Freshwater	15	36
Pollution & Waste	8	19	Science Based Archaeology	7	17
			Polar	1	2

The users of the ICP-AES facility obtain access to a high performance instrument and to the established analytical protocols that are used in the laboratory. Many users of the facility also make use of the sample preparation facilities established at Royal Holloway and this information can be transferred back to their own institutions. The ICP-AES facility also contributes towards the data quality assessment that users undertake. The availability of a good range of Certified Reference Materials assists this process considerably. The facility is making a substantial contribution to research student training, in the provision of analytical data and also in the evaluation of the quality and suitability of the data.

Targets for the ICP facility

The contract approved by NSS in 1997-2000 included targets for the 3 years. The details given on an annual basis were:

Maximum number of days the instrument can be used by NERC service users - including calibration, downtime and quality assurance (per annum)	100
Number of analyses to be completed per annum	5,000
The estimated full economic cost estimates per annum	£28,000
Unit cost estimate (per sample)	£5-60

(These figures have been accepted by the ICP Steering Committee).

1999-2000 The targets given above for days used and number of analyses completed were achieved and exceeded. The Total Cash Costs of the Service was £28,000 and the unit price (cost per sample) was £3-40.

2000-2001 The targets given above will again be used as guideline figures.

Instrument performance

The analytical performance of the ICP-AES instrument during the year under review has not been as good as previous years. The old Philips instrument became increasingly unreliable in the first half of the year and work had to be transferred to the new Perkin Elmer Optima system earlier than expected. The accelerated transfer of work caused some inconvenience for users and substantial difficulties for staff at Royal Holloway Geology Department. However, the new instrument is now working routinely and giving excellent results. Analytical performance is monitored with regular checks being made for analytical sensitivity and precision. Downtime has been small and accessibility for NERC users has continued at a high level. There is now no significant backlog of samples awaiting analysis and all accepted users have been able to complete their research within agreed time limits.

Publications.

Annex 6 gives details of the papers published by users of the facility and Annex 7 gives details of the recent publications by facility staff. The practical difficulties for a small facility such as the ICP-AES facility in compiling reliable information on user's publications has been highlighted in previous annual reports. The staff resources available (60% of a PGRA) and the added burden during the year under review of installing and commissioning the new instrument has limited the time available to pursue users for their publications. The data given in Annex 6 for the users publications is certainly incomplete and will be updated when information is available.

6. Finance

The Full Cash Cost during the year was £28,000. This gives a unit cost of exactly £3-40 per sample, based on the analysis of 8229 samples. Details of the budget and actual expenditure for 1999-2000 are given in Annex 5. There was some overspend on salaries as the PGRA is at the top of the salary scale and allowance for this has not been made in the budget. It is worth noting that the cost of consumables, including instrument servicing is substantially in excess of the figures given in Annex 5 for the NERC use of the ICP-AES system. There is a considerable subsidy to the NERC service from the commercial users of the ICP-AES instrument.

7. Staff/Service Management

NSS provides funds for 60% salary for a Postgraduate Research Assistant who operates the ICP-AES facility on a day to day basis. The current PGRA is Ms N Paige, she was appointed in September 1997 and her present contract would finish at the end of the present ICP-AES contract (end March 2000). The new ICP-AES NERC contract will provide continued funding for 60% salary for a PGRA and Ms Paige's contract has been renewed until April 2001.

The overall management of the facility is the responsibility of the Head of the facility – Dr J N Walsh. NERC funding for the ICP-AES facility makes no contribution towards the salary of the Head of the Facility, nor to any other personnel.

NERC Ion Microprobe Facility (IMF)

1st April 1999 - 31st March 2000

Department of Geology and Geophysics
University of Edinburgh
West Mains Road
EH9 3JW

<http://www.glg.ed.ac.uk/research/ionprobe/ionprobe.htm>

IMF ANNUAL REPORT

Ion Microprobe Facility (IMF) 1 April 1999 to 31 March 2000

1. Service Objectives

The Facility provides access through NERC Science Programmes Directorate (SPD) to a modern ion microprobe (Cameca ims-4f) for UK scientists that operate under NERC's area of interest. The ion microprobe is a highly versatile instrument, having the capability of measuring isotopes across the periodic table, from H to U. Features of the technique include: *in situ* isotopic analysis; very low detection limits (ppb) for trace element analysis and high spatial resolution (1-20 μ m), all performed with minimal sample preparation. Integrated within the Facility is access to an electron microprobe (EMPA) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) that may be used for sample characterisation prior to ion microprobe analysis.

Funding is also included for the Tephrochronology Analytical Unit (TAU) which provides access to the IMF, EMPA and SEM for tephrochronology studies. A full scientific account of the IMF research is in the Annual Report submitted to the Ion Microprobe Facility Steering Committee (IMFSC) (Appendix 2) and available on request.

2. Overview and Highlights

The IMF principal investigators, together with colleagues in the Departments of Chemical Engineering, Chemistry and Mechanical Engineering, have been successful in attracting a large grant from the Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF) for the establishment of a new Edinburgh Material and Micro-Analysis Centre (EMMAC). The centre-piece of EMMAC will be a large radius ion microprobe with multicollection capability giving greater resolving power and higher transmission than the present Cameca 4f. The multi-collector capability will permit higher precision isotope ratio measurements, potentially rivalling gas-source mass spectrometry.

- The upgrading of the Cameca ims-4f has continued with the installation of an improved electron flood gun, enhancing the performance of high precision stable isotope analysis. The new gun gives better charge neutralisation at the point of analysis by providing a more uniform flood over a broader area.
- A new technique has been developed for the routine determination of Ni in mantle garnets. This type of analysis, usually performed on a proton microprobe, is used as a geothermometer for diamond prospecting and is now sufficiently well developed to offer as a service to the NERC community.
- The high precision analysis of Si isotopes in quartz, and their application to oil reservoir rocks, has been developed and refined by Dr. C. Macaulay. This new application of the ion microprobe technique combines its strengths of *in situ* analysis with high spatial resolution and high precision. The results have already been presented at the American Association of Petroleum Geologists.

3. Science

Research applications in the earth sciences range from low temperature environmental processes to high pressure and temperature geochemistry (Appendix 2).

Stable Isotopes Analysis

- Silicon isotope ratios ($^{30}\text{Si}/^{28}\text{Si}$) in quartz were measured (Macaulay, Graham and Haszeldine), to trace the origins of quartz cements in four North Sea reservoirs. Quartz cements grow in the pore space of reservoir sandstones, reducing porosity and permeability, and exert a major control on hydrocarbon reservoir quality. In two reservoirs the quartz cements were shown to have the same isotopic signature ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) as the detrital grains, indicating that silica was sourced from detrital grain dissolution. Two other oil fields were unusual in containing siliceous sponge spicules. In one of these fields quartz overgrowths have lower $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ than detrital grains, but the same $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ as the sponge spicules, indicating a biogenic silica source. However, overgrowths in the other field have the same $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ as detrital grains, indicating cement silica sourced by detrital grain dissolution rather than the sponge spicules.

- Oxygen isotope analyses have been made of carbonates precipitated during retrograde alteration of marbles and schists in the Scottish Highlands (Guest, McCaig and Graham). The analyses indicate that alteration was the result of downward movement of both meteoric and basinal fluids into the metamorphic basement rather than an upward movement of deep crustal fluids.
- Zircon is a refractory mineral extensively used in dating. However, recent experimental studies have cast doubt on its ability to withstand high temperatures and pressures without internal homogenisation or exchange with its surrounding. Oxygen isotope studies (Peck, Valley and Graham) of single detrital zircon grains in granulite facies quartzites have shown conclusively that oxygen diffusion in zircons is slow enough for them to retain their igneous $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values through granulite facies metamorphism. This calls into question the recent experimental oxygen diffusion data for zircons which suggest rapid diffusion rates.

Diffusion and Viscosity Studies

- The outer core is the largest single phase region of the Earth and is responsible for the geodynamo as well as contributing to heat-flow, core-mantle coupling and seismic propagation within the Earth. Despite its importance, however, surprisingly little is known about its viscosity: estimates based on geophysical measurements span 13 orders of magnitude. Dobson found that, in contrast to earlier experiments, liquids at high P and T agree very well with both recent atmospheric pressure measurements and *ab initio* simulations at outer core pressures. The predicted viscosity for outer core liquid is around 5×10^{-3} Pas, thirty time less viscous than water.

Trace Element Studies

- The trace element composition of komatiite liquids, quenched as glass inclusions in olivine, have been successfully used to establish the dynamics of the ancient mantle. The analysis supports the contention that the komatiites were sourced from a hot mantle and the results are consistent with the cooling models that assume the ancient mantle was $>200^\circ\text{C}$ hotter than it is today.

Volcanology

- Hydrogen isotope (D/H) distribution in amphibole phenocrysts from the recent Soufriere Hills eruption has distinguished two different isotopic and textural types. Early D-rich amphibole cores represent exchange of surface steam-heated waters with older (pre-eruption) viscous magma that failed to reach the surface. Later D-depleted amphiboles grew from isotopically light and recent (1996) magmas after earlier conduit-filling material was flushed out. These results underpin a new model of remobilisation of material during the current eruptions on Montserrat.
- Large eruptions from silicic arc volcanoes, like those from the Toba caldera, Sumatra, are environmentally devastating. It is important to identify and model the processes which trigger these eruptions and the timescales involved. Trace element analysis (Thomas et al.) of the plagioclase phenocrysts has provided a high resolution record of the evolution of this volcano. It has shown that residence times (1000-3000 years) of magmas are short and challenges the conventional assumptions of orderly and protracted magma evolution.

Climate

- Stalagmites contain potentially important records of recent climate change, especially rainfall variation. Finch and Shaw have established a clear correlation between measured rainfall and Sr concentration. More recent work by Fairchild, using high spatial resolution multi-element analyses, have established that sub-Annual variations are common. This work has also established that other elements (e.g. P) may be even more sensitive than Sr in defining annual growth rates of stalagmites and variations in the past climate record.

4. Future Developments

The present instrument will continue to operate and be upgraded during the installation and operation of the new high resolution instrument. It is anticipated that overall demand for SIMS instrument time will increase as the capabilities of the new instrument become apparent. The future development of the new instrument

will rely on the availability of high quality standard materials. Studies will be started on both isotopic and trace element standards for geochronological and isotopic research projects. Although no major instrument improvements are anticipated for the ims-4f in the coming year, further development of its faraday cup secondary current measuring system, using the Keighly high precision ammeter, should be applicable to isotope analysis on the new instrument.

5. Summary of Performance Information

Applications to IMF

The number of approaches to the Facility remains high at over 35 in the last year. 17 of these approaches resulted in a full application to the IMFSC and a further 4 are expected in the near future. 5 were not feasible on the present instrument and 4 requests required only a few days and were carried out as pilot projects. 5 requests may yet result in applications if the projects receive funding from either NERC Research Grants Committee or other sources.

The IMFSC met to consider the 17 formal applications on the 14th May and 29th October 1999. Only 13 applications graded $\alpha 3$ (35%) and above were awarded instrument time. 4 (30%) of these successful applications were for research student projects. The small proportion of low α -graded applications results from the fact that technically unsuitable proposals are discouraged at an early stage. The breakdown of the grades were:

IMF Committee Grade	Number of Applications	Number of Applications (%)	Applications Awarded Time
$\alpha 5$	1	5.9	✓
$\alpha 4$	6	35.3	✓
$\alpha 3/4$	2	11.8	✓
$\alpha 3$	4	23.5	✓
$\alpha 2$	1	5.9	
$\alpha 1$	0	0.0	
β	0	0.0	
Re-submit	3	17.7	

NERC Science Areas

All work awarded instrument time was within the Earth Science area. The projects awarded instrument time were divided between the following NERC Environmental and Resource issues:

Biodiversity	Environmental Risk/Hazard	Global Change	Natural Resources	Pollution/Waste
0	4	1	8	0

Publications for Calendar Year 1999

Publications for the calendar year 1999 for SPD funded projects, for both IMF and TAU researchers, were all within the Earth Science area; these include:

- 18 papers published in refereed Journals in the calendar year.
- 13 Ph. D theses finished in 1999.
- 15 presentations were given at conferences in 1999

A full list of ion probe publications to date can be found in the full scientific Annual Report (Appendix 2) and additional information on the IMF and the TAU can be found on their web sites at <http://www.glg.ed.ac.uk>.

Targets and Milestones

The ion microprobe is normally scheduled on a weekly basis with bookings made from 4 to 9 months in advance. Tight scheduling is dependent on instrument reliability. This is ensured by in-house maintenance and repairs combined with a manufacturer's partial service contract.

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Total number of operational hours by SPD and RGC users

- In the last year no day was lost as a result of instrument failure.
- All SPD users were allocated time within the schedule they requested.
- The total number of hours used by SPD operators has fallen as demand from NERC Research Grant holders has increased.
- Total instrument usage of **3505** hours compares with a 7 year average of **3400**
- A total of **1320** hours (38%) was used on student projects.

Operational hours by SPD and Research Grant users 1999-2000

- In the last year 59% of operational time was on SPD approved projects.
- 33% of the instrument time was on NERC Research Grant funded (RGC) science
- 8% of time was on other independently funded research.
- A total of 17 different institutions were represented.
- 35 different users received instrument time.

Service Management and Staffing

Four staff members maintain the IMF, and the TAU, two of whom are SPD funded (Annex 9). All users of the IMF receive training in the operational use of the ion microprobe as well as in the SIMS technique. The Cameca '4f is not an automated instrument and requires that the user being present at all times, supervised by a member of the IMF staff. Ancilliary facilities for sample preparation and characterisation are provided by the Facility. An EPMA and SEM are available to users for additional characterisation of samples prior to, and during, analytical sessions. Fast access to the SEM has proved essential for stable isotope studies since repeated characterisation of specimens is necessary for efficient use of ion microprobe analytical time.

Finance – Budget for 2000-2001 and spend for 1999-2000

The Ion Microprobe Facility is largely funded by NERC SPD and individual NERC Research Grants. In addition, some funding is received from other research grants, principally through overseas users and commercial work. The requested Budget for support of the ion probe in 2000-2001 can be found in Annex 8. The budget and spend for 1999-2000 was:

Salaries	Instrument/Overheads etc	Full Cash Cost	Actual Spend
£59.2K	£52.5K	£111.7	£111.9K

NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

ISOTOPE COMMUNITY SUPPORT FACILITY

at the

**SCOTTISH UNIVERSITIES
ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH CENTRE**

Annual Report

April 1999 - March 2000

**Adrian Boyce
(Facility Manager)**

**Tony Fallick
(Director of SUERC, Head of ICSF)**

ISOTOPE COMMUNITY SUPPORT FACILITY at SUERC

Annual Report - 1999-2000

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1. Service Objectives

The Isotope Community Support Facility (ICSF) supports the Earth Science research community, facilitating access particularly to the Stable Isotope Laboratory of the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre. 100% of our project work is of a collaborative nature, largely with UK University departments. Access to researchers is through application to the Steering Committee (NIGFSC); under special circumstances, the Head of Facility, Prof. Tony Fallick, approves pilot studies preparatory to future applications. Isotope data production and postgraduate student training in technical and interpretative use of light stable isotope (H, C, O & S) analyses lie at the core of the service to be delivered, with access as appropriate to SUERC's comprehensive radiogenic isotope systems. Funding is primarily for one academic (Dr. Boyce) and a 50% technical post (Ms Julie Dougans).

2. Overview and Highlights

This is the second year of the current contract for the ICSF, thus, in December 1999, the ICSF submitted a formal application for renewal by the NERC Services Review Group (SRG). The review was competitive against other NSS Facilities whose Exit Strategy fell simultaneously, as well as bids for new Facilities. Following SRG review, and final ratification by the Earth Science Technology Board, ICSF scored as follows (1 lowest, to 5 highest)

Need	Uniqueness	Service Quality	Science/Training Quality	Overall Rating
4.5	4.0	4.5	4.0	4.25

This resulted in a successful bid, and funding is assured until March 31, 2004. Funding for an additional 50% technician was not granted.

ICSF has given support to and developed **nineteen** existing and new approved projects at **ten** UK Universities and Institutions, with **four** projects currently in development involving a further **two** Universities (Table 1). **Fourteen** postgraduate students (13 PhD) have undergone extensive training in stable isotope techniques, making use of **eleven** isotope ratio mass spectrometers and appropriate preparation systems at SUERC. In this way, ICSF continues to support and promote the government's priority for the long-term health of the science base. There is a clear focus of the research carried out by ICSF on two NERC ENRI's - **Natural Resource Management and Pollution and Waste** - with around 80% of the approved projects falling into these categories. Whilst maintaining focus, we are expanding our portfolio into other ENRI's such as **Global Change** and **Natural Hazards** (see below). Through personal research time, ICSF has established collaboration with colleagues at several international institutions, enhancing the profile of the ICSF/SUERC internationally and cross-fertilising ideas with approved students.

Over the past year, Dr. Boyce has collaboratively published **fifteen** peer-reviewed papers, including nine in a thematic volume arising from Europe's foremost Applied Geology meeting: 5th Biennial SGA/IAGOD conference, London. Dr. Boyce was instrumental in ensuring that PhD students on appropriate approved projects submitted and presented their work at this meeting. In addition, Dr. Boyce has a further **four** papers in press, and **five** in review.

Balancing commitment to existing and developing ICSF projects, ICSF has also continued a limited excursion into directly supporting NERC Thematic Programs and Non-Thematic Research Grants over the past year. Dr. Boyce was a co-PI on the successful **Micro to Macro** project: *Multi-scale fluid-flow path analysis: calibration and modelling using mineralisation systems*. (Barnicoat et al: GST/03/2653; £167,712). Dr. Wilkinson (Imperial College) and Dr. Boyce have been invited to resubmit a NERC Research Grant: *Fluid flow and geochemical interactions in an ancient sub-seafloor ore-forming system*. (GR3/12893; £147,079). These fall clearly in the Natural Resources ENRI. Most recently, Dr. Boyce was a co-PI with Prof. Fallick and Dr. Willan (BAS) in an application to the Antarctic Funding Initiative, which received approval for an outline bid (OB99/08), with the full application (£127,077) currently being considered. The latter marks the first application of ICSF to the ENRI "Global Change".

3. Science

The following two studies are selected as highlights of the approved project work over the past year. ICSF is now established as the stable isotope facility which is pre-eminent in ore deposit studies in the UK. This is reflected in the continuing demand from this sector of the UK Earth Science Community (see Grants, below) and in the publications (Appendix 6A), as well as demand for international collaboration. Cross fertilisation of ideas from international projects with students from approved projects has been a valuable aspect of their training.

a. Cameros Basin Pyrite Study (Raiswell & Bottrell, Leeds in collaboration with Huelva and Madrid, Spain)

Spectacular, museum-quality pyrite cubes are found in the Mesozoic, non-marine, Cameros Basin, in the Iberian ranges of Spain. These pyrites have been traditionally interpreted to be diagenetic in origin, yet their field occurrence, petrography and conventional sulphur isotope composition are more consistent with a hydrothermal metamorphic origin. Using newly developed laser techniques, we analysed the S isotope composition of anhydrite inclusions ($\geq 200\mu\text{m}$ in diameter) and host pyrite to determine whether equilibrium was established at metamorphic temperatures.

Independent, but controversial, evidence of the temperature of pyrite deposition is based on chemical analysis of chlorite inclusions, which suggest that peak metamorphic temperature was around 350°C . Petrographically, these inclusions certainly suggest that the pyrite formed during or just after peak metamorphism. Our programme of analyses gave a mean temperature of some of the analyses of $367\pm 6^\circ\text{C}$. Together with the chlorite analysis, this refuted the earlier diagenetic hypotheses, and confirmed the likely metamorphic origin of the pyrite crystals.

However, further work revealed that although half the py-anhydrite pairs analysed give plausible metamorphic temperatures, the others give equilibrium temperatures consistently around 600°C (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Plot of pyrite versus anhydrite $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ from pyrite crystals in the Cameros Basin, Spain.

This is a very surprising result, and suggests that a process may be taking place hitherto unsuspected. The parallelism of the lines, and the distinct variation of both anhydrite and pyrite $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ suggests that the process may be an artefact of the technique, whereby pyrite S contributes to the anhydrite S during laser combustion. Initially we felt that reproducing exact mixing ratios of varying individual $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ would be most fortuitous, but our experiments show that where pyrite becomes overheated by the laser during anhydrite decomposition, solid phase reaction can incorporate pyrite-sulfur into the sampled gas in a stoichiometric fashion, hence the consistency of the erroneous temperature estimates from this group. Successful analyses were only obtained when overheating of the pyrite was avoided during laser decomposition of anhydrite inclusions. Thus, while the new laser system allows isotopic measurement of anhydrite inclusions too small to be analysed conventionally, caution is warranted! This work applies new system developments funded in part by NSS through Dr. Boyce's personal research and development time, and is now published (Alonso-Azcárate et al - see Annex 5A and 5B).

b. Hydrothermal flow vectors in and proximal to faults active during the early Carboniferous in the basal lens of the Navan Zn+Pb deposit: Evidence from metal distribution trends, mineral textures and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ analyses. (Russell & Blakeman, Glasgow with Dr. John Ashton, Outokumpu Tara Mines Ltd)

The Navan Zn+Pb deposit is Europe's largest producer of Zn, and is the giant deposit of the Irish base-metal orefield, an area that contains the highest concentration of Zn in the world. This study used the sulphur isotope ratio of ore sulphides to locate the feeder structures to the deposit in the largest ore lens (5 Lens, containing ~70 percent of the known tonnage of the ~90Mt orebody). Lead distribution patterns in 5 Lens suggested that the migration of metal-bearing fluids was principally focused by early to mid Lower Carboniferous, near vertical NNE, NE and ENE minor normal faults. These faults predate or are coeval with the major extensional, partly listric, ENE faults which now control the general disposition of the deposit. Could a traverse involving detailed laser $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ analyses of paragenetically well characterised ore sulphides distinguish which of these structures (or both) the fluids feeding the mineralisation utilised? Is there any

evidence that these structures hosted surface fluids during the mineralising event/s?

Sulphides with positive $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values associated with the up-welling, metal-bearing fluid generating the Navan deposit have been highlighted by previous workers (Anderson et al., 1998). On our traverse across five minor and one major faults, positive $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values (+1 to +18‰) were returned in galena, sphalerite and marcasite sampled within 3m of all the faults on the profile (Fig. 2). This strongly suggests that the metal-bearing fluids flowed through all of these fractures. Conversely negative $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values (-1 to -26‰) were returned in galena and sphalerite sampled 3m or more from these faults. In one sample, within 1m of a fault, pyrite $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values are as low as -34‰ indicating that, at times, fluids containing the highly fractionated, bacteriogenic sulphide also circulated within these faults. Furthermore, textures indicating comminution and dissolution, when coupled with the evidence of isotopic overprinting, force the conclusion that mineralization occurred during active faulting.

The minor, near vertical NNE, NE and ENE normal faults displace only early to mid Lower Carboniferous lithologies. There is no evidence of reactivation during

late Carboniferous tectonism, which otherwise affected the major, partly listric, ENE extensional faults. We therefore concluded that the metallogenic event at Navan occurred during early to mid Lower Carboniferous. This conclusion is consistent with published evidence from Navan, as well as with observations on other base-metal sulfide deposits within the Irish Orefield, especially the Silvermines and the Tynagh orebodies. A paper on this work has now been submitted to Economic Geology, following publication of preliminary results in the conference volume of the 5th Biennial SGA/IAGOD meeting (Annex 5A).

Figure 2: Distribution of average ore sulphide $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ relative to fracture planes (0 metres).

4. Future Developments & Targets

Following the rejection of the bid for a further 50% technician time by the Services Review Group, discussions were held with Lin Kay, and it was decided to seek further technical support through collaborative NERC Research Grant applications. This avenue offers opportunity to enhance the capacity of training and throughput of NERC (though not Facility-approved) work by the ICSF. Already, ICSF has been successful in attracting high quality, collaborative science projects using this route (see Sect. 2), and we will endeavour to continue to enhance our profile in this way, in tandem with our commitment to, and development of approved project work. We estimate four new projects being submitted for approval by the Steering Committee during the following year, and will aim to keep the quality and number of peer-reviewed publications at a similar level (i.e. around 4-6 in quality international journals).

5. Summary Performance Information

a. Project Work

Over the year to April 2000, ICSF supported nineteen existing and new approved projects at ten UK Universities and Institutions, with four projects currently in development involving a further two Universities (Table 1). Fourteen postgraduate students (five NERC CASE students and a further five standard NERC students; two commercially funded PhD's; 1 overseas funded PhD; 1 NERC MSc) have undergone intensive training in stable isotope techniques, making extensive use of eleven isotope ratio mass spectrometers and appropriate gas preparation lines and clean labs at SUERC. Annexes 4A&B display % time allocation by Institution, give a breakdown of cost per project allocated on a time spent basis, and provides tracking information on all active projects.

i) Grading of proposals submitted during the year 99/00:

$\alpha 3/4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2/3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	R*	Pilot	Reject
1	2	1	0	0	1	4	1

ii) % distribution and costs of approved and pilot projects supported during the year 99/00 according to science area and ENRI's:

ESTB		Biodiversity		Env. Risk/ Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resource Man.		Poll. & Waste		Other	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
100	88	nil	nil	Pers.	Res.	5	4.54	73	64.2	10	8.4	12	10.7

A high degree of customer satisfaction is noted in letters from PI's requested for the SRG: Annex 6.

b. Publications and invited talks

Data in Annex 5A highlight an exceptional year for peer-reviewed collaborative publications, with fifteen papers published. Following efforts of ICSF to encourage collaborators to present their work at Europe's largest Economic Geology conference last year (SGA-IAGOD, "Mineral Deposits: Processes to Processing", London), nine of the peer-reviewed papers have appeared in the book resulting from the conference. (A further two papers presented data from approved and pilot projects at the conference without Dr. Boyce as co-author.) Abstracts of the five highest rated publications are given in Annex 5B:

- ⇒ two highlight laser S isotope development work and its application to geological problems, including the first ever reported laser anhydrite $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ analyses (see also Sect. 3);
- ⇒ one draws attention to the intriguing occurrence of anomalously low δD fluids associated with basin brine mineralising systems;
- ⇒ one cites the first occurrence of Au mobilised by low temperature, hydrothermal brines, and its significance for Au resource exploitation;
- ⇒ one completely changes the accepted genetic model for France's (and one of Europe's leading) fluorite producing orefields.

Dr. Boyce gave an invited keynote lecture to the Annual Meeting of the Society of General Microbiology at Leeds University, September 1999, entitled: *The role of sulphate reducing bacteria in forming major crustal geochemical anomalies: The Lower Carboniferous Irish Zn+Pb Orefield.*

c. Staff

Again, Ms Julie Dougans has been exemplary in her post, offering diligent and professional assistance to both the ICSF and the Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility (50/50 funded by both Facilities). Her skills in data production, maintenance and student training have once again been invaluable to both Facilities. Dr. Boyce's efforts have also been recognised by Glasgow University who, following formal review, awarded him a discretionary point.

d. Personal Research

Just under 9% of Dr. Boyce's time was spent on personal research, which is within the contractually agreed 15% allocation. Personal Research time this year has allowed ICSF/Dr. Boyce to develop already strong international contacts. For example, the successful multi-disciplinary Sperrins Gold Project (sponsored by the Dept of Economic Development of Northern Ireland), has resulted in the first non-commercial publication from the study was published in 1999 (ref 3: Annex 5A). Another example is the collaboration between ICSF, Yale University and Imperial College which is advancing our understanding of the genesis of the world class Irish Zn+Pb deposits (ref. 13, Annex 5A). A new collaboration with Prof. Sbrana of University of Pisa has begun recently researching the hydrothermal regime of the classic Vesuvius and Vulcano eruptive centres bringing ICSF expertise to bear for the first time on the ENRI – Natural Hazards.

e. Other Information – NERC Grant Development

Over the past year, ICSF has become actively involved in grant applications to NERC. This is a new departure for the Facility, and is not intended to become a significant source of funding or project work. Such applications will be dealt with by Dr. Boyce and Prof. Fallick with due regard to existing commitments, and will only be considered if they dovetail with existing key areas, or offer opportunities to expand the science base of ICSF, and encourage collaboration. During the past year, Dr. Boyce was a co-PI on a successful application to the NERC Thematic Programme - Micro 2 Macro: *Multi-scale fluid-flow path analysis: calibration and modelling using mineralisation systems.* (GST/03/2653; £167,712) PI's: Dr. AC Barnicoat & Prof. BWD Yardley (Leeds); Dr. JJ Wilkinson (Imperial); Prof. CM Graham (Edinburgh); Dr. AJ Boyce (ICSF/SUERC). This project aims to integrate micro- and macroscale structural and geochemical data from the Irish Base-metal Ore Province in particular to understand the fluid flow and fluid mixing responsible for the development of the world class Navan ore deposit. Dr. Boyce has been invited to talk on this project at Geoscience 2000.

NERC Scientific Services

Argon Isotope Facility

at the

Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre

Annual Report

April 1999 - March 2000

Dr. Malcolm S. Pringle
Manager, Argon Isotope Facility

Prof. A. E. Fallick
Director, Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre

1 SERVICE OBJECTIVES

The NERC Argon Isotope Facility (AIF) provides the Earth Science community access to the noble gas analytical facilities, especially Ar/Ar techniques, at the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC). Established in 1994, 1999/2000 was the 6th full year of operation.

2 OVERVIEW AND HIGHLIGHTS

1999/2000 was the first year that both the original mass spectrometer and extraction system (purchased in 1987 by the Scottish Universities) and a new system (funded by NERC Scientific Services over 1996-98 after recommendation by the NIGFSC and 1996 SRG review) were available for use at the same time. This increased capacity had a direct impact on facility output performance, with 5400 Ar/Ar analyses completed during 1999/2000, a 39% increase over 1998/99, and 952 half-day units directly allocatable to AIF projects, a 33% increase over 1998/99.

The full facility equipment inventory is included in Annex 1.3, and remains similar to that originally proposed (inter-changeable CO₂, Nd-YAG, and UV laser systems; ultra low-blank resistance furnaces for each mass spectrometer). However, due to marked performance and safety advantages, as well as a scientific need for large numbers of analyses requiring an infrared laser, we experienced a greater-than-expected demand on the new CO₂ laser system. Thus, a second (ex-demo) CO₂ laser and optic system was acquired from the manufacturer, and upgrading the original SUERC Nd-YAG laser optics was postponed. The second CO₂ laser system has been in near continuous use since Sept 1999.

Community demand for access to the AIF is robust and diverse. It includes both University- and NERC institution-based research. Through 1999/2000, 36 proposals have been submitted to the NIGFSC since the AIF was established (complete project list in Annex 1.5.1). All but three were approved (94%, average grade, α 3.1), including two during 1999/2000 (graded α 3/4 and 3). A further 4 were approved at the May 2000 meeting (average grade, α 3.8). We attribute both the high success rate and long-term rise in average review grade in large part to the investment in time that AIF personnel make with UK geoscientists during the critical planning, pre-proposal stage. We do note a trend to larger, more detailed projects, with increasing analytical demands, suggesting that the total number of projects accommodated per year may actually decrease even as analytical capacity increases. We also note that progress on some approved projects has been hindered by limited sample preparation facilities and expertise at the proposing institution. When possible, we assisted with sample preparation at SUERC, especially when student training was required.

3 SCIENCE

Mica Exhumation: The use of single-grain age determinations from foreland sedimentary sequences has developed into a powerful tool used to document major orogenic exhumation events and sedimentary provenance. Stuart et al. (*submitted*, IP/494/1096) analyzed white mica from the major Late Paleozoic clastic progradation recorded in northern UK sediments, and show both a major 415 Ma source from Scandian nappes produced during the Caledonian orogeny as well as a previously undocumented, 440 Ma pre-Scandian source. Also, discrete post-orogenic uplift events apparently kept the Scandian orogen a major topographic feature and sediment source for over 100 million years after nappe emplacement.

Much of the current effort has focussed on Himalayan evolution. For example, a 55 Ma age for the c. 8-km-thick clastic red bed succession of the Balakot formation, Pakistan, was derived from biostratigraphy on intercalated marls. This 55 Ma age, by >20 m.y. the oldest substantial deposits eroded from the Himalayan mountain belt, has significantly influenced models of major regional and global orogenic processes. However, Najman et al. (*submitted*, IP/455/0995, Fig. 1 a. and b. below) show that Ar/Ar dating of individual detrital white micas include a significant 36-40 Ma mode, incompatible with the biostratigraphy. Instead, new detailed mapping concludes that the marl units are structurally intercalated with the Himalayan-derived sediments, and cannot be used to date the clastic sediments. Therefore, the oldest Himalayan-derived material is at least 15-20 m.y. younger than previously

believed and models based on the older age must be re-evaluated. Figure 1 c. summarises over 1000 single-crystal ages from 5 foreland formations and 2 recent river sediments (Projects IP/428/0994, IP/455/0995, and IP/517/0997). The occurrence of mica equal to the stratigraphic age older than 20 Ma, as well as the divergence from equality younger than 20 Ma, is consistent with a period of rapid exhumation between 20 to 25 Ma (c.f., Chamberlain, 1991), probably extending back to 35 Ma (c.f., Najman et al, 1998), but not from 18 to 3 Ma (as proposed by Copeland and Harrison, 1990).

Figure 1. Individual mica Ar/Ar ages from Himalayan foreland sediments. **a.** Age distribution of 257 individual grains from Balakot Formation, Pakistan, representing first significant non-marine sediments from orogen. **b.** Age spectra of 4 micas from 36-40 Ma population. Note no detectable alteration, thus Balakot must be ≤ 38 Ma, not c. 55 Ma as previously thought. **c.** Mineral versus depositional age for over 1000 crystals from 5 formations and 2 recent river sediments. Note divergence from mineral = stratigraphic age younger than 20 Ma.

Large Igneous Provinces: New results on the duration of volcanism at two of the largest terrestrial basalt systems -- the North Atlantic Tertiary Province (NATP) and Kerguelen Plateau (southern Indian Ocean) -- are contrary to established models. The NATP has been described as a classic rifted volcanic margin, with volcanism occurring over at least 10 m.y. However, our data for the British Tertiary Igneous Province (IP/448/0395), combined with recently available ages from East and West Greenland, suggest that almost all of the initial volcanic products were erupted during the reversed magnetic period Chron 26R, c. 61 to 58 Ma, more consistent with an impacting plume model rather than a longer period of rifting and plume incubation. On the other hand, the c. 50×10^6 km³ Kerguelen Plateau / Ninety East Ridge system has been modeled as a classic plume-head / plume-tail pair, or even a double plume-head with bi-modal volcanism separated by 30 m.y. However, our results from ODP Leg 183 (Dr Pringle sailed as the senior UK representative) indicate that Cretaceous volcanism in the Indian Ocean was certainly not bimodal, and could even represent a relatively constant flux from about 120 to 90 Ma, consistent with a rifted volcanic margin origin.

Quaternary volcanism: Studies focused on preparing the previously reported Montserrat work for publication (Harford, et al., *submitted*, IP/516/0997), and a personal research project on the temporal evolution of the Krafla system, Iceland (with K Saemundson, Icelandic Energy Authority). 18 ages on 9 samples spanning the entire stratigraphic succession at Krafla yielded precision of better than 1% on rhyolite and 3-5 k.y. on basalt, and show for the first time that (1) an Icelandic central volcano evolves in less than c. 250 k.y., (2) the significant caldera collapse/ignimbrite formed at c. 110 ka, and (3) the complicated glacial-interglacial volcanic stratigraphy of the system is consistent with known climatic records. However, the ages of several tall (600-800 m), subglacially-erupted rhyolite domes suggest that the ice thickness around Krafla at c. 90 ka was significantly greater than previously thought.

4 FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

We plan to take delivery of a heavy liquid overflow centrifuge early in 2000/01, completing installation of state-of-the-art mineral separation facilities at SUERC. This fulfils a critical need that we have encountered with some approved projects, apparently arising as at least some university departments cut back on both sample preparation facilities and experienced personnel. The AIF is fortunate that both Mr Davidson and Dr Pringle have had significant experience in such techniques. Also, and again with partial support from the NERC Scientific Services Capital Budget, we plan to upgrade and repair the original CO₂ laser and temperature probe as well as design a new diamond viewport in order to extend the technique to smaller and/or younger samples.

5 SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

5.1 Numbers and percentage of α -graded projects supported

Three new proposals were reviewed during 1999/2000. Two received grades of α 3/4 and α 3 and were approved; the third received a grade of α 2 and was not approved. Four more proposals were approved in May 2000 (average grade α 3.8). Full titles and details are included in Appendix 1.5.1.

22 projects were supported during 1999/200, including new analytical work on 8 and support for 9 PhD studentships. These include 15 approved projects (71%, average grade α 3.3), development efforts leading to 5 new proposals (5%), 4 pilot projects (4%), and in-house R&D (20%). Time allocation by grade and institution is summarised in Fig. 2., full details are listed in Annex 1.5.4.

Figure 2. 1999/2000 AIF total time allocation (952 allocatable half day units) by review grade and institution.

5.2 Percentage distribution and costs of projects according to Science Areas

		NERC		Science Area					NERC ENRI					
Atmos	Earth	Marine	T&F	EO	SBA	Polar	Biodiversity	Env Risks	Global	Nat RM	P & W	Other		
£ 0	£ 165k	£ 0	£ 0	£ 0	£ 0	£ 0	£ 0	£ 6.2k	£ 64.8	£ 47.0	£ 0	£ 47.0		
0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4%	39%	28%	0%	28%		

5.3 Publications

Seven manuscripts were published in the Earth Science peer-reviewed literature during 1999/2000. In addition, six additional manuscripts were in press or under review, three Ph.D. studentships supported by the AIF were completed, and at least 11 conference abstracts were presented (complete lists in Annex 1.6). Annex 2.3 includes full abstracts for all published, in press, and submitted manuscripts, as well as a representative selection of conference abstracts.

5.4 Targets and Milestones

1999/2000 was the first full year that both the original and new mass spectrometer and extraction systems were available for use at the same time, and continued the steady increase in analytical productivity which has characterised the AIF since inception (Fig. 3). The new system was operational most of the year, with less than 2 months down-time due to relatively routine maintenance. We were not as lucky with the (now 12-year-old) original SUERC mass spectrometer, which required 2 filament changes, leading to about 5 months of lost analytical time. However, the SUERC Ar/Ar laboratory still managed 6145 total analyses on the two systems; 5400 (88%) were for AIF projects. This is well in excess of the number anticipated in the original AIF Service Level Agreement, and a 39% increase over the number of analyses completed during 1998/99 (Fig. 3). We also note that the facility, especially Mr Davidson, spent approximately seven weeks training and assisting 5 different post-graduate students in mineral separation techniques on the SUERC sample preparation equipment.

Figure 3. Number of Ar/Ar analyses performed at SUERC since inception of the AIF in 1994.

5.5 Financial Details FY1999/2000

Full Economic Cost:	£165k	Recurrent Allocation:	£119.4k
Unit Cost:	£173 / half day unit (952 allocatable half day units)	Capital Allocation:	£8.2k

5.6 Service Management & Staffing

The AIF is staffed, fully at SUERC, as follows:

Manager:	Dr Malcolm S Pringle	since Apr 1994	Grade RIII @ 100%, 5-year contract
Technician:	Mr B K Davidson	since Apr 1996	Grade F @ 100%, 5-year contract

1. Service Objectives

The Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility (MEMF) provides access to state-of-the-art electron beam-induced X-ray microanalysis facilities for those UK based researchers (both students and more established workers) who operate within the NERC remit areas (Earth Science, Environmental Science and Science Based Archaeology). In addition to the access to instrumentation, users are trained in the use of the equipment and given advice on the interpretation and evaluation of the data that they acquire. This advice is provided both by the staff of the Facility and through discussions with academic staff with the relevant expertise in the Department of Earth Sciences, University of Manchester. The MEMF is also committed to further development of applications of microbeam methods of analysis to Earth Science, Environmental and Archaeological problems.

2. Overview and Highlights

The reporting period has seen the first year of full operation of the CAMECA SX100 Electron microprobe; the novel features of this advanced instrument have facilitated new areas of research in disparate fields, as described below. The new service that can be provided as a result of the acquisition of the SX100 was given an official launch at an event in October, at which we were pleased to welcome representatives of NERC and the user community. The new capabilities and the full range of instrumentation available within the facility have been publicised by a poster distribution to relevant departments nationally. The service also hosted a meeting of CAMECA UK users in December 1999.

Dr C.L. Hayward joined the service in September 1999, taking up a NERC (NSS) funded position. In addition to helping in the running of the service, through advising and training users, Dr Hayward is particularly involved in the development of new methods and applications in microanalysis. He has commenced research activities in the areas concerned with microprobe determination of oxidation states of transition metals, low level trace element determination and low atomic number elemental analysis. Of particular note are the initial detection limits measured using the SX100 for elements such as nickel and copper in natural pyrite, which are in the range of 4-8 ppm. Additional experimentation with analytical conditions is likely to further reduce detection limits to 1-2 ppm levels for certain elements. The ability to identify the oxidation state of iron, manganese and other elements by the microprobe would represent a major advance, as previous studies have not led to rapid and routine measurements. Work at the MEMF has commenced with the investigation of a range of iron-bearing mineral. Samples have been independently analysed by Mossbauer spectroscopy, in order to obtain quantitative data on iron oxidation state for comparison with microprobe data. X-ray spectra collected using the SX100 indicate spectral shifts in iron and oxygen X-ray lines. Detailed analysis of these X-ray spectra has been enabled by the recent acquisition of sophisticated spectral fitting software. A detailed study of the effect of crystallographic orientation and mineral chemistry on boron analysis in certain borate minerals has been started.

Funding has been obtained during the reporting period for new instrumentation, a replacement X-ray analysis system for the JEOL 6400 instrument (funded by the Earth Sciences Department, Manchester University) and a new Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) funded as part of an award from the Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF). The latter instrument will be a state-of-

the-art, high-resolution field emission microscope with both an environmental chamber and a cryogenic chamber, as well as energy dispersive X-ray analysis capability. It will enable the high-resolution imaging and analysis of "wet" samples and delicate materials such as microbes and biofilms.

The new system for the JEOL 6400 will be available from June 2000, with immediate benefits to service users. The Environmental SEM forms part of the "Research Centre in Molecular Environmental Science" This JIF-financed initiative is a community facility that will greatly enhance national capability to undertake fundamental molecular scale research on the materials and processes that are at the core of Environmental Science. It is anticipated that this instrument will be on-stream by late Spring, 2001.

Staff have been engaged in a number of collaborative international projects, including work associated with the development of microprobe techniques and applications. For example, Mr Plant and Professor Henderson are currently working with the CAMECA company (France) to derive revised and improved mineral formula recalculation procedures for use with the instruments manufactured by the company. A joint investigation involving Professor D. J. Vaughan and Professor J. R. Craig, (Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University) has been concerned with mapping the distribution of both major and trace elements in weathered spent munitions from firing ranges from localities in the eastern USA (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: X-ray maps of lead L-alpha (left) and oxygen K-alpha (right) collected using the Cameca SX100. The images are of a piece of lead shot, and show leaching of lead and the growth of secondary oxide minerals in the leached rim.

This study, aimed at an understanding of the environmental impact of such "waste" material has employed the unique elemental mapping capabilities of the SX100. In collaboration with Professor C.M.B. Henderson, Dr. D. Seward (ETH Zurich, Switzerland), visited the facility to undertake microanalysis of apatite as a compliment to fission track studies designed to yield exhumation ages of continental crust in Madagascar.

3. Science

The Facility has continued to provide data for projects across a wide range of science. Some examples include the following.

Dr K Taylor (MMU) has examined metal uptake into early diagenetic mineral cements and the applications of this to contaminated modern sediments. A primary control on the environmental fate of metals in contaminated sediments is the uptake of trace metals by early diagenetic minerals. Information from modern sediments, however, is limited by both the slow rate of mineral precipitation and the problems inherent in sample preparation. The aim of this research is to determine the timing and extent of trace metal uptake in early diagenetic minerals (carbonates, sulphides) from ancient sediments, which have undergone clear early diagenetic pathways. This data will form the basis for much-needed quantitative information on the role of early diagenetic mineral cements on contaminant behaviour in aquatic systems.

Dr K Hudson-Edwards (Birkbeck) has examined the environmental impact of heavy metal contamination of river systems fed from regions of intensive mining activity. The Rio Pilcomayo in Bolivia is heavily contaminated with heavy metals (e.g. Zn, Ag, Sb, Pb) derived from 450 years of mining of the Cerro Rico precious metal-polymetallic tin ore deposits. Microprobe analysis of minerals in river sediment samples for the project 'Remediation of Metal Pollution in the Rio Pilcomayo' has revealed that sulphides from discharged tailings are the major hosts of the contaminant elements.

Mr T Bailey (UCL) used the facility to make detailed trace element distribution profiles from fossil belemnites, as part of a project that also incorporates data derived from the NERC laser-ablation ICPMS facility. This study has benefited from other recent work by Mr Plant on microprobe analysis of trace elements in carbonate minerals.

Professor D. Flynn (Earth Sciences, Liverpool) made use of the facility to finalise collection of analytical data prior to memoir publication relating to NERC and BGS mapping contracts of Shetland.

The area of Science Based Archaeology continues to be well supported, for example Ms K Welham (Department of Archaeology and Prehistory, University of Sheffield) has continued a major program of analysis of medieval archaeological glasses and synthetic analogues.

4. Future Developments

A major part of the establishment of the "Research Centre in Molecular Environmental Science" will be the procurement of a Philips Field Emission ESEM. A new Laboratory to house this instrument is to be constructed alongside the existing MEMF laboratory suite. As noted above, this new instrument will combine high-resolution electron microscopy with the ability to perform *in situ* microanalysis of delicate materials in their natural states. This will allow examination of a range of samples from the natural environment which have hitherto been impossible to analyse. The investigation of sensitive archaeological items without the need for potentially damage inducing specimen preparation is an additional, exciting new prospect. Building works associated with the new Research Centre will refurbish most of the basement wing of the Manchester Earth Sciences Department which houses the MEMF. These will commence in September 2000. Careful consideration has been given to arrangements which will ensure continued uninterrupted access to the MEMF throughout the duration of works.

Operational difficulties with energy dispersive microanalysis systems from the Oxford Instruments company has obliged the service to look for replacement equipment. The University of Manchester has provided funds for a new X-ray detector and analysis system for the JEOL 6400 analytical SEM. After careful evaluation of the systems available, an IMIX system from the PGT company was chosen and ordered. Delivery and installation is scheduled for May 2000. This system will offer a number of analytical improvements over the previous instrumentation, including low atomic

number element quantification and the ability to derive quantitative analyses from micro-area image acquisitions. An approved allocation from the NSS Capital budget will allow replacement of the analyser electronics and computer acquisition system for the Geoscan microprobe during the next financial year. As on-going research by Dr Hayward Mr Plant and Professor Vaughan, concerned with trace element analysis, will involve running the SX100 microprobe at its operational limits, some hardware modifications to this instrument may be required.

5. Summary of Performance Information

Numbers and percentages of α -graded proposals supported.

Twelve users accessed the service in the reporting period.

The projects were graded as follows; α 4 (33%), α 3 (42%), α 2 (25%).

Publications for the Calendar Year 1999

We are aware of 4 publications, by means of literature survey and direct notification by users. We have been notified of approximately 6 further publications, which are in preparation for publication during 2000-2001. The publication list is attached at Appendix 6.

Targets and Milestones

The CAMECA SX100 and the Jeol 6400 instruments have exceptionally heavy workloads. NERC service access is maintained alongside instrument time required by the Earth Science Department and other Departments of the University of Manchester and UMIST.

The first session for a user at the facility is often devoted to preliminary evaluation of the samples to be analysed, and the establishment of an appropriate analytical regime with the necessary elemental standardisations. On a number of occasions in the reporting period, it has been possible to set aside sessions for instrument set-up in advance of the arrival of the user. Working in this way has ensured that analytical throughput is maximised whilst a user is on site. To optimise the use of the service, it is proposed that this approach be employed whenever possible.

Evaluation of applications to the service by the local steering committee has proved to be most beneficial, with preliminary grading at this level serving to facilitate rapid access to the service.

Downtime on some instruments in the last year has resulted in lost access time to local users, (NERC service access remained prioritised and did not suffer, although access to the Geoscan instrument for one user was postponed for a few weeks). Provision of replacement instrumentation, detailed elsewhere, will avoid a repetition of this situation.

Financial details

MEMF allocation for 1999/2000 was £55.51K (£35.79, staff costs; £8.95, overheads; £10.77, other recurrent) No capital budget funds were requested for this period.

Service Management & Staffing:

Head of Service	Professor D. J. Vaughan
Service Manager	Mr D. A. Plant, Senior Experimental Officer (30% NERC)
PDRA	Dr C. L. Hayward (100% NERC)
SEM technician	Mr S. Caldwell (20% NERC)

1999/2000 Annual Report: Open University Uranium Series Facility, Radiogenic Isotope Geochemistry Group, Department of Earth Sciences.

1. OUUSF service objectives:

- To facilitate high quality collaborative research into natural processes using U-series isotopes.
- To provide training in the laboratory techniques and the underlying theory for students and research scientists working in areas of NERC related science, such as recent volcanism, Quaternary climate change, archaeology and hydrology.
- To develop improved analytical techniques for the mass spectrometric analysis of U-series isotopes in natural samples.

The major objective of the OUUSF is to provide instruction, advice and participation with the design of post-graduate training, post-doctoral and research projects. This involves direct one-to-one training and supervision of post-graduate students and post-doctoral workers in the laboratory, with subsequent interpretation and publication of the results. Detailed instruction is given in the techniques and procedures of chemical preparation, in the operation of thermal- and plasma-ionisation mass spectrometers, and in quality control and data analysis. Students and post-doctoral workers participate fully in seminars and discussion groups with staff and students in the Department of Earth Sciences.

2. Overview and Highlights

OUUSF became operational in the middle of 1998 with funding until April 2001. A formal application for renewal of funding was submitted in December 1999 to the NERC Services Review Group 2000 and the facility was rated as follows:

Need	Uniqueness	Service Quality	Science/Training quality	Average
4	3	4.5	4.5	4.25

Subject to approval by the ESTB, funding will be available until April 2004.

OUUSF now has a functioning Website at <http://www2.open.ac.uk/rii/nssindex.htm> that has already attracted additional interest in the facility.

U-series data of archaeological bone yield internally verifiable ages using the Diffusion-Adsorption model for selected bone sections. Reliable ages on fossil bone are critical to many studies in archaeology and recent evolutionary change, and so this new approach represents a highly significant break-through.

Using U-series dating of minerals and glass it is now possible to investigate the timing of events in the pre-eruption evolution of magmas, and to compare those with the volcanic record, to determine links between events underground and the timing of volcanic eruptions. Other achievements are reported in more detail:

3. Science

Global Change

The geological and fossil record does not translate simply and directly into meteorological variables such as temperature, wind direction or rainfall, but so-called 'proxy' data may be calibrated to meteorological variables. Such proxies allow climatic reconstructions and include pollen, *Coleoptera*, tree ring widths, and geochemical data, mostly from precipitated carbonates, such as corals, molluscs, lake-sediments and most frequently, speleothems. Geochemical data include Oxygen and Boron isotope ratios, trace element ratios, humic acid contents and others. All geochemical data can be plotted against depth, and many can be seen to vary in harmony. However depth, or counted layers in speleothems, are at best only a proxy for time. As there is also growing uncertainty as to whether growth layers in speleothems are strictly annual in nature, what is actually needed is an absolute timescale to which all proxy data can be evaluated. Although volcanic ash layers can provide important time-markers, and C-14 is important in dating the last 40 Ka, the overwhelming advantage of TIMS U-series analyses is that it extends the dating range to 350 Ka.

U-series dating is at its most powerful for dating speleothems, however, karst caves are not necessarily the most promising environments to find suitable climate proxies, especially since the Oxygen isotope data in cave carbonates are often ambiguous. One project that has addressed climate reconstruction has been undertaken by Baker/McGarry and combines the painstaking collection of pollen in stalagmite samples and the analysis of organic acids, which are probably indicating rainfall, with U-series dating.

McGarry has analysed a series of stalagmites and an important site in the Mendip Hills provides a 10 cm flowstone sample that is bracketed by ages of 72.9 +/- 0.7Ka to 66 +/- .5Ka year, indicating that this sample grew rapidly during the early part of the last glaciation, in Oxygen Isotope Stage 4. During more benign conditions (interglacials), land is covered with temperate forest. Since free water and vegetation are both required, speleothems should not grow during glacial periods. This speleothem, which has formed during OIS 4, has yielded pollen of thermophilous species including oak, ash and hazel, which suggests that climatic conditions in the south of England at this time were not as severe as previously supposed. The organic acids in this flowstone also suggest fairly wet soil conditions with little humification of organic matter. All the stalagmites studied by McGarry have yielded pollen assemblages that indicate temperate forest, even though land ice was close to these caves at some times.

Archaeology

The evolution of our hominid ancestors and the way they have manipulated and reacted within their environments captures the imagination and for this reason the initiation of two pilot projects which investigate early behaviour and engineering are particularly exciting. The first pilot project addresses the timing of the presence of Middle Stone Age Man in Africa, and the beginnings of the artistic nature of Homo Sapiens, and the second project the indirect dating of a waterworks system in the City of David (Jerusalem).

The Twin Rivers Middle Stone Age site in Zambia is a collapsed cave system that contains dateable

speleothem deposits interstratified with lithics and faunal remains. The site is particularly important because of the discovery of some 307 pigment-fragments that were probably used for body adornment during hunting and other ceremonial rituals. Mineral analysis of the seven colours of pigments found at the site has revealed that they were actually sourced some kilometres away from the site and ground into a paste on specialised paint-grinding equipment. Such evidence suggests that these Stone Age inhabitants were producing painted art long before they evolved into anatomically modern *Homo Sapiens*.

Recent excavations at Twin Rivers have provided speleothem material that has been TIMS dated to between 137Ka to >400Ka with the majority of dates falling within the 240-30Ka BP range, believed to be the range for African Middle Stone Age. The archaeological and hominid sequence at Twin Rivers is itself bracketed between >350-269Ka. The results from this study so far provide a chronology for the Middle Pleistocene occupation of sub-Saharan Africa where ritual behaviour apparently occurred alongside technological advances in weapon manufacture, which presumably allowed the evolution of pre-anatomically modern hominids into anatomically modern *Homo Sapiens*. TIMS dating at this site thus suggests that the roots of modern ritualistic behaviour, such as early Man's artistic nature, may have emerged much earlier than previously thought in Africa.

The second pilot study addresses the engineering feat of constructing a subterranean waterworks system beneath the oldest inhabited section of Jerusalem and has long provided a puzzle to biblical historians and archaeologists as to how and when the sections of channels, tunnels, pools and vertical shafts were made. The likely construction date and method are in dispute as written evidence is conflicting. The failure of the Assyrian King Sennacherib to take Jerusalem from King Hezekiah (727-698BC) was credited to the functioning of the aquaduct bringing in essential water allowing the city to survive the siege although other historians have suggested construction ages of 1000BC, 141-37BC and 2000-1800BC from the literature. Detailed investigations reveal that the inner tunnel walls were carefully sealed with plaster and mortar to aid in waterproofing the structure fairly early on in the tunnel's history.

From an inscription at the tunnel's southern end, the complex 534 metre route was constructed by two teams working from either end of the tunnel and finally meeting at the middle to complete the aquaduct, although the methods used for directing the two teams are still hotly debated. Geological surveys have suggested that karstic dissolution channels and geological fissures only partly determined the route taken by the tunnel and most of the route was somehow navigated by the construction teams. Over time, the plaster has been covered with flowstone which is now several centimetres thick and this material has allowed the first age determinations on material from this tunnel.

TIMS dating of this material will provide a post quem age on the tunnel construction. Radiocarbon dating of plant material trapped within the plaster from the site has yielded dates of 780BC and 550BC and initial TIMS dates from this study suggest that the age of the tunnel falls within the range 442-1951BC. The age determinations are, however, heavily dependent on the use of an appropriate detrital Th correction, as the flowstone contains large amounts of detrital ²³²Th and to date we have been only able to tie the flowstone age to the earlier dates of the historical accounts of the tunnel's presence.

4. Future developments

Anticipated facility developments include: 1) the intention to attract archaeological research projects using our bone dating techniques based on a diffusion-adsorption model. 2) continued efforts to develop techniques to deal with detrital ²³⁰Thorium, 3) incorporate our new Plasma Ionisation Mass Spectrometer as a complementary analytical tool to TIMS.

5. Summary of Performance Information

5.1 NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities Steering Committee approved 5 projects in 1999. All projects scored α3-4. Two projects have Post-Doctoral researchers attached to them, one a Leverhulme Fellow, the other a Dorothy Hodgkin Fellow, the latter post-doctoral project is also linked to a NERC small grant. OUUSF staff members have had discussions with members of the NERC community on a dozen occasions to advice on the suitability, mostly for dating purposes, on a variety of samples. This has resulted in 5 small

'service to the community' and 'proof of concept' projects. Some of these projects may result in full proposals in due course and currently several other scientists have shown interest in the facility and are actively seeking suitable sample material.

5.2 To date, samples analysed by the laboratory comprise 40% SBA, FEC 22636, and 60% ES, FEC 37576, NERC Sciences areas, and 36% GC, FEC 21731, 21% ER&H, FEC 12676, NERC ENRI

5.3a ES publications

Baker, A., Caseldine, C.J., Gilmour, M., Charman, D., Proctor, C.J., Hawkesworth, C.J. and Phillips, N. (1999). Stalagmite luminescence and peat humification records of palaeomoisture for the last 2500 years. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.*, 165, 157-162.

Genty, D., Massault, M., Gilmour, M., Baker, A., Verheyden, S. and Keppens, E. (1999). Calculation of post dead carbon proportion and variability by the comparison of AMS 14C and TIMS U/Th ages on two Holocene stalagmites. *Radiocarbon*, 41, 251-270.

Roberts, M.S., Smart, P.L., Hawkesworth, C.J., Perkins, W.T. and Pearce, N.J.G. (1999). Trace element variations in coeval Holocene speleothems from GB cave, southwest England. *Spec. Iss. The Holocene*, 9, 707-714.

5.3b SBA Publications

Pike, A.W.G., Nielsen-Marsh, C., and Hedges, R.E.M., (in press). Modelling Bone Dissolution Under Different Hydrological regimes. *Archaeometry*.

5.4 Targets and milestones

Due to a mishap during regular maintenance of the mass spectrometer, the instrument was out of action for 120 days, during May to October. This protracted period was due to the fact that the manufacturers supplied an inappropriate spare part that was not vacuum-tight and were unable to supply a functional part immediately. Modifications and repairs were then made 'in-house' and have proved to be effective. Re-scheduling and extensive work during unsociable hours by staff and post-graduates ensured that lost time was made up quickly, and we were back on schedule after the Christmas period.

A user survey has been carried out and was submitted with the Funding Renewal Application to the Services Review Group 2000. No complaints were received.

5.5 Financial details

	Actual, approx.	Budget	Surplus
Research staff	£15306		
Technical staff	£25604	£43,020	£2109
Travel	£1740		
Recurrent costs	£14929	£12,500	£0.00
Subtotal	£57580	£55,520	-£2429
Indirect costs	£18818	£19,790	£971
Total	£74249	£75,310	£1061

No capital expenditure is planned.

5.6 Service staffing

Peter van Calsteren	Senior Project Officer Grade IV, 0%
Mabs Gilmour	Project Officer Grade II, 20%
Anthony Cohen	Research fellow Grade III, 50%
Jo Rhodes	Technician, Grade D, analyst, 100%
Janet Dryden	Secretary, 0%

2.3 MARINE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

NERC Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS)

Annual Report and Forward Look - April 1999-March 2000

Summary Report

1. Service Objectives

The objective of the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS) is to provide the UK environmental research community and other potential users with remotely sensed data from several Earth observation satellites and to provide advice and support in the use of the data. The data are used in most areas of environmental science, with marine, atmospheric and terrestrial sciences accounting for most of the user community. Information derived from the data is used to provide a greater understanding of the Earth's environmental processes. The complete archive of satellite data currently comprises around 45,000 recordings dating back to 1978, much of which are unique.

2. Overview and Highlights

Service: DSRS acquires, archives and distributes data from polar orbiting satellites. Recent data sets are available in real-time, while requests for archive data are generally processed within a few days. Most data are distributed via the Web and occasionally on computer media or in the form of hard copy imagery. The receiving station exists primarily to serve NERC users, although data collected are also available to anyone on a commercial basis.

Satellites: Data is currently collected from the NOAA satellite series carrying the AVHRR instruments (1978-present) and SeaStar satellite carrying the SeaWiFS ocean colour instrument (1997-present). The receiving station also receives data from Meteosat.

The AVHRR (Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer) is sensitive in the visible, near-infrared, and the infrared 'window' regions. It has a spatial resolution of around 1.1km. Applications of AVHRR data cover marine, atmospheric and terrestrial environmental science.

SeaWiFS is an ocean colour instrument and yields information such as concentration levels for phytoplankton (microscopic marine plants). The data are of great significance to the marine community in studying oceanic factors affecting global change and biogeochemical cycles. Only researchers authorised by NASA may have access to SeaWiFS data. DSRS continues to operate with a real time SeaWiFS licence, very few of which have been issued outside of the USA. This is a measure of DSRS's reputation and the international significance of the supported research.

Partners: One of the key activities is provision of data to the Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service (RSDAS) at Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML). RSDAS staff are specialists in processing data to generate products for use by the scientific community (marine scientists in particular), without the need for further processing. Archive data are provided in response to RSDAS/user requests. An important feature of this service is the rapid turn round of data from reception at Dundee to delivery of processed imagery to the environmental scientist in the field, particularly those onboard NERC research vessels. All new data received at Dundee is immediately transferred to RSDAS, where processed products are generated and made available to users in near-real time. This is important in the planning of a research cruise and crucial during the cruise, when imagery is used to guide the research vessel to maximise the success and cost effectiveness of the cruise. Programmes such as BENBO, LOIS, PRIME and OMEX have benefited. DSRS (in conjunction with RSDAS) provided primary support for the SeaWiFS Exploitation Initiative thematic programme.

Archive: Throughout the year a total of 3735 satellite recordings were added to the archive (NOAA-2978, SeaWiFS-757), representing a success rate of 99.63% based on the number of scheduled recordings. The servicing of data requests is given priority, with archive preservation work taking place as time permits. The archive has been accumulated over 23 years and forms a valuable resource for the environmental research community. Due to problems with degradation, the entire magnetic tape archive (1978-97) is being copied to CD-ROM. The work has been in progress for over 4 years and a milestone has been reached this year, in that all data on reel-to-reel HDDT tape, most vulnerable to degradation, have now been copied. Remaining tape based data are on VHS cassette which shows no sign of degrading yet - the data will be copied nevertheless. In total, 20000 recordings have been copied with 13000 remaining and at the current rate of progress the transcription will be complete within 2-3 years. Two copies of each data set are being made with one copy being held at Dundee to support user requests, and the other copy being stored at the NERC EODC (Earth Observation Data Centre) in a fire proof safe.

Public Understanding of Science: As well as providing data services for scientific users, DSRS promotes public understanding of science by free access to information and imagery via the Web. An article in NERC News (Winter 1999) by R. Reynolds, a DSRS user, was aimed at schoolteachers and described the weather satellite images available on the DSRS site. The intention was to promote the images as a way of learning basic science and to raise awareness of the archive and services.

The University of Dundee is hosting the 4th International Satellite Direct Broadcast conference in July 2000, with scientists and engineers from across the world attending to discuss the latest developments in satellite ground station technology and applications of direct broadcast data.

New Developments: DSRS is currently working on a new system to receive and process X-Band MODIS data from the NASA EOS series of satellites. Funded by NERC, this system is intended to address future needs of the user community. MODIS extends upon the capabilities of both AVHRR and SeaWiFS by providing many more spectral channels with increased radiometric resolution and in some cases improved spatial resolution. Upgrade work has been ongoing for the past three years to cope with the huge increase in data rate/volume for MODIS. Initial work included design and installation of a new antenna, procurement of a data receiver/demodulator, and upgrades to the internal computer network. Further progress was restricted due to launch delays for the first EOS-MODIS satellite (Terra) - this eventually took place in December 1999. A high specification file server/data processing workstation and data archiving system were purchased around this time and integrated into the DSRS set up. Software has also been developed and acquired to process data from received (raw) format through Level 0 to Level 1 for delivery to RSDAS and users. At the time of writing, direct broadcast of MODIS data from Terra had just become operational, the first data had been received by DSRS and testing/evaluation of the processing chain was being carried out.

3. Science

DSRS is mainly involved in data acquisition/distribution and is not generally required to advise at the project proposal stage. Information and advice is regularly provided on imagery and products, especially for new users. Examples of projects supported during 1999/2000 are given below.

Determining Short-Term Changes in the Flooding Regime of Climatically Sensitive Playas (Dr. R Bryant, Geography, UO Sheffield)

The aim is to examine the application of a time series of AVHRR satellite images to the study of a climatically sensitive closed basin in Southern Tunisia. Specific objectives are to: (i) monitor monthly changes in the lake area and seasonal water balance, (ii) determine the detailed hydrological response of the playa to rainfall, (iii) examine the extent to which remote sensing of playa flooding may be

used to give information on contemporary changes in regional rainfall patterns in other parts of North Africa. *These objectives are directly relevant to NERC requirements for a greater understanding of Global Change over a range of time and space scales.*

HYDALP - Hydrology of Alpine and high latitude basins

(Prof. S Quegan, SCEOS, UO Sheffield)

This EU project involves collaborators from Sheffield, Bern and Innsbruck Universities, Macaulay Land Use Research Institute and Swedish Hydrological & Meteorological Institute. The project uses hydrological models for snowmelt runoff simulation and forecasting in the Scottish Highlands, Swiss and Austrian Alps and Northern Sweden. The models use meteorological and hydrological inputs which are potentially best provided by Earth Observation data such as AVHRR. The aim is to use the EO data to improve monitoring and forecasting of runoff from alpine and high latitude basins and to prepare a basis for the operational use of the information.

Mesoscale Orographic Processes

(Prof. S Mobbs, Environment Centre, UO Leeds)

The research is supported through NERC's Clouds, Storms and Regional Meteorology core strategic funding. It is known that hills of particular length scales and heights are important to large scale flow, as they generate significant drag through various processes. Field experiments and numerical model development are being used to investigate how processes interact and contribute to net drag. It is anticipated that the models could be used operationally to make detailed forecasts. The work will benefit greatly from the use of AVHRR images to reveal lee wave clouds and to provide real atmospheric data for the verification of models. The imagery will also be used to make observations of convection over mountain ranges for an investigation into orographic triggering of convection.

4. Future Developments

There are outstanding issues to be dealt with from the X-Band upgrade program. A second antenna, with a 2.8m dish and new design of pedestal, is being manufactured and will be installed more favourably than the first on the UO Dundee Dental School building (no data loss due to surrounding buildings). This will replace an existing 1.8m NOAA/SeaWiFS antenna. The new antenna will become the main operational system for EOS-MODIS, but will also be capable of NOAA/SeaWiFS reception so that current recording schedules are maintained. A small, inexpensive 1.2m antenna is to be manufactured and installed temporarily to ensure NOAA/SeaWiFS reception schedules are maintained while installation, testing and commissioning of the new X-Band antenna is carried out. The 1.2m system will subsequently be available as a backup unit to be rapidly deployed as required.

As MODIS data become available, processing software to generate formats required by RSDAS and users must be tested, online quicklook browse facilities and Web based ordering of data should also be provided. There may be network issues to resolve to ensure near-real time support is possible.

More generally, provision of an Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) for tracking/recording equipment and computer workstations is to be investigated. This is in the light of lengthy mains power interruptions which resulted in lost recordings during 1999/2000. A UPS would also protect vulnerable workstations against short term mains problems (sags, surges, spikes etc.) .

The possibility of extending the facility further to receive and distribute data from other satellites will be investigated. Additional antennas and suitable sites are required, user feedback must be obtained on preferred satellites/instruments and capital funding must be secured.

5. Summary of Performance Information

(i) Projects Supported/Grades

	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	Reject	Total
Standard Projects	3	10	14	1	0	0	0	28
Student Projects	1	3	5	0	0	0	0	9

(ii) Percentage Distribution and Cost of Projects According to Science Area and NERC ENRI's

Science Area:

Atmospheric		Earth		Marine		T & FW		EO		SBA		Polar	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
9.8	25.9	10.6	28.1	42.6	113.1	9.1	24.1	9.7	25.8	8.6	23.0	9.6	25.6

NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues:

Biodiversity		Env. Risk/Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resources		Pollution/ Waste	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
12.9	34.4	15.5	41.1	40.1	106.6	18.7	49.5	12.8	34.0

(iii) Publications for the Calendar Year 1999

An extensive search of the BIDS ISI database plus feedback from RSDAS and users identified 22 refereed and 27 non-refereed, DSRs engendered publications/proceedings with NERC funded authors. The table below relates these to science areas. A further 9 publications/proceedings were identified with non-NERC funded authors, e.g. overseas scientists - classed as commercial clients.

Atmospheric	Earth	Marine	T & FW	EO	SBA	Polar
6	2	31	4	6	0	0

(iv) Targets & Milestones

Distribution of service capacity between the main tasks:

Satellite Recording/Archiving etc.	User Requests	Tape Archive Copying to CD-ROM
10%	40%	50%

Satellite recording equipment was used each day throughout the year:

Scheduled Recordings	Successful Recordings	Success Rate	Data Acquisition
3749	3735	99.63%	280 Gbytes (approx.)

Only notable downtime was due to two interruptions to UO Dundee mains supply. Total downtime was 4-5 hours (< 0.1% of capacity) and accounted for almost half the satellite passes not recorded.

(v) Financial Details 1999/2000

Full Cash Cost	Unit Cost@5333hours pa	Recurrent Allocation	Capital Expend.	Revenue
£266.9k	£50.05	£228.13k *	£44.16k	£22.31k

* Total Salaries = £ 161.70k, Overheads @ 25% x Total Salaries = £ 40.43 k, Consumables & Travel = £ 26.00k

(vi) Service Management/Staffing

NERC funded	UO Dundee funded
1 Grade 2 Scientific Officer/Station Manager (100%)	1 Station Director (part time@30%)
2 Grade 1 Software/Systems Specialists (100%)	
1 Grade D Clerical Assistant (100%)	
4 Grade C Technicians - 1 maintenance, 3 shift (100%)	

Fig. 1 - DSRS experimental X-Band Antenna for NASA EOS-MODIS data reception.

Fig. 2 - First MODIS data received by DSRS from the EOS am satellite (Terra) and showing the UK. Band 31, 1225 UTC on 8 May 2000. (calibrated by UO Wisconsin)

Fig. 3 - DSRS Web site registered user and data request statistics.

Fig. 4 - Registered user areas of interest.

(NOTE - In order to illustrate the DSRS contribution to public understanding of science, the above figures include the huge number of users of and requests for free access, non-scientific products available on the Web site, e.g. reduced resolution browse imagery.)

Fig. 5 - Examples of processed AVHRR images of Tjaktjajaure basin in Northern Sweden used in the EU project HYDALP (Hydrology of Alpine and high latitude basins) involving researchers from UO Sheffield. A & B are geocoded images: channel 1 (red), reflective portion of channel 3 (green) and NDVI (blue); the basin boundary is outlined in magenta. C & D are the corresponding classified images: white - snow, cyan - cloud, green - vegetation and yellow - other. Images were used to generate time series of snow cover maps and hence estimates of snow covered area (SCA). The SCA estimates were used in verification of hydrological models of snowmelt runoff.

The Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service: Annual Report April 1999 - March 2000

1. Service Objectives

The Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service, based at the Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences Plymouth Marine Laboratory, provides value-added remote sensing products mainly derived from data captured and archived by the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station. This ensures that the UK marine science community does not duplicate effort of satellite data processing. Funding is received through a Service Level Agreement with NERC Science Programmes Directorate and a grant from the SeaWiFS Exploitation Initiative Special Topic. Additional funding is earned through commissioned research (CR) from the EU, European scientists, and the private sector.

2. Overview of Service

RSDAS primarily supports the marine science community, with a small number of users in the Earth Sciences and Terrestrial and Freshwater communities. Products comprise sea-surface temperature data from the advanced very high resolution radiometer (AVHRR) and ocean colour data products from the NASA sea-viewing wide field of view sensor (SeaWiFS).

Data processing is undertaken via a number of ways. All data received at Dundee are automatically transferred via FTP to Plymouth and are processed automatically on RSDAS workstations to higher level geophysical or biological products, such as sea-surface temperature or chlorophyll concentration. Produced are re-mapped into standard (e.g. Irish Sea, western English Channel, NE Atlantic – see section 3.2) or user requested regions, annotated and stored on a web-accessible database. This means that many subsequent data requests can be dealt with by images already in the database. Requests for products not in the RSDAS database proceed either by reprocessing locally archived imagery; ordering and processing data archived at Dundee; or for regions outside the Dundee receiving range ordering data from NASA or NOAA (see section 3.1). RSDAS also ensures that pre-processed data from NASA, ESA or NASDA are used where appropriate to maximise the support that can be provided.

A major activity is the near-real time image processing in support of research vessels at sea: images are used to guide the ship to areas of particular interest such as a mesoscale eddy or a phytoplankton bloom (see section 3.1).

3. Highlights and Science in 2000

3.1 SOIREE: *Nature* Paper based on imagery

The SOIREE project was supported through a proposal to RSDAS from Dr A. Watson UEA (in support of a non-thematic grant from UEA and PML) investigating the response of phytoplankton in the Southern Ocean to iron enrichment. The cruise took place in February and March 1999 and proved a success with the iron inducing an artificial bloom. RSDAS provided near-real time support during the cruise; however, images were largely cloud-covered. Data were also obtained subsequent to the cruise imagery and one image, 23 March 1999, 42 days after the initial iron release, showed a remarkable 'bangle' like structure (see figure 1) of high chlorophyll surrounded by the typical low values in the Southern Ocean. The high values have never before been seen in the region and the loop was geographically correlated with the enrichment experiment. This is believed to be the first-ever satellite observation of an induced phytoplankton bloom, and showed that the bloom persisted with high chlorophyll concentration well after the seeding. The results have been written up and submitted to *Nature*, with Sam Lavender of RSDAS as one of the co-authors.

3.2 Eddies in the NE Atlantic: Analysis of 5,000 images

An application was received in November 1999 from Dr Adrian Martin, SOC, to search for eddies in the NE Atlantic using the RSDAS automated front detection method. This work expands upon the eddy studies in the NERC PRIME thematic (Martin et al 1998, *J. Mar. Res.*, **56**, 439-462.) and the $\alpha 5$ rated ACSOE proposal. The request entailed analysis of over 5,200 images: using previous unit costs this request alone would have 'cost' twice the total allocation for RSDAS! Fortunately, the area of interest is covered by a standard RSDAS 'region of interest' and so additional work required extraction of areas from existing images (e.g. fig 2). This shows how the development of automated data analysis enables vast data requests to be realistically supported.

3.3 Near-real time cruise support: TV and Press coverage of a NERC Cruise

Near-real time support during 1999 was at a typical level with six NERC cruises (Discovery - 1, James Clark Ross - 3, Challenger -1, Squilla -1) plus other European cruises supported through RSDAS (2) or commissioned research (6). The R/V Squilla cruise, involving Marine Biological Association, University of York and CCMS staff, sampled a bloom of coccolithophores south of Plymouth. The bloom was exceptionally bright and its visibility from the coast provoked public interest. RSDAS images (e.g. see figure 3) were used by local and national press (Western Morning News & Evening Herald and Daily Mail & The Sunday Times) and local and national TV (BBC Spotlight and BBC National News). The National BBC programme also included footage on the deployment of the NERC aircraft. As a result of these activities ~6 million people have seen RSDAS images through their TV. A NERC News article on the bloom and associated research will appear in the Summer 2000 issue.

4. Future developments

April 2000 marks the renewal of the RSDAS contract for a five-year period covering both AVHRR and SeaWiFS data provision as part of the baseline. These two systems are now mature and it is envisaged that stepwise improvements to processing software will be undertaken in line with UK research and NASA developments. An example of local research will be the implementation of algorithms developed by Gerald Moore and Jim Aiken, CCMS-PML, to extract inherent optical properties from SeaWiFS imagery.

As a result of staff departures, and internal CCMS reorganisation, replacement RSDAS staff are being recruited. To ensure continuity, Dr Peter Miller, who has been involved with RSDAS since its inception will be the new RSDAS manager.

The major new activity in 2000 will be the start of development of a service based on NASA's Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS): the first instrument was launched on 18 December 1999 on-board "Terra" and a second MODIS is planned for launch on "Aqua" later in 2000. The planned RSDAS service was funded through MSTB, SPD and CCMS-PML funds and will rely on data capture through the Dundee Receiving Station X-band reception upgrade.

5. Summary of Performance Information

a) Proposal Supported

RSDAS supports UK scientists who have submitted an application form either to RSDAS or via the Dundee Receiving Station. Applications expected to 'cost' greater than £500 are peer-reviewed by the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Steering Committee: this is currently undertaken once each year which means that in many cases the work is undertaken prior to the review. Applications are also accepted on-line for access to pre-processed imagery available via the RSDAS WWW site. Images can be downloaded by users through a protected web-site linked to database that logs image statistics.

During the year 21 new applications were received. Support was provided to 27 individuals, groups or thematic programmes (see Annex 4.1 for full details) which included applications received and reviewed in previous years; these were graded as follows:

	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	Total
Standard	2	9	10			21
Student		1	2			3
Total	2	11	14			24

b) Distribution of Projects

The applications can be mapped to NERC's Environment and Natural Resource Issues (ENRI's) and NERC Science Areas as follows:

Science Area	Cost £	%
Atmosphere	3049	3%
Earth	4265	5%
Marine	64884	73%
T&F	0	0%
Earth Observation	12724	14%
Science Based Archaeology	0	0%
Polar	4524	5%

ENRI	Cost £	%
Biodiversity	4622	5%
Environmental Risks	8639	10%
Global Change	54605	61%
Natural Resource Mgt	20154	23%
Pollution & Waste	1425	2%
Other	0	0%

c) Publications for Calendar Year 1999

A total of 22 paper publications and 12 conference presentations or posters (see annex 4.3) using RSDAS data or support appeared in 1999. These include nine contributions to peer-reviewed papers or books; three further peer-reviewed papers by RSDAS staff, four PhD theses and MSc dissertations, and six non-peer reviewed paper articles. RSDAS staff co-authored 10 publications. It will be noted that all non-peer reviewed articles and presentations included RSDAS authors: this reflects the virtually non-existent return from the community on publications.

d) Public Understanding of Science

NERC places great emphasis on explaining its role and science to the wider scientific community and general public. RSDAS supported six publications or media "events" during the year.

e) Targets and Milestones

A major task undertaken in 1999, by Peter Miller, was the testing, and correcting where necessary, of approximately 800 programmes for Year 2000 compliance: this ensured that there were no problems with RSDAS software at the start of this year.

The services review in January 1999 graded RSDAS overall as α 4.63 or specifically: Need α 5; Service Quality α 5; Science/Training Quality α 4; and Uniqueness α 4.5. The review group recommended that RSDAS should support data analysis from new satellites (specifically NASA's MODIS) and a grant was prepared and funded by MSTB, SPD and CCMS.

Use is running at 100% of capacity and is essentially limited by the time available to meet commitments within the bounds of the SLA. Work is undertaken in order of α -rating but since most applications comprise a number of individual jobs some work on all applications of all grades can be undertaken.

f) Financial Information. Service Management and Staffing

The 1999/2000 RSDAS Service Level Agreement (SLA) cost allocation was £53.5k plus a capital allocation of £7.7k. The SLA was split as follows: Salaries (incl. National Insurance and superann.) £32.2k, travel and subsistence, consumables & minor capital £8.4k, and overhead on staff £12.9k. The staff complement for 1998/9 supported by this funding comprised:

<u>Staff:</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Percentage allocated</u>
Steve Groom	SEO	25 %
Dr Peter Miller	HEO	33%
Dr Tim Smyth	SO	50%
Mat O'Donnell/ Martin Collins	ASO	50%
Total		1.58 staff-years

The Full Cash Cost was calculated using a new method which included: the contribution from CCMS (the difference in overhead, as a percentage of staff costs, between the Full Economic Cost and the 40% paid by NERC); the Responsive Mode Services group management cost; and a capital rental based on equipment in the facility. This gave FCC of £89.2k (equivalent to £53.5k allocation + £2k RMS management + £25.28k CCMS contribution + £8.4k capital rental).

The SeaWiFS grant provided for approximately £35k which supported Dr Sam Lavender at 100% level together with recurrent and capital expenditure of £9.24k.

**2.4 TERRESTRIAL & FRESHWATER SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY**

NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF) Annual Report for financial Year April 1999-March 2000

This report covers the sixteenth year of Airborne Remote Sensing Facility operations, the period 1 April 1999 to 31 March 2000.

1. Service Objectives

The ARSF exists to provide the UK environmental science community and other potential users with the means to obtain remotely sensed data in support of research and survey programmes. It provides the opportunity for training and promotes good practice in the use of remote sensing data. The facility promotes the awareness, application and technology of remote sensing techniques among the wider scientific community. The application of such data, on a repetitive basis at almost any desired temporal frequency, is an increasingly cost effective means of monitoring the environment – terrestrial, freshwater, marine and atmospheric.

The ARSF is a unique service providing researchers with synoptic digital and analogue imagery of high spatial and spectral resolution. Radiometrically and geometrically corrected digital multispectral data are produced from the Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and the Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (*casi*). A large format aerial survey camera is also deployed.

2. Overview/Highlights

A major R&D focus of the ARSF has been the development of an innovative data processing system over the past five years. The Azimuth Systems AZ16 Integrated Data System (IDS) will provide fully automated processing of data at high spatial resolution.

The IDS is unique in combining a satellite-driven Global Positioning System (GPS) with an aircraft-mounted inertial measurement unit - the Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS). The IDS is capable of accurately monitoring the aircraft's position in three dimensions and determining variations in the aircraft's attitude. This allows imagery to be directly assigned spatial co-ordinates to a high resolution. The IDS is unique in its ability to automatically eliminate distortion in multispectral imagery and deliver to users geometrically rectified products, allowing direct registration to maps/charts, direct comparison of multitemporal surveys, and accurate input of data to GIS systems at potentially sub-metre resolution (sub-metre accuracy is not possible with the current aircraft due to limitations imposed on GPS antennae spacing).

The AZ16 IDS flight hardware was installed in the aircraft in April 1999 and performed exceptionally well, acquiring high-quality data throughout the operational season. During the winter the system was upgraded with a state-of-the-art Javad Positioning System (JPS) which will provide positioning measurements at 20 Hz using GPS and GLONASS satellite constellations. This will improve the accuracy of the geometric correction applied to the level 1a imagery.

Data acquired with the enhanced Daedalus Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) is of particularly good quality. The instrument is now capable of good water penetration and research is now underway to quantify this feature. This capability will greatly enhance coastal and estuarine applications.

In December, the old *casi-502* was exchanged for the latest specification *casi-2* under very favourable terms offered by the manufacturer. The *casi-2* takes advantage of newer technology and is a lighter, more compact and reliable system.

In the course of the year processing of IDS data was implemented. Data collected during the 1999 season will be processed and delivered to users from the end of April 2000, concurrent with 2000 data as it is collected.

Significant progress has been achieved in processing the 1995-97 and 1998 data backlogs. At the end of March, 81% of the 1995/97 backlog and 82% of the 1998 data had been processed and delivered. Although primary staff effort will be devoted to processing 1999 and 2000 data, residual effort will be directed to clearing the remaining data backlog.

The ARSF users were represented by 4 papers at the 4th Int. Airborne Remote Sensing Conference and Exhibition, Ottawa, in June 1999, and with 7 papers at the 25th Annual Conference of the Remote Sensing Society, University of Cardiff.

Despite typical British weather conditions encountered during the 1999 flying season, the crew managed to acquire good quality data for 28 projects. A total of 232 flying hours were flown during the year, with 165 hours on science projects, 10 on commercial applications and 57 on instrument testing, R&D and crew training.

Operations were consolidated at Conington during the year. The maintenance contractor is providing an excellent service and the aircraft is now very reliable, minimising unforeseen maintenance downtime. Considerable efficiency gains have been made with the operation of the service. The flight crew has been reduced from 3 to 2 by taking advantage of new flight management and navigation technology, enabling replacement of the Navigator with a Science/Operations Co-ordinator. In addition to providing the user community with an enhanced liaison capability the Sci/Ops Co-ordinator also acts as a backup Systems Operator, increasing the operational flexibility of the service.

3. Science

The ARSF is primarily a data-acquisition service and, once approval for the project is gained, input is generally restricted to advising users – especially students – as to the optimum combination of instruments, resolution and bandset for the task in hand. At the application stage the Steering Committee provide input and added value to the applications, particularly in the case of invited resubmission (R*). Examples of science project flown in FY 1999/00 are given below:

“High spectral and spatial resolution airborne remote sensing for determination of algal bloom types and velocity-flow fields” α5 (Geography Dept., University of Edinburgh)

This project results from collaboration between the Universities of Edinburgh and Strathclyde with the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency. The aims of the research are two-fold: to field validate model-based approaches to quantifying and identifying algal blooms in coastal regions identified from Monte Carlo modelling and, secondly, to evaluate the utility of airborne remote sensing as a means of determining surface velocity maps in small scale turbid environment such as estuaries in order to parameterise and validate hydrodynamic models. This research could lead to the production of new algorithms applied to data acquired by satellite sensors with improved spectral resolution such as MODIS, OCTS, MERIS and SeaWiFS.

“An investigation of biologically generated habitat provision and coastal erosion at different spatial scale” α4 (School of Biological Sciences, University of Southampton)

The aim of this study is to evaluate the influence of borer organisms, in particular of piddocks, in the ecology of soft rock shores and in the rate of coastal erosion in area of special ecological and natural interest. The research sites are Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty (Bembridge Ledges), or recommended for World Heritage Status (Lyme Regis Cliffs). Multi-temporal airborne remote sensing data will be used to examine broad scale habitat and topography. The overall aims are four fold: to map the habitat distribution and density of piddocks, to obtain information on seasonal changes in the population, to test the hypothesis that habitat provision and increased habitat complexity increases species diversity, and to estimate the rate of bio-erosion caused by the piddocks in comparison to the overall coastal erosion.

"An Improved Method of Soil Type Mapping Using Airborne Remote Sensing" α 4 (Department of Geography, University of Southampton)

The overall aim of this project is to develop a technique for mapping soil types in the UK using airborne remote sensing and to test this for selected soil types in southern and eastern England, under different illumination and cloudiness conditions. The research is innovative in proposing a method to separate the variation due to soil colour from that due to bi-directional effects based upon the geometry of illumination and viewing, rather than through feature space rotation of the data, which is the more conventional approach. The new method takes advantage of the flexibility that airborne sensing offers in terms of the direction of flight lines and the illumination conditions during the overflight and its requirements for cloudy data make it well-suited to operational use in the UK.

4. Future Developments

The provision of a replacement platform for the Piper PA31-350 Navajo Chieftain is progressing well. Following endorsement by the Steering Committee and Director Science Programmes' approval to proceed, the specification for a new aircraft was advertised on the Official Journal of the European Communities. Eight companies expressed an interest and Deutsches Zentrum für Luft-und Raumfahrt (DLR) was identified as the preferred tenderer. The aircraft offered is an extensively modified Dornier 228-101 that will be capable of undertaking extended marine and atmospheric work. This will widen the user base of the facility. Negotiations are now taking place to secure the aircraft by the end of the summer 2000, with the intention of introduction to service in February 2001.

5. Summary of Performance Information

The annual Announcement of Opportunity generated 26 applications, an increase of 30% compared to the previous year, confirming the strong interest of the scientific community in the use of the facility. The applications were peer-reviewed in accordance with the standard NERC practice: 20 α -graded applications were approved for flying and there were 15 carry-over applications from the previous seasons.

The distribution of grades assigned to applications is as follows:

Standard Applications							
α 5	α 4	α 3	α 2	α 1	β	R*	Reject
1	6	8	3	2	0	3	3

The percentage distribution and cost of projects according to science area is as follows:

ESTB		ASTB		MSTB		TFSTB		EOEG		SBASG	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
26.0	211.3	0	0	18.3	148.7	40.7	330.7	7.5	61.0	7.5	61.0

The percentage distribution of science projects and costs according to NERC ENRIs is as follows:

Biodiversity		Env. Risk / Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resource Management		Pollution & Waste	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
32.6	264.9	0	0	0	0	40.0	325.1	27.4	222.7

Publications – Calendar Year 1999

Feedback from the users and a literature search identified a total of 12 refereed publications, 16 non-refereed publications /conference proceedings/newspaper articles and 1 PhD thesis.

The distribution of these publications according to science area is as follows:

Earth Observation	Marine	Terrestrial and Fresh Water	Archaeology	Earth Science	Atmospheric Science
10	4	7	2	6	0

Targets & Milestones

During the period 1 April 1999 to 31 March 2000 the aircraft and crew were on standby for 112 days for a total of 83 operational flying days, accumulating 232 flying hours.

Aircraft /crew utilisation: (Days)

Research HEI/Institute	Commercial	Standby	Standown	Scheduled Maint.	Unscheduled Maint.	Total
78	5	112	41	120	9	365

Allocation of capacity: (nominally 250 hours per year)

Users		Instruments tests & development		Training		Total Hrs Flown/ Utilisation		Under-Utilisation (weather)	
175 hrs	87.5%	30 hrs	12%	27hrs	10.8%	232 hrs	92.8%	18hrs	7.2%

Allocation of flying effort:

Science	Testing/Trials	Training	Commercial
71%	13%	12%	4%

Data acquisition:

ATM	<i>casi</i>	Photography
440 flight lines	408 flight lines	1415 Frames
~ 11 Gbytes	~ 17 Gbytes	

Finance FY 1999/2000

Full cash cost £k	Unit Cost @232hrs pa £k	Recurrent Alloc £k	Capital Expend £k	Revenue £k
812.7	3.51	366.0	42.7	2.7

Service Management/Staff

The ARSF is currently staffed as follows:

Operations Manager	A Kaye	30% Band 5(s)	SPD based Swindon Office
Science/Operations Co-ordinator	F Tadina	100% Band 6(s)	SPD based ARSF Conington
Pilot	C. Joseph	100% Band 6(s)	3-year FTA based ARSF Conington
System Operator	G Osborn	100% Band 6(s)	3-year FTA based ARSF Conington

In the course of the FY, Mr Osborn and Mr. Tadina attended a PRINCE Project Management Course and Capt Joseph underwent a Do228 conversion course. Capt Joseph compiled a Safety Pilot Course and initiated training intended to enable both Mr Osborn and Mr Tadina to control the aircraft should the pilot be incapacitated.

Further Information:

If required, more information can be found in the detailed annexes from which the above items were extracted. These are available from Science Programmes Directorate upon request.

THE NERC AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY'S INTEGRATED DATA SYSTEM

A.K. Wilson & S. Foster

Section for Earth Observation, CEH Monks Wood,
Abbots Ripton, Huntingdon Cambridgeshire, PE20 2LB, UK
email: akw@ceh.ac.uk

Summary

The Section for Earth Observation (SEO), on behalf of the Natural Environment Research Council's Airborne Remote Sensing (ARS) Facility, and in collaboration with UK industry (Azimuth Systems), has developed the Integrated Data System (IDS) to provide world class, spatially referenced, environmental data. The IDS comprises two digital imaging sensors - the Daedalus (268 (11 channel) Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and a state-of-the-art push-broom CCD imaging spectrometer, known as the Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI). Geometric rectification of image data is made possible by the IDS's unique combination of GPS and inertial based navigation systems that allow precise geo-location of every imaged pixel onto a map coordinate system. An additional element of the IDS development has been the major enhancement of the ATM scanner, which now provides data with unprecedented radiometric sensitivity and high signal-to-noise.

Level 10 - Decommissioned ATM ATIS RTG scans in the Monks Wood ARS Facility. The ATIS RTG scans are the most sensitive scans available for the ATM as they are the only scans that have been taken with the ATIS RTG.

Level 8 - The data is processed by the ATM scan processor and is then stored in the ATIS RTG. The data is then processed by the ATM scan processor and is then stored in the ATIS RTG.

Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARS)

Specification	Daedalus (ARS/ATM)	AZ-10 (ATM)
AVI resolution	8 - 14µ	10 - 14µ
Range of UV bands	0 - 105	0 - 105
Channel widths	0.5 - 1.25 - 2.5	None required
Total channel PMV	24.5µ	None
Actual PMV	12.25µ with 0.5µ channel width	None (2.5µ channel width in push-broom mode)
Roll correction (in flight)	±15° from flight path (roll rate of 100°)	None (3-axis correction in post-processing)
Number of pixels/scanline	716	518
Mirror scan rate/second	12.5 / 25 / 50	12.5 / 25 / 50
Body Body (BB) (BB) 1	1 - 1000000000	1 - 1000000000
Data recording	1 - HDDT tape drive	1 - 1000000000
Data visualization	Discipline of digital signal	Waterfall image of selected bands on solar monitor

Table 1 Comparison of Daedalus ARS and the original Daedalus (268) ATIS and AZ-10 (ATM)

The development of the Integrated Data System has enabled the NERC's ARS Facility to provide high quality spatially referenced environmental data for a wide range of applications. The system is currently being used for a wide range of applications, including the monitoring of land use change, the assessment of environmental risk, and the monitoring of natural resources.

NERC Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy

Annual Report of Pool Manager 1999-2000

The Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS) is a unique facility providing researchers with access to high performance field spectroradiometers for measuring the reflectance of objects in their natural surroundings.

Such measurements are essential to underpin quantitative Earth Observation from aircraft and satellite sensors.

Field spectroscopy provides the fundamental link between biophysical measurements made at ground level and the data recorded by remote sensors.

Field spectroradiometers have a crucial role to play in calibrating and verifying data collected by aircraft and satellite sensors.

EPFS plays an important role in training research students in the methods and techniques of field spectroscopy and in the wider area of quantitative remote sensing

reflectance. The project has involved multiple loans of several instruments for field data collection at Barton Bendish in Norfolk, a site was selected by NASA as an *EOS Core Land Validation Site* for the AERONET initiative.

Another $\alpha 5$ graded project (EPFS ref. 308), which was also supported by the ARSF, involved collaboration with the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) to investigate the biological characteristics of algal blooms and the hydrodynamics of the ambient water at a localised site in the Firth of Forth.

The Pool continues to support science across the whole NERC remit. For example, during the year, EPFS instruments have been used to measure the spectral reflectance of sand on Ascension Island in research on the implications of temperature dependent sex determination in green turtles (Hays GR9/585) and to measure the effect of solar angle on glacier albedo (Brock, GR8/4352).

User publications for 1999 also reflect the wide range of scientific topics supported, from methodological research underpinning the latest high spatial resolution satellite sensors (Aplin *et al.*, 1999), to practical applications related to air pollution (Jacovides *et al.*, 1999), and formal scientific experiments, such as that by Jago *et al.*, (1999), to investigate the potential for estimating chlorophyll concentration in plant leaves from measurements of canopy red edge position.

In-house research on the use of a neural network to estimate spectral irradiance has borne fruit in terms of a conference paper reporting very promising results of the technique (Milton *et al.*, 2000), and a prototype instrument which will be tested further during 2000/2001.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Demand for field spectroradiometers covering the full range from VNIR to SWIR wavelengths remains very high, and the two instruments currently in the Pool operate at capacity most of the time, with no back-up available when either is out of service. Demand for these full range instruments exceeds availability for the summer of 2000. An additional instrument covering this region is required to meet this demand and provide the necessary back-up.

Collaboration between the Pool and Dr Graham Ferrier of the University of Hull will result in the acquisition of an underwater housing for the GER 1500 spectroradiometer. This will eventually be made available to EPFS users and will greatly enhance the Pool's potential for supporting marine science. It is anticipated that the housing will be tested and deployed in late 2000.

Preparations are underway to provide support for the NERC-BNSC SAR and Hyperspectral Airborne Campaign (SHAC) in June 2000. During the campaign, Pool spectroradiometers and the sun photometer will be deployed at several UK sites, with the aim of obtaining ground spectral data synchronous with the airborne data. Such data are deemed essential to the scientific objectives of the campaign.

5. SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

During the year April 1999 to March 2000, EPFS supported 26 projects, the majority of which were Terrestrial and Freshwater Science. The remainder was made up of Marine Science, Earth Science, and Polar Science. Over half of all projects were in support of NERC Research Grants, and a further 17% were in support of NERC studentships.

The following measures indicate the level of service provision and equipment utilisation. A full summary of performance indicators is included as Annex 5.

5.1 Numbers and percentage of α -graded loan proposal supported

Table 1. Applications for loans during 1999/2000, by peer review grade and number supported

Applications	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R	Total
Studentship	0	7	5	3	1			16
Other Researcher	2	4	5	5	0		1	16
Total Applications Received	2	11	11	8	1		1	34
Applications Supported	2	8	9	6	1			26
To be supported 2000/01	0	3	2	0	0			5

Of the 34 applications received for loans during 1999/2000, 26 projects were supported during that period, many involving multiple loans. Five remain scheduled for loans during 2000/2001, including one postponed due to the researcher suffering an injury. Two projects (both graded $\alpha 2$) were not supported, in one case because equipment was in use for a more highly graded project and in the second because the instrument scheduled for loan failed and underwent repair at the manufacturers. One application was rejected.

Applications are directed to the Pool Manager in the first instance, which allows opportunity for the additional or revised information to be requested from the applicant before the application is submitted for peer review. This is considered a valuable means of fostering new users, promoting wider use of the facility and expanding the user community, and partly explains why few applications are rejected.

Table 2. Number and cost of projects and percentage distribution according to peer review grade

	$\alpha 5$		$\alpha 4$		$\alpha 3$		$\alpha 2$		$\alpha 1$	
	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%
No. & %	2	8%	8	31%	9	35%	6	23%	1	3%
Cost & %	£49,288	30%	£82,112	50%	£17,431	11%	£14,829	9%	£1,586	1%

5.2 Percentage distribution and costs of projects according to Science areas and NERC ENRI's

Table 3. Number, and cost of projects and percentage distribution according to science areas

	ES		AS		MS		TFS		EO		PSarc	
	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%
No. & %	3	11%	0	0	2	8%	20	77%	0	0	1	4%
Cost & %	£8,440	5%	0	0	£11,346	7%	£141,678	86%	0	0	£3,782	2%

Table 4. Number, and cost of projects and percentage distribution according to NERC ENRI's

	Biodiversity		Environmental Risk & Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resource Management		Pollution & Waste	
	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%	N / £	%
No. & %	0	0	2	8%	3	11%	15	54%	6	23
Cost & %	0	0	£3,704	2%	£20,374	12%	£100,864	61%	£40,304	25%

5.3 Publications for Calendar Year 1999

Annex 6 details publications by EPFS users and staff during the year. Thirty-three (33) user publications are identified from the 1999 calendar year (Annex 6.2). These include 12 journal articles, 3 book chapters, 16 conference papers and 2 theses. EPFS staff had 4 refereed papers published in 1999 and a further journal paper

is in press. EPFS produced 13 internal publications, including 5 software upgrades. Table 5 summarises all these publications according to NERC Science areas.

Table 5. Summary of publications according to science area

	ES	AS	MS	TFS	EO	SBA	PS	Other e.g. software
Users	1	2	1	28	0	0	1	0
EPFS Staff	0	3	0	1	4	0	0	9

5.4 Targets and Milestones

The goals for the EPFS during 1999/00 and progress towards them are summarised in Annex 7. The Pool continued to provide high quality support for users and maintain a high profile in the research community, with the EPFS internet site providing a primary point of contact and communication with potential and existing users. Progress was made in all three EPFS research projects, with publications resulting in each case. The equipment procurement schedule remains incomplete pending the replacement of the GER IRIS MK IV. The performance of the Pool instruments has been good as evidenced in the number of loan days supported and comments received on the instrument report forms.

Table 6. Percentage instrument usage 1999/00

Instrument	ASD FieldSpec FR	GER 3700	GER 1500 (x2)	CIMEL
Capacity (days)	146	237	237	219
Loan days	143	241	600	142
Percentage	98%	102%	127%	65%

5.5 Finance FY 1999/2000

Recurrent Spending

The recurrent cost of the contract in 1999/2000 was £75.6k, compared with a budgeted figure of £80.5k. In addition to this amount, £9,464 was made available by NERC for essential repairs and upgrade to the ASD field spectroradiometer.

Capital Expenditure

No funds were allocated for the purchase of capital items in 1999/00 but following an equipment failure the ASD FieldSpec FR was repaired and upgraded to a FieldSpec Pro. The FieldSpec Pro offers improved portability, speed and usability advantages over the old system.

Full Cash Cost (FCC) Allocation of EPFS Instrument Support

The total Full Cash Cost allocation of EPFS instrument support is summarised in Table 7. This total cost allocation compares with an estimated FCC for the Pool of £144,300 for 1999/00. The FCC figure is provided by NSS, and the significantly higher FCC for this year compared with that estimated for 1998/99 is due to a change in the method of calculation.

Table 7. Full Cash Cost allocation of EPFS instrument support 1999/2000

HEI	Centres/Surveys	Total
162,440	2,806	165,246

Income Generation

The Pool provided instrument loans and technical support to Itres Research (Canada), The Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Belgium), DERA and the University of Reading. These loans generated £1,420

income. Other income was received from NERC Scientific Services for two CASI calibrations (£1,970 each) and one ATM bench calibration (£580).

5.5 Service Management and Staffing

Following the recommendations of the 1998 SRG review, staffing was reduced from 2 to 1.5 FTE. David Emery, the Pool Manager, was employed as a full time PGRA, and was assisted by three part-time researchers: Dr Liz Rollin (PDRF, 0.2 FTE), Valeria Salvatori (PGRA, 0.2 FTE for 8 months) and Dominic Lawrance (PGRA, full-time for 2 months). Miss Salvatori left the Pool to undertake a PhD at the University of Southampton and Mr Lawrance to undertake an MSc in Geophysics at the University of Birmingham.

NERC ^{15}N Stable Isotope Facility

Centre for Ecology & Hydrology

CEH Merlewood
GRANGE OVER SANDS
Cumbria LA11 6JU

ANNUAL REPORT (April 1999 to March 2000)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

1. Overview and highlights:

This is the Annual Report of the activities of the ^{15}N Stable Isotope Facility in support of proposals funded at least in part by NERC for the period 1st April 1999 to 31st March 2000. The primary remit of the Facility is to provide stable isotope analysis of ^{15}N and ^{13}C for research workers in the terrestrial and freshwater life sciences in NERC institutes, or in university departments receiving NERC funding. The Facility undertakes research and development, covering all aspects of ^{15}N and ^{13}C analysis technology and applications, which is of direct benefit to, or to meet the future needs of terrestrial and freshwater life sciences research. The ^{15}N SIF aims to promote the awareness, application and technology of ^{15}N and ^{13}C analysis techniques and to disseminate to the wider scientific community, in addition to provide training and promote good practice in the use of ^{15}N and ^{13}C analysis techniques.

May 4th 1999 saw the arrival of the new Facility manager to replace Mr. Chris Quarmby who had been in charge of the ^{15}N SIF since 1985. As regards the daily operation of the Facility it has been a highly successful year in terms of its functional organisation, equipment, staffing, visitors and subsequent sample throughput. New management protocols have been instigated, specifically aimed at improving the: (i) archiving of user and laboratory documentation, (ii) sample organisation, (iii) efficient operating practices and (iv) staff training. In the laboratory, the other bulk IRMS has been upgraded to perform ^{13}C isotope measurements. This instrument runs routinely for ^{15}N and ^{13}C stable isotope analyses and has added an extra back-up resource for the ageing ANCA Roboprep bulk analyser. It is pleasing to report that the combined effects of running these two bulk instruments has not only increased sample throughput in the Facility but also cleared the two month sample back-log that existed very early in the financial year. Modifications have also been made to the combustion reactor and furnace temperature on the

Tracegas Preconcentrator to enable routine CH₄ isotopic measurements. After its initial installation in 1997, the Micromass UK/Agilent Technologies GC-C-IRMS system has had the first phases of R & D performed on it during the latter stages of this reporting period. Initial work has concentrated on ¹³C analyses. Early signs look promising, although further R & D work needs to be performed before ¹⁵N SIF is willing to offer compound specific carbon analyses to the TFS user community. Strong links have been formed between ¹⁵N SIF and Micromass UK as a result of promotion and publicity events organised by the Head of Facility. ¹⁵N SIF placed a bid for a state-of-the-art benchtop quadrupole mass spectrometer to enable compound identification prior to GC-C-IRMS analysis. The bid was successful in securing 25K from NERC SPG.

Eight visiting post-doctoral staff and have made use of the Facility during the reporting year and whose projects have covered a broad range of isotopic applications e.g. CO₂, CH₄, bulk ¹³C and ¹⁵N. ¹⁵N SIF has been involved in a number of self promotional exercises during the past year. Facility web-pages have been updated and have been also added to the Soil Biodiversity Thematic Program website. An Isotope Masterclass (The Application of Isotopic Techniques in Soil Ecology) was organised June 30th – July 2nd. The annual meeting of the Stable Isotope Mass Spectrometry Users Group (SIMSUG2000) was organised by CEH-Merlewood (18th-19th January, 2000) with large organisational involvement by ¹⁵N SIF staff.

Mr. Sleep successfully completed an intensive four day gas chromatography training course organised by Agilent technologies in November 1999. SIF have recently appointed a new member of staff to handle work generated by the GANE and Soil Biodiversity NERC thematic programs, funded by Soil Biodiversity (25%), GANE (25%) and TFS/NERC (50%).

2. Scientific highlights:

Three examples of NERC science projects awarded high alpha grades are given below from the period 1999/2000:

1). The aim was to investigate the importance of mycorrhizas (an association formed between a fungus and a root whereby the plant receives nutrients especially P, and the fungus receives carbon from the plant) on soil respiration rate. The fungal mycelium is often very extensive in virtually all soils. Four sets of perspex tubes, covered with 35 micron mesh and containing plant-free soil were sunk into the Sourhope experimental plots. The mesh prevented root in-growth but allowed mycorrhizal mycelium to penetrate and colonise the soil with the core. Half of the cores were rotated regularly to snap the hyphae so half the cores were free of mycorrhizal mycelium. Half of the two treatments were pulse labelled with enriched CO₂ and the 1st harvest cores removed and incubated at soil temp from which headspace gas samples were analysed. Trace gas stable isotope analyses CO₂ were conducted in ¹⁵N SIF. The exciting results produced from this project indicated that carbon moved very quickly along the atmosphere, plant, root, mycorrhizal, soil, atmosphere pathway and indicated that mycorrhizas are likely to be extremely important in rapid cycling of carbon even in ecosystems that are considered fairly deficient in mycorrhizal responsiveness (i.e. Sourhope. cf. calcareous grasslands). The results were all the more exciting as this was done in the field with the minimum of disturbance to the soil system. Virtually all studies investigating carbon dynamics in grasslands in relation to mycorrhizas have used simplified pot systems often with sand (approved project α4).

Fig. 1. Time after pulse label (key: diamonds: non-rotated; squares: rotated; triangles: control)

2). This multidisciplinary thematic research project developed the first in situ $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ pulse experiments at the designated experimental site at Sourhope, to determine the fate and turnover of plant derived carbon in a number of soil/plant organic matter pools and soil/plant respired CO_2 . Using a mobile stable isotope delivery laboratory, pulse labelling with 50 atm% $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ was directed into twelve pulse-chambers at rate of 2-5 litres minute⁻¹. Macrofauna, soil, plant and air samples were sampled four times over a period of six weeks after the initial pulse. The research aims to incorporate usage of both bulk, trace gas and eventually compound specific stable isotope measurements in ^{15}N SIF. Collaborative research teams at Sheffield University (see above), Stirling University and Macaulay Land Use Research Institute are now working in parallel on different aspects of this project (approved project $\alpha 4$).

3. A detailed study on mycelial systems of cord-forming fungi, to specifically relating to understanding how balances between metabolic demand and the need for nutrient conservation determines nutrient translocation (rates, route, direction). The research should provide essential information on the functioning of a fungal group that is extremely important for decomposition and nutrient cycling in forest ecosystems (approved project $\alpha 3$).

3. Future developments:

The commissioning of a bench-top GC/MS instrument to be used in conjunction with the GC-C-IRMS technique. The introduction of compound-specific $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ analyses to the isotope community as a viable service option. Initiate R & D on GC-C-IRMS to incorporate compound specific ^{15}N analyses Initiate R & D on the trace gas analyser to incorporate N_2O analyses (^{15}N and possibly ^{18}O : thus maintaining strong links with Dr. Susan Waldron at SUERC). Complete SIF refurbishment and laboratory modifications (including new office for Thematic programme SO, new sample storage areas for enriched/natural abundance samples, tender additional ultra-precision micro-balance and autosampler for trace gas-module).

4. Summary of performance information:

(i) Summary of NERC thematic versus non-thematic projects supported (NILSSC α gradings). The R* (sufficient of merit to qualify for resubmission with advice of the SC) was re-graded $\alpha 4$ and is included in the thematic totals

Committee grading	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*	R
Thematic	0	4	1	0	0	0	1	0
Non-thematic	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	7	3	0	0	0	1	0

(ii) Summary of α -gradings versus NERC ENRI's (99/00)

ENRI								
Biodiversity	0	3	0	0	0	0	1	0
Nat. Res. M.	0	4	3	0	0	0	0	0

(iii) Percentage distribution and cost allocation according to NERC ENRI's 99/00

ENRI	Nat. Res. Man.	Biodiversity	P & W	Global Change	ER & H
% distribution	85.7 %	14.3 %	0	0	0
£K	89.5K	14.9k	0	0	0

(iv) Peer reviewed paper published 99/00:

Feedback and literature checks identified a total of 11 refereed publications/conference abstracts and 8 non-refereed publications/conference abstracts for the Facility. The identified publications fall into the following Science and Technology Board/Expert Group categories:

STB/EG	Earth STB	Atmosph. STB	Marine STB	Terrestrial & Freshwater STB	Earth Observation EG	Science-based Archaeology EG
No. of publications	3	0	0	15	0	1

(v) *Targets and Milestones:*

Total sample turnover in 1999/2000 compared with 97/98 and 98/99

	¹⁵ N enriched	¹⁵ N natural abundance	¹³ C enriched/natural abundance	Alternative methods	Grinding under liquid nitrogen
97/98	1425	1194	1054	0	1661
98/99	1373	2201	1435	106	593
99/00	2823	1353	2648	44	1112

Stable isotopic analyses fluctuate drastically from year to year depending upon the projects undertaken. This year has shown that requests for ¹⁵N enriched samples and ¹³C (natural abundance/enriched) have doubled since 1998/99, requests for ¹⁵N natural abundance samples has reduced by 38%. Grinding under liquid nitrogen has doubled. Only 44 alternative preparation procedures (e.g. distillations) have been requested this year.

(vi) *Finance 99/00*

The SLA states that the core staff compliment is two and SPG and CEH will share direct costs of the salaries, employers NI contribution and recurrent costs equally. A third post is entirely supported by SPG with a cash contribution from TFSTB carrying a 46% overhead.

Approved/estimated 99/00:

Core staff	Recurrent allocation 99/00	Commissioned staff + 46% overhead*	Additional recurrent*	Capital	Unit cost @ 426 units pa
£41.08 K	£17 K	5.84 K	3 K	26.3 K	£222.53

* estimated

Actual SPG allocation 99/00	Notional overheads @ 46%	Capital spend	RMS full cash cost
£45.6 K	£20.98 K	£26.3K	£94.8 K

(vi) *Planned capital expenditure*

£9 K has been allocated from SPG to purchase a second Sartorius ultra-precision micro-balance M2P model and a Gilson auto-sampler unit for the Micromass Tracegas Pre-concentrator.

(vii) *Service management during 99/00:*

The NERC ¹⁵N Stable Isotope Facility is currently staffed as follows:

Facility Manager	SSO
Scientific Officer Isotope analyst	SO
Scientific Officer Isotope analyst	SO (3 year contract NERC Thematic Programs)

(viii) *Further information:*

If required, further information can be found in the detailed annexes from which the above information was extracted. These are available from Services and Facilities on request.

ANNUAL REPORT
for the
NERC EARTH OBSERVATION DATA CENTRE (NEODC)
FINANCIAL YEAR 1999/2000 (APRIL – MARCH)

1. Service Objectives

NERC has acquired and retained during the preceding 30 years a vast quantity of remotely sensed data of the surface of the Earth obtained by satellites and aircraft. This valuable resource - estimated present value in excess of £4M – provides a unique record of environmental conditions and comprises digital data which in most cases have been rigorously calibrated and geo-corrected. Environmental scientists are therefore able to use such data with confidence in support of research and survey in the environmental sciences including long-term environmental monitoring.

The Mission of the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre is therefore to ensure the responsible stewardship and distribution of this data, to give guidance on the availability and use of its and other Earth observation (EO) data, and to routinely acquire additions to the data holding in an efficient and cost-effective manner in response to requests from accredited customers. The NEODC also monitors the stewardship accorded to other Earth observation data acquired by NERC so that such data are managed as a valuable resource for present and future environmental science. The NEODC also acts as a source of information regarding EO data generally and provides advice and guidance on matters of copyright, policy and strategy with regard to all NERC EO data resources.

2. Overview and Highlights

In order to achieve its mission the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre :-

1. maintains a central archive and catalogue of NERC commercial satellite data and NERC airborne remotely sensed data - accessible through the NEODC website: www.neodc.rl.ac.uk
2. provides access to this data for NERC Centres and Surveys, the UK HEI community, NERC Thematic Programmes and NERC-funded academics and other groups in accordance with the terms of the NERC Data Policy
3. co-ordinates and supervises the archiving and dissemination of all digital data and ancillary information relating to the annual flying campaigns of the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility
4. provides advice on availability and copyright regulations pertaining to commercial satellite data
5. acts as a contact and liaison point for communications on other national and international archiving/cataloguing initiatives relating to EO data
6. provides policy and strategy input to NERC corporate data policy through membership of the NERC Data Strategy Group.

The Highlights of the year have been:-

- the acquisition of new data - and/or distribution of archive data - for a series of NERC Studentships and Research Grants and in support of several NERC Thematic Programmes
- the completion of the SEEDCORN project
- the recent appointment of a Project Scientist to further enhance the effectiveness of the NEODC service to the NERC and UK environmental research and survey community
- and the incorporation of Antarctic EO satellite imagery from the British Antarctic Survey into the NEODC archive.

3. Science

Remotely-sensed digital and analogue imagery of the surface of the Earth – terrestrial and aquatic – are used extensively in support of research and survey across the full spectrum of NERC's environmental sciences and make a major contribution to all five of the NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues (ENRIs).

The NEODC provides services to many UK HEI departments carrying out research into the natural environment and these include:- Geology, Geography, Biological Sciences, Earth Sciences, Soil Science, Ice and Climate, Archaeology, Planning and Landscape, Environmental Sciences, Remote Sensing, Marine Science and Coastal Management, Oceanography, Civil Engineering, Zoology, Hydrogeology, Epidemiology and Public Health, Land Use, Glaciology, Built Environment and Engineering Geology.

Likewise, within the NERC Centres and Surveys there is wide application of Earth observation data and recent users of the NEODC services include most of the component laboratories and units.

New and archive satellite and airborne data was delivered to 17 NERC award holders – five of these were research grant projects and ten comprised PhD studentships and two involved MSc projects. The titles of most of these • -grade projects are listed below and demonstrate the breadth of NERC science for which NEODC data services provided a valuable input:

“Tectonics and Topography: Application of High Resolution Digital Elevation Data Derived Using SAR Interferometry”

“Communication and the Mating System of Badgers”

“Remote Sensing of Ocean Currents in the South China Sea”

“Mapping Abandoned Shorelines of Tibetan Lakes to Measure Holocene Distortion of the Surface”

“Monitoring Forest Cover and Wetland Sedimentation in Cat Tien National Park, Viet Nam”
(see Figure 1 below)

“Crustal Deformation in Greece and Turkey from SAR Interferometry”

“Effects of Wildfires on Vertebrate Community Structure and Forest Dynamics in Amazonia”

“Evolution of Tolerance: Influence on the Ability of Remote Sensing to Detect Vegetation Stress”

“The Ecology and Genetics of Mauritian Skinks Earmarked for Use in Habitat Reconstruction”

“Experimental and Field Studies of Fan Delta Architecture: Fault Episodicity Versus Sea Level Controls”

“Estimation of Land Surface Biophysical Properties from Satellite Sensor Measurements of Directional Reflectance” (see Figure 2 below)

“Predicting Mosquito Populations from Soil Physical Properties and Landscape Position in East Africa”

“Evaluation of Satellite Imagery in the Archaeological Assessment of Arid Zone Environments”.

Fig 1: False-colour Landsat 7 TM image of Central Viet Nam

Fig 2: True-colour Landsat 7 TM image of SE England

NERC Thematic Programmes which are known to have made use of the services of the NEODC Facility are:-

- Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS)
- Plankton Reactivity in the Marine Environment (PRIME)
- Urban Regeneration and the Environment (URGENT).

4. Future Developments

The NEODC SEEDCORN project finished at the end of 1999 and the vast majority of its objectives were achieved within the funding provided and a final report was submitted to the NERC Project Manager. The remaining tasks, which are mainly concerned with the incorporation of post-1993 airborne data onto the archive and standardising data and metadata formats for the pre-1993 airborne data, will be carried out during 2000 and 2001.

Further targets and deliverables which are defined for 2000/01 are:-

- Incorporation into the NEODC archive of outstanding EO datasets presently existing at many of the NERC Centres and Surveys sites and appropriate metadata cataloguing of such imagery
- Development of a user registration and accreditation mechanism for the NEODC website
- Establishment of a direct link to the NERC Metadata Gateway
- Promotion of the NEODC through improved Website information content and the development of direct links to other UK and international gateways for EO information and datasets
- Ongoing storage of the existing secondary DSRs AVHRR security archive at RAL
- Storage of radar and hyperspectral data from the BNSC/NERC 2000 (SHAC) Airborne Campaign.

5. Summary of Performance Information

Throughout the year the Data Centre has continued to provide a cost-effective and efficient service for the search, purchase, archiving and distribution of commercial satellite data on behalf of the NERC-funded community. An equivalent search and distribution service has also been provided for airborne data products for all academic and commercial customers.

Many associated enquiries relating to Earth observation data resources and copyright regulations have been received at the Data Centre and these have been dealt with on a secondary basis with appropriate advice and information provided.

The NEODC also participated in the activities of the NERC Data Strategy Group, including input to revisions to the NERC Data Policy Handbook and data management guidelines.

The NERC Earth Observation Data Centre is a member of, or attends, the following Committees:- NERC Data Strategy Group (NDSG), NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee (ARSFSC), and NERC Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Steering Committee (DSRSSC). The Membership and Terms of Reference for the NDSG, ARSFSC and DSRSSC are appended as Annex 3.

NERC α -grade Projects Supported:

Research Grant: 5 PhD Studentship: 10 MSc Studentship: 2

NERC Science Areas (All Customers):

	AS	EO	ES	MS	SBA	TFS	Polar
Percentage %	2	20	15	12	5	45	1
Cost £k	1.9	19.3	14.4	11.6	4.8	43.3	1.0

NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues (All Customers):

	Biod	Env R	Glob	Nat RM	P&W
Percentage %	15	20	6	49	10
Cost £k	14.4	19.3	5.8	47.2	9.6

Targets and Milestones:

There were several perceived risks to the pre-1998 NEODC archive facility which could have significantly reduced or totally negated its existing value to the environmental community. The greatest of these threats to the integrity of the archive was the increasing age and obsolescence of the data tape media and the associated read/write devices which permitted access thereto. A case was therefore submitted in 1997 to the NERC SEEDCORN initiative for funding to enable the transfer of the archive onto more up-to-date and reliable media using state-of-the-art technology with a back-up copy for increased security. At the same time a metadata catalogue and data access server would be established to include a browser providing quick-look thumbnail imagery for area coverage and data quality assessment. This catalogue and quick-look imagery would be provided on a new NEODC website.

The bid to the SEEDCORN initiative was considered worthy of support and in excess of £100k was awarded to the NEODC for this 21-month project which commenced 1 April 1998.

The transfer of digital imagery from the iTSS manual tape store at Keyworth to the robotic tapestore at RAL is now complete and a server mechanism has been established for rapid access to the NEODC archive. Furthermore a Website has now been created for the NEODC and a search mechanism for both satellite and airborne data has been incorporated together with a complete series of thumbnail imagery which allows customer assessment of area coverage, cloud cover and data quality. Most data transfers to customers from the NEODC archive are now executed by means of ftp.

A summary tabulation of customer enquiries received by the NEODC is provide in Annex 2 to this report - the majority of these communications requested archival searches and/or delivery of Earth observation data - either satellite or airborne.

- 39 searches of external image archives were undertaken with, in most cases, the results being returned to customers within one working week, and all within two working weeks.
- 23 requests for data from the NEODC image archive were processed and the majority despatched within 10 working days of the initial request.
- 11 new sets of commercial satellite data imagery – incorporating 57 image scenes – were purchased (total cost: £16,114) in response to requests from NERC staff or NERC-funded academics. This imagery comprised Landsat 4, 5&7 TM and ERS-1&2 SAR digital data.

Following confirmation of image specifications and data pricing, the supplier delivery time rarely exceeded 15 working days, except where data were sourced from non-European ground stations.

No significant data quality problems were recorded during the year.

No other formal or informal complaints regarding the quality and delivery of the NEODC services during 1999/2000 have been received.

Finance:

The cash Budget allocated to the NEODC for 1999/2000 was £118.4k

The cash spend by the NEODC for 1999/2000 was £94.6k – the £23.8k underspend resulted mainly from the late appointment of the new staff member who was completing his PhD.

The Full Cash Cost(FCC) – including notional NERC overheads and capital rental – for the NEODC for 1999/2000 was £120.1k. This FCC minus the annual underspend - £96.3k - has been used to derive the Customer Cost Allocations in Annex 2 and the Cost Allocations provided in Section 5 above for the NERC Science Areas and ENRIs.

Service Management and Staffing:

The Facility staff and levels of commitment in support of the NEODC in 1999/2000 were:-

Project Manager: Dr S J White	0.50 manyears
Project Scientist: Mr M J Pritchard	0.25 manyears.

6. Further Information:

Annex 1: NEODC Mission Statement

Annex 2: NEODC Customer Cost Allocations - 1999/2000

Annex 3: Terms of Reference and Membership of NERC DSG, ARSFSC and DSRSSC

Annex 4: NEODC Inventory

Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility at the University of Bristol

Annual Report 1999-2000: Executive Summary

1. SERVICE OBJECTIVES

The Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility (OMSF) provides a service for the NERC community requiring mass spectrometric and stable isotope analyses of organic compounds in biological and environmental materials. The Service offers expertise and instrumental capabilities for complex mixture analyses through combined (gas or high performance liquid chromatography, i.e. GC and HPLC) linked to organic or light stable isotope mass spectrometry (GC only at present). Information that is provided includes compound structures via mass spectra, 'fingerprint' distributions via GC/MS or HPLC/MS, and compound-specific stable isotope (C, N, H and O) compositions. The facility is probably the most experienced laboratory anywhere in the world in the application of compound-specific stable isotope analysis techniques to environmental science. The support is both service and collaborative in nature. Outside users submit applications to use specialist instrumentation, techniques and/or expertise not available in their own institutions. Access for researchers is through application to the Steering Committee (OMSFSC). Only applications receiving an $\alpha 3$ grade or better are supported. All outside researchers working on supported projects are encouraged to visit the Bristol laboratory and become fully involved in the analyses of their samples and processing of data, thereby maximising the training aspect of the service.

2. OVERVIEW AND HIGHLIGHTS

2.1 Renewal - In December 1999 OMSF submitted a formal application for renewal by the NERC Services Review Group (SRG). The review was competitive against existing Services and new bids. Following the SRG review, and final approval by the NERC Science and Technology Boards in February 2000, OMSF scored as follows (1 lowest, to 5 highest).

Need	Uniqueness	Service Quality	Science/Training Quality	Overall Rating
5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0

This resulted in a successful bid with funding being granted until 31st March 2004.

2.2 Use of the Service - During the year April 1999 to 2000 OMSF has given support to, and been involved in the development of, ten projects with UK Universities and Institutions (Table 1). Both PhD students and postdoctoral researchers have received training and hands-on experience in the use of the five mass spectrometers and 'wet' chemical preparation laboratories that comprise the Service and in the interpretation of data obtained. The laboratory has received two overseas visitors for extended periods of training in molecular techniques in the fields of organic geochemistry (Dr S. Xie, PDRA, China University of Geosciences, 1 year) and chemical archaeology (Miss N. Weber, PhD student, Harvard, USA, 6 months). In-house use of the facilities (outwith the NERC allocation) includes the work of 6 PDRAs, 1 postgraduate research assistant, 24 postgraduate students and 3 technicians, on a diverse range of research projects encompassing biogeochemistry, organic geochemistry, chemical archaeology, palaeoclimate reconstruction and biomolecular palaeontology, many of which are collaborative in nature between different departments within the University of Bristol (notably the Departments of Earth Sciences and Archaeology and School of Geographical Sciences), other UK Universities (Oxford, Cambridge, UCL, York, Stirling and CGCHE) and research institutes (CEH, BAS, IGER and IARC-Rothamsted).

2.3 New instrumentation - A notable extension to the range of analytical capabilities offered by the Service to outside users is the second GC-IRMS instrument, the Finnigan Delta^{PLUSXL}. This instrument was purchased through funds granted by JREI and makes the Bristol laboratory unique in the UK for compound-specific stable isotope research, with capabilities for determining $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, δD and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values for individual compounds. The ability to perform compound-specific stable isotope analyses

constitutes one of the major developments in the field of combined chromatography/mass spectrometry in the past decade and is envisaged become the major part of the work of the Service the coming years.

3. SCIENCE

3.1 Detection and classification of atmospheric methane oxidizing bacteria in soil

This research performed in collaboration with colleagues at the then Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (now Centre for Hydrology and Ecology, Merlewood) was important since the bacteria present in well-drained non-agricultural soils are known to mediate the oxidation of methane directly from the atmosphere, contributing 5-10% of the global methane sink. The aim of this project was to utilise compound-specific stable isotope techniques to identify the major classes of high and low affinity methanotrophic bacteria responsible for methane oxidation in soil. Significantly, such organisms are notoriously difficult to culture in the laboratory; hence, a preferred approach would be to use *in situ* methods of labelling microbial populations using isotopically labelled methane. A carbon-14 based approach had been described in the literature but lacked specificity and, because the method was based on a radionuclide, could never be transferred to a field setting. The approach in this study was to employ short-term incubations of forest soils with $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ methane; thus, based on the "you are what you eat" principle, any methanotrophic organisms would become labelled with ^{13}C derived from the methane they had consumed.

Figure 1. A plot of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of PLFAs from soil after incubation and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ pulse-labelling. Pulse labelling was done under elevated methane (100 p.p.m.v., white squares), atmospheric methane (1.8-3.6 p.p.m.v., black triangles and control (non-enriched and unlabelled soil, black circles). Missing data points correspond to components for which reliable values could not be obtained. Numbers on the x-axis correspond to the PLFAs as follows: 3, 14:0; 5, 15:0; 6, 15:0; 10, 16:0; 11, 6:1 11; 12, 16:1 ω 8c; 13, 6:1 ω 7c; 14, br17:0; 5, 16:1 ω 5t; 16, br17:0; 17, 17:0; 19, br17:1; 20, br18:0; 21, 17:0; 23, br18:0; 24, 18:0; 26, 18:1 ω 9c; 27, 18:1 ω 7c; 28, 18:1 ω 5c.

Phospholipid fatty acids were extracted from the soil incubated with $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ (with appropriate controls), structurally characterised by GC/MS and, most importantly, their $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were determined by GC-IRMS. As can be seen from Figure 1 certain fatty acids were enriched in ^{13}C , confirming unambiguously, that they derived from methanotrophic bacteria. The results obtained confirmed the presence of both high and low affinity methanotrophs. The high proportions of ^{13}C -labelled C_{18} fatty acids and the co-occurrence of a labelled, branched C_{17} fatty acid, indicated that a new methanotroph, similar at the PLFA level to known type II methanotrophs, was the dominant soil micro-organism responsible for atmospheric methane oxidation. These results were published in *Nature* [Bull et al., 405, 175-178 (2000)]. The approach used demonstrates the power of compound-specific stable isotopes techniques in studying biogeochemical and ecological processes. Moreover, the study emphasises the importance of the complementary use of organic mass spectrometry, in providing the detailed structure analyses of fatty acids, in combination with compound-specific stable isotope measurements by GC-IRMS, both of which are essential in establishing chemotaxonomic associations.

3.2 Palaeoclimate records in compound-specific δD values of a lipid biomarker in ombrotrophic peat -

This research represents the Service's first results of research involving compound-specific δD measurements of individual lipids on the newly-installed Finnigan Delta^{PLUSXL} GC-IRMS. The research was a collaborative venture involving a visiting postdoctoral researcher from China (Dr Xie), two of our own PhD students (Chris Nott and Luke Avsejs) and collaborators from CGCHE (Professor Frank Chambers) and the University of Newcastle (Dr Darrel Maddy). Previous work on the macrofossil record in Bolton Fell Moss demonstrated this bog to be climatically sensitive and, while this and other raised

bogs typically provide records for the latter part of the Holocene, a coherent record is frequently lacking from blanket bogs owing to humification resulting in loss of identifiable macrofossils. One of the goals is to develop biomarker techniques to allow vegetation records for highly humified peats to be reconstructed.

Preliminary work focused on sections of the peat for which macrofossil records can be correlated with biomarkers characteristic of living bog plants, most specifically on the peat immediately beneath the modern-day surface (0-40 cm) since detailed meteorological records exist for this most recent period providing the basis for validating new climate proxies. A previous investigation of the *n*-alkane distributions derived from the peat revealed clear variations in the relative abundance of the *n*-C₂₃ and *n*-C₃₁ down core, corresponding to vegetation changes at the bog surface through time (Figure 2a and b).

Figure 2. Profiles showing temporal variations of the biomarker abundance and compound specific isotope values (black squares) correlating with temperature, rainfall and the macrofossil record [continuous lines; macrofossil record is for 1 cm contiguous samples while the mean temperature is based on the growing season for *Sphagnum* (May to September) in England calculated as a 30-year running average (Manley, 1974; Parker et al., 1992) and the yearly Carlisle rainfall record (Jones P.D., 1983; National Meteorological Library, Bracknell)]: (a) *Sphagnum* macrofossil distribution (% of the total peat plants); (b) variation in the ratio *on*-C₂₃/*n*-C₃₁ with depth; (c) and (d) show variations in δD values of the C₂₃ *n*-alkane (‰), with temperature and rainfall, respectively.

In this part of the investigation the aim was to assess whether or not more detailed climatic information could be obtained through stable isotope measurements, anticipating that compound-specific stable isotope methods would provide enhanced specificity and sensitivity compared with bulk techniques. The *n*-C₂₃ component was selected since it was found to be present in all the modern *Sphagnum* spp. Compound-specific δD values, recorded by means of the new GC-thermal conversion-IRMS (GC-TC-IRMS) technique, of the biomarker *n*-alkane (*n*-tricosane; *n*-C₂₃) correlate with vegetation changes in the past >200 years (Figure 2; age depth model based on ²¹⁰Pb dating). The bog vegetation is sensitive to climate change, correlating ($r = 0.77$) with the global scale cooler period of the later 19th and early 20th centuries. These findings represent the first example of the use of compound-specific δD values of lipid biomarkers as a climate proxy. The results are in press in *Organic Geochemistry*.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

One of the goals for the forthcoming year will be to bring compound-specific determinations of ¹⁵N on stream using the new Finnigan Delta^{PLUSXL} GC-IRMS. Demand for this capability is increasing, and no facility exists within the UK for performing such analyses. Preliminary work has shown that acceptable values can be obtained for standard compounds but further work is required to develop the technique to such a stage that routine determinations can be performed on N-containing compounds such as amino acids, amino sugars and chlorophylls (as maleimides). Further development work will also be undertaken in extending the application of compound-specific δD techniques to compound classes other than *n*-alkanes. In response to demand both from outside and in-house users a thermal desorption inlet will be fitted to the Finnigan Delta S GC-IRMS which will enable stable isotope measurements to be performed on volatile compounds trapped from head-spaces above environmental or biological materials (e.g. volatile organic compounds emitted from soils or plants).

In accordance with our medium to long-term capital plan, a collaborative JIF application led by Professor Evershed, between the School of Chemistry, Department of Earth Sciences and School of Geographical Sciences, has been made to NERC to establish an interdisciplinary 'Molecular and Stable Isotope

Biogeochemistry Research Centre for the 21st Century. The bid incorporates proposals for major laboratory infrastructure refurbishments (including the laboratories that house OMSF) and new instrumentation, thereby maintaining a world class centre for environmental research based on molecular and stable isotope approaches, with a greatly increased range of analytical capabilities that would be offered by the Service to the UK community.

5. SUMMARY OF PERFORMANCE INFORMATION

5.1 Applications supported - The proportion of the Service's total capacity assigned to outside users for the period April 1999 to March 2000 was 9.5%. **The mean grade assigned to applications was α 3.9, reflecting the high quality of science undertaken by the Service.** This capacity is costed (and allocated) on an 'hourly' basis rather than 'per sample' to account of the markedly different lengths of times required to perform 'direct inlet' (= 0.5 hr probes and loop injections; 0.25 hr for bulk stable isotope analyses) and 'combined chromatography/mass spectrometry' (= 1.5 hr; GC/MS, GC-IRMS and HPLC/MS) analyses and the additional time required to carry out 'wet chemical' sample preparations and post-run data processing. **Based on the agreed allocation of 370 hours (= analytical units) assigned, the 704.5 hours of 'Analytical Support' work performed for outside users constitutes 190 % of the agreed target.** No allowance has been made for downtime in the calculation of time allocated to outside users. **The total funding from NERC for the period was £49,308.**

Table 1. OMSF service support to outside users for the period 1st April 1999 to 31st March 2000.

Projects	Institution	Department	PI	Grade	Status	ENRI ¹	Total time (hrs)
Insect wing cuticles	University of Exeter	Dept. of Biol. Sciences	Dr R.T. Wootton	α 4	Service	NR	18
Sea surface temperature reconstruction	University of Durham	Dept. of Geography	Dr A. Rosell-Mele	α 4	Service	GC	256
Variation in pCO ₂ in last 60,000 years	University of Durham	Dept. of Geography	Dr A. Rosell-Mele	α 4	Service	GC	65.5
Composition of coal liquids	UCL	Dept. of Chem. Eng.	Dr A.A. Herod	α 3.5	Service	NR	126.5
Sedimentary bacterial hopanoids	University of Newcastle-upon-Tyne	Fossil Fuels and Environ. Geochem.	Dr P. Farrimond	α 4	Service	T	24.5
Organic residues in archaeological pottery	University of Bradford	Dept. of Archaeological Sciences	Dr C. Heron	α 4	Service	NR	40
Isotope analysis of amino sugars	IGER	Soils Group	Dr R. Bol	α 4	Collaborative	BD	15
Climatic indicators of aridity from lake sediments	University of Swansea	Dept. of Geography	Dr K. Ficken Professor A. Street-Perrot	α 4	Collaborative	GC	123
Methanotrophic bacteria in soils	CEH	Soil Ecology Section	Professor P. Ineson	α 4 ²	Collaborative	BD	25
Nematode control	University of Bristol	Dept. of Clinical Veterinary Science	Dr G.C. Coles	α 3	Collaborative	NR	11

¹NR = Natural Resource; GC = Global Change; T = Terrestrial; BD = Biodiversity. ²Assigned as part of Service Heads 10% discretionary allocation.

5.2 Publications - In the seven years of operation the Service has contributed data to 13 PhD theses and more than forty papers published or in press for outside users. This year has been a very successful year for the Service with four papers published, some 9 submitted or in press, and two PhD theses completed. A notable feature of the published work of users is the high standard of the journals in which the work is reported (mean impact factor >2.0). The work of the in-house users of the facilities have resulted in 25 published works and 7 PhD theses completed for the period April 1999 to March 2000.

5.3 Personnel - Funding was provided for one full-time technical post (Mr A. Gledhill; Grade D) and recurrent costs. Professor Maxwell FRS is the director of the Service and Professor Evershed the manager. Mr J.F. Carter is a University supported Research Associate for the Service and acting steering committee meetings secretary.

5.4 Capital bid - The capital bid from the Service for 1999-2000 incorporated a number of smaller computer upgrades and replacement equipment items totalling £6,369.

**Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility
ANNUAL REPORT April 1999/March 2000**

East Kilbride Glasgow G75 0QF Telephone: East Kilbride (01355) 270142 Fax: (01355) 229898

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

1. Overview and Highlights:

This report covers the period 1st April 1999 to 31st March 2000, the sixth year of operation of the LSCSIF.

The Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility (LSCSIF) exists to support the Terrestrial and Freshwater and Marine scientific research community, facilitating access to stable isotope facilities (both natural abundance and enriched tracer work) that are not widely available within the ecological community. The LSCSIF is unique amongst the NSS funded isotope facilities as it is the only one that has the capacity for doubly labelled water (DLW) analysis for the study of energy expenditure. However, we also meet the sustained demand for $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ and $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ at natural abundance in bulk organic matter, and are responsive to demand for $^{34}\text{S}/^{32}\text{S}$, D/H and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ measurements.

This was the second year of the second contract to support the LSCSIF (April 1998 - March 2001). As such in December 1999 the Facility was reviewed and the renewal for the period April 2001 - March 2004 was granted based on assessment of the following criteria:

Criterion	Need	Uniqueness	Service Quality	Science / Training Quality	Mean rating
Score out of 5	5.0	4.5	4.0	4.5	4.5

The Service Review Group noted that the application of isotope analysis in ecology is scientifically exciting and the Facility contribution to the NSS portfolio is important. The request for an additional 50% technical support was also supported. This is warmly welcomed, as it is becoming difficult to cope with the current demand for support and this has been at the expense of technique development (see Fig. 1)

During the past year of service we have collaborated on ten approved projects, which have involved the training and cross-discipline skill-development of one NERC M. Res. student, two Ph.D. students and three post-doctoral researchers (two NERC fellows) in the analytical techniques appropriate to their project. Three of ten projects required doubly labelled water analyses, and the remaining seven required natural abundance $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ measurements. Despite the greater demand for natural abundance measurements this year, the doubly labelled water projects still commanded more facility resources (63%) due to the time-consuming nature of the analyses, but we hope that this time allocation will drop in the forthcoming year due to advances we have made in developing faster analytical techniques for such analyses. Collaborative research is encouraged, and this policy has been reasonably successful.

In the service level agreement, 50% of staff time is allocated to laboratory work on collaborative projects, which incorporates an allowance for instrument calibration, equipment maintenance and pilot projects. Combined maintenance and project collaboration averaged 76% of staff time per quarter (Fig. 1), therefore the facility was used 152% of its agreed capacity.

Figure 1. Distribution of Facility resources during 99/00.

2. Scientific highlights from the past year of service include:

1. The impact of climate change on species distribution and behaviour has implications for biodiversity and conservation. While recent studies have suggested that birds can adjust their egg laying to earlier Springs, little is known of the response of individual species to environmental change. Use of the doubly labelled water technique to investigate egg laying energetics in wild Great Tits (NERC funded) showed the pattern of Spring warming can be critical to the ability of this species to respond to climate change. Warmer springs tend to advance the appearance of the caterpillars used to feed Great Tit chicks, but if the early Spring does not warm as quickly as late Spring, energetic constraints may hinder Great Tits from advancing their laying date. The energy necessary to produce large eggs must be diverted to thermoregulation, so that birds must either lay small, poor quality eggs or delay egg laying. This can lead to a mismatch in the timing of chick and caterpillar hatching and a consequent reduction in the breeding success. A detailed understanding of a species' biology may be necessary to predict the effects of climate change rather than the broad correlational approach often used to date (Prof. Bryant, Stirling University, in press for *Nature*).

2. Nearly a decade ago sea trout catches in western Scotland dropped to an all-time low and have remained there since. Monitoring spawning success of both sea-run and freshwater-resident salmonids is of central importance to effective management policies for stock conservation. Although spawning adults can be usually be identified on the basis of their colour, size and body form, the technically laborious carotenid pigment profiling is the only technique currently known to identify eggs of alevins collected from the field as the progeny of anadromous (Atlantic salmon, sea trout) or nonanadromous (brown trout) fish. Dr. McCarthy (NERC Fellow 1996-1999) used CF-IRMS to show that eggs

sampled from anadromous spawning trout are easily distinguished from non-anadromous spawning trout by their carbon and nitrogen isotopic signature (U. of Glasgow).

3. Competition for food resources is thought to be a major force in shaping animal communities with interspecific competition influencing the presence / absence of a species in a community, its population size and habitat use. Recent NERC-funded studies by Dr. Adams and colleagues on Arctic charr in Scotland have identified populations containing two or more sympatric morphs, but limitations in stomach content analysis could not fully test the hypothesis that morphs living in sympatry occupy distinct foraging niches. Carbon and nitrogen isotopic signatures indicate diet and trophic status respectively, with a 3‰ difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ thought to represent a shift of one trophic level. Isotopic fingerprinting of the charr confirmed that sympatric morphs are occupying different foraging niches - benthivorous, planktivorous and piscivorous - and identified water bodies where polymorphism is currently occurring (U. of Glasgow).

Figure 2: Carbon and nitrogen isotopic signatures of Arctic charr from Lochs Tay and Rannoch.

3. Summary of performance information:

i) number and percentage of α -graded proposals submitted during the year 99/00:

Standard applications								
$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	Currently under review	Pilot	Reject
0	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	0

Student applications								
$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	Currently under review	Pilot	Reject
0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1	0

ii) the % distribution and costs of projects supported during the year 99/00 according to science area:

ESTB		ASTB		MSTB		TFSTB		EOEG		SBASG	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
						100	75				

iii) the % distribution and costs of projects supported during the year 99/00 according to NERC ENRI's:

Biodiversity		Env. Risk/ Hazard		Global Change		Nat. Resource Man.		Poll. & Waste		Other	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
86.9	65.2			7.1	5.3	6.0	4.5				

iv) Peer-reviewed papers in press or due published during the calendar year 1999:

User feedback and literature checks identified a total of six refereed publications which relate to the NERC Science and Technology Board / Expert Group fields as given below. The complete publication list is given in Appendix 1.

	EO	Marine	T/F	Arch	Earth	Atmos.
No of publications (1999)			4		2	

v) targets and milestones

Our specific targets in the sixth year of providing this Facility were to:

1. Increase the user group and expand the applications of stable isotopes.
2. Meet the existing demand for doubly labelled water (DLW) analysis at a time suitable to the user.
3. Accommodate the demand for the rapid throughput of combined $\delta^{13}\text{C}/\delta^{15}\text{N}$ natural abundance measurements within Life and related sciences.

Our efforts in publicising the applications of stable isotopes in ecology and the role of the Facility are beginning to show within the community. Of the seven applications submitted this year, five were from new users, a trend that has continued into the year 00/01. Progress has been made in bringing the Europa CF-IRMS on-line for $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ analyses but due to limited resources we have still not been able to allocate sufficient time to render this system routinely operational. This will be our development priority in the year 00/01. Currently under review is one of the application for DLW analysis where a much larger isotopically labelled sample volume is available (1ml as opposed to 100 μ l). This project is doubly interesting as it will allow us to combine development of CF-IRMS for faster throughput of DLW projects with data production. The requested additional 50% technical support linked to the Facility renewal has been brought forward, so the development targets scheduled for 00/01 are realistic.

To date we have been able to accommodate all users at a time suitable to their fieldwork commitments, however the currently approved and anticipated DLW workload is such their may be some conflict in demands for lab access from approved users. Dr. Waldron should be able to handle this, but Steering Committee support may be required.

vi) financial details

Full cash cost	Unit cost @426 units pa	Recurrent Allocation	Capital Expenditure	Revenue
£75,000	£176.06	£62,550*	£12,500	£0k

vii) service management and staffing during the year 99/00:

Head of Service	Facility Manager	Facility Technical Support
Prof. Fallick, non-salaried	Dr. S. Waldron, Research Fellow@100%	Mrs. J. Dougans, Grade D @50%

viii) Further information: can be found in the detailed annexes from which the above items were extracted. These are available from the Services and Facilities on request.

Buxton Climate Change Impacts Laboratory (BCCIL)

Annual Report

April 1999 - March 2000

K Thompson

1. Service Objectives

BCCIL is at the Health and Safety Laboratory, Harpur Hill, Buxton, but its staff are based at the University of Sheffield. BCCIL aims to provide space, infrastructure and assistance to support high-quality field research in climate change and related areas of ecology and environmental sciences.

2. Overview and Highlights

One of our major activities during the year was to maintain and improve the existing long-term experiments at the site. In particular, we aimed to improve the reliability and ease of maintenance of our flagship climate change experiment by redesigning the rainshelter covers for easier removal and winter storage. Over the years, we have made many small incremental improvements to the rainshelters, and 1999 saw the best performance to date, with no operational failures at all. We expect the new covers to be operational by summer 2000 and to be much easier to operate with a small staff. BCCIL now has unrivalled experience in the design, use and maintenance of automatic rainshelters. Many years ago, plans were supplied to the Texas Agricultural Experiment Station; they recently reported that they have worked very well and that they have had numerous requests for the plans.

We are also designing and installing a new digital temperature monitoring and control system. This will have a much larger capacity and will be much more reliable than the existing analogue system. It has not previously been possible to monitor all control and heated plots, but in future we will be able to do so.

In addition we completed extensive improvements of facilities for visitors. We also continued to publicise the opportunities offered by the Laboratory. Our web site (<http://www.shef.ac.uk/~nuocpe/bccil/>) was extended and improved and the Director delivered illustrated talks about the Laboratory at eight other institutions. We have also purchased and installed a webcam on the slope opposite the experiments, which should very shortly be transmitting live images on our web site.

Our climate change experiment is now in its seventh year. This unique experiment continues to demonstrate the resistance of the unproductive vegetation at BCCIL to drought and soil warming treatments, in stark contrast to the vegetation receiving similar treatments at Wytham, which has proved to be highly vulnerable to climate change. However, the plant community at Buxton is not immune to climate change, and it is now clear that warming and drought are responsible for a slow but steady decline in the abundance of sedges. These data, which have been presented at several conferences, are of crucial importance in forecasting the effects of climate change in the UK and form part of a major study of regional climate change in the East Midlands, commissioned by the Environment Agency and led by Entec plc. A paper based on the combined data from BCCIL and Wytham has been favourably reviewed by *Science* and we expect it to be published later this year. A poster based on the same data will be presented at the ESA/BES symposium in Orlando.

Data from BCCIL and from Wytham were supplied to the GCTE global analysis of warming experiments carried out by the National Centre for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis in San Diego. Both sites are thus now part of the GCTE Network of Ecosystem Warming Studies (GCTE-NEWS), the goal of which is to integrate and foster research on ecosystem-level effects of rising temperature. BCCIL and Wytham are two of only seven grassland sites in this global network. A manuscript describing the analysis is now almost complete and will be submitted shortly to *Ecological Applications*.

For the third and final year, BCCIL staff made a major contribution to the collecting effort for the Millennium Seed Bank. After Kew and Edinburgh Botanic Garden, BCCIL made the third largest number of collections for the Millennium Seed Bank.

3. Science

BCCIL's potential will only be fully realised if the site and the experience and skills of its staff are exploited in developing new science. We are therefore pleased to report that several major new initiatives have been proposed during the year.

A bid to GANE, with Trevor Ashenden of CEH Bangor as lead PI, will exploit our years of experience with rain shelters by using a new set of shelters to exclude anthropogenic N deposition. New plots will be shielded year-round from rain and the water replaced by deionised water, thus removing all 'wet' N deposition, about 40 % of the total. As far as we are aware, this will be the first attempt anywhere to examine the effects on a natural plant community of reducing N deposition in the field.

Also aiming to exploit our long experience with field climate change technology, a major Vth Framework bid will study the vulnerability of grasslands to climate change from E-W across Europe, in the UK, Netherlands, Germany, Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania and Switzerland. At Buxton this will involve using data from the existing climate change experiment and also establishing new treatments. A novel feature of this project is the use of solar-powered rainshelters to manipulate both rainfall *and* temperature at locations lacking mains electricity.

Another project, funded by an EU Marie Curie Fellowship, will attempt for the first time to separate the direct and indirect effects of climate change on plant litter decomposition. This project will use plant material from the existing climate change experiment, but will also involve the establishment of new climate-manipulated plots.

4. Future Developments

The steering Committee graded and approved eight proposals for 2000-2001. Below, these proposals are arranged into categories:

Higher plants – climate change	3
Higher plants – nitrogen deposition	1
Mosses – mineral nutrients	1
Soil fauna – climate change	1
Mycorrhizas – climate change	1
Soil microbes – UVB	1

The projects approved represent a healthy balance between above- and below-ground, but a number of important areas are underrepresented or absent, including the impact of climate

change on bryophytes and on nutrient mineralisation and CO₂ flux. This is particularly regrettable, since one finding of the GCTE-NEWS analysis is that there is no soil warming experiment anywhere in the world where all three key ecosystem variables (soil respiration, net N mineralisation, and aboveground plant productivity) are being measured. Another obvious omission from the BCCIL portfolio is the above-ground insect community. A high priority during the coming year will be to attempt to fill these gaps with appropriate projects.

5. Summary of performance information

5.1 Proposals supported

BCCIL supported two student projects, one funded by NERC and the other by a University of Nottingham studentship.

We also continued to provide training for groups of undergraduate and postgraduate students from the Universities of Sheffield, York, Manchester and Liverpool. A presentation from the Director continues to form part of the final year undergraduate course in Community Ecology at the University of Sussex.

Date	Institution	Course	Numbers
21.10.99	Liverpool University	Environmental Biology Hons	15
5.12.99	Manchester University	MSc Pollution and Environmental Control	23
		MSc Environmental Engineering	8
		MSc IDPM	7
23.2.00	York University	MRes	32
6.4.00	Sheffield University	APS 241	20
		APS 246	39

All projects and training were in the TFS science area.

NERC ENRIs:

	Biodiversity	Env risks	Global change	Nat. resource man.	Pollution & Waste
£	35100		93600		36270
%	21		57		22

5.2 Publications - calendar year 1999

All TFS

Type of publication	Number
Refereed papers listed in ISI database	5
Other refereed publications	-
Books written	-
Book chapters written	-
Books edited	-
Non-refereed publications	-

5.3 Targets and milestones

A number of targets for 1999-2000 were agreed between the Steering Committee and Director. With very few exceptions, these targets were either met or exceeded (see Appendix).

During 2000-01, one of our main targets will be to continue to alert the research community to the opportunities offered by BCCIL. Although a major effort was made in this direction during the past year, a number of institutions remain to be visited, including CEH Bangor, MLURI and the Universities of Nottingham, Derby, Bradford, UMIST and Liverpool John Moores. The Director will also undertake a more directed search of research groups that might be willing to fill the important gaps identified in 4.1 above.

At the site, we will continue to modify and refine our experiments in order to make them more reliable and easier to maintain. We will fully commission the webcam and exploit its public relations possibilities, including the possibility of small amounts of commercial sponsorship. If GANE funding is secured, one of our main activities in 2000-01 will be the construction and installation of the new nitrogen-reduction experiment.

Several publications are in press or in review, but another priority is to turn the backlog of accumulated data into further publications. An updated publication on the long-term invasions experiment is a particular priority and will be submitted during 2000. We also hope to monitor the invasions experiment (now ten years old) and the permanent quadrats in the climate change experiment (deferred from 1999). However, these are very time-consuming activities and must be accommodated alongside the routine monitoring of the climate change plots. All these activities are strongly weather-dependent.

5.3 Finance

Total expenditure on staffing, including overheads, was £144,438.58. Other expenditure of £49,212.09 included major improvements to the laboratory infrastructure.

5.4 Service management

BCCIL has three full-time staff (Dr Ken Thompson, Director, and Andrew Askew and Stuart Band, technicians) and a half-time secretary, Dr Val Greggains.

Andrew Askew completed his part-time MSc in Applied Artificial Intelligence in the Department of Computer Science, University of Sheffield in September 1999.

NERC Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility (SMGF) First Annual Report (1 September 1998 - 31 March 2000)

This report covers the period 1 September 1998 to 31 March 2000, including the first full year of operation of the SMGF.

1. Service Objectives

The aim of the SMGF is to provide the UK environmental science community with access to molecular genetic facilities and training. The Facility achieves this aim by using peer review to ensure that only the best science is supported, by advertising the Facility as widely as possible, by encouraging users to publish their work in publications and at conferences, and by compiling methodological data and providing materials. The Facility monitors user satisfaction and acts on users' suggestions. The Facility also carries out some underpinning research and development towards improving and extending the available technologies.

2. Overview and Highlights

In January 1998, the Services Review Group recommended that the SMGF should be funded until 31 March 2002, with a review of performance in January 2001. The Facility had originally been planned for establishment in the Department of Biology at the University of Leicester, but a resiting to the Department of Animal and Plant Sciences at the University of Sheffield was agreed following the move by the Head of Service, Professor Terry Burke in May 1998. It was also agreed that the Facility's opening would be delayed until September 1998 and that the report on the first seven months would be included with this first full year's report.

The initial projects carried out in the Facility were dominated by behavioural studies of birds, reflecting the laboratory's reputation in this area and the availability of appropriate methods. However, recent applications have increasingly included a broader range of taxa and questions.

Projects from the University of Sheffield were peer-reviewed as for those from elsewhere and were given access to the Facility, but the costs of these projects were offset by the University's contribution to the Facility (background technical support and provision and maintenance of equipment).

3. Science

Three examples of α -graded projects completed in the SMGF are described below:

Song as an indicator of age and extra-pair paternity in the Sedge Warbler Acrocephalus schoenobaenus using DNA profiling. (R Marshall & C Catchpole, RHBNC, London)

Many apparently monogamous species of birds have now been shown to be socially monogamous but genetically polygynous, as they engage in copulations outside the pair bond. It has previously been shown in the sedge warbler that male song is used by females when selecting their primary mate: the more elaborate the song, the more attractive the male is to the female. This study aimed to test the prediction that female sedge warblers choose superior extra-pair males on the basis of their song structure, using microsatellite markers in order to assign paternity to chicks found not to be genetically related to their putative social fathers.

A comparison of genetic with social fathers on the basis of previously recorded male characteristics would then be possible.

Preliminary analyses suggest that there is a unique system of extra-pair mate choice in the sedge warbler. Female sedge warblers prefer extra-pair mates with smaller song repertoires than their social mate. In other words, they have extra-pair copulations with males of lower quality. This is the opposite of what has previously been found in the closely related great reed warbler. The reasons for this apparently paradoxical result are the subject of further investigation.

Mating frequency in wasps (K Foster & F Ratnieks, University of Sheffield)

The purpose of the research was to use microsatellite loci to determine relatedness among worker wasps in each of four species (variation is caused by variation in number of males mated to the queen) and its relationship to male production by workers. The prediction was that male production by workers will occur in species with low (ca. single) queen mating frequency. The work on *Vespula vulgaris* was initiated in the SMGF. Previous work on worker policing (i.e. the inhibition of reproduction by workers) has mainly been done in bees. The aim here was to test theory by seeing if policing also occurs in wasps.

The novel discovery was made that worker policing occurs in *V. vulgaris*, a species with multiply mated queens, as predicted by theory. In the hornet, *V. crabro*, queen mating frequency was close to one but all males were queens' sons, in contrast to theoretical expectation. In *Dolichovespula* wasps queen mating frequency was close to one and workers reproduced as predicted by theory. In *D. saxonica* queen mating frequency was variable. Worker policing occurred but was modulated by queen mating frequency, happening predominantly in the colonies with multiply mated queens, as predicted by theory.

Brood sex ratio variation and extra-pair paternity in blue tits, Parus caeruleus (D Leech, I R K Stewart & I R Hartley, Univ Lancaster)

Sex allocation theory predicts that parents should manipulate brood sex ratio in order to maximise the combined reproductive value of their progeny. Females mating with high quality males should, therefore, be expected to produce brood sex ratios biased towards sons, as male offspring would receive a relatively greater advantage from inheritance of their father's characteristics than would their female siblings. Furthermore, it has been suggested that sex allocation of chicks fathered through extra-pair fertilisations should also be biased towards sons. Contrary to these predictions, no evidence was found that the distribution of sex ratios in a sample of 1483 chicks from 154 broods of blue tits (an exceptional sample size) deviated significantly from that of a binomial distribution around an even sex ratio. There was also no significant effect of male or female biometrics, feather mite loads or time of breeding on brood sex ratio, suggesting that females in our population were either unable to manipulate offspring sex allocation or did not do so because selection pressures were not strong enough to produce a significant shift away from random sex allocation. The paternity of 916 chicks from 95 broods was determined using DNA microsatellite typing. One hundred and seven chicks (11.7%) from 45 broods (47.4%) were sired by extra-pair males. There was no significant effect of paternity (within-pair versus extra-pair) on sex of individual offspring. The results suggest that, in addition to the weakness of selection pressures, the possible mechanisms responsible for the allocation of sex may not be sufficiently accurate to control offspring sex at the level of the individual egg. The results contrast with some similar studies using generally much smaller sample sizes.

4. Future Developments

Five out of 15 respondents to a SMGF users' questionnaire independently indicated that more technical support was required. There has been a strong and increasing demand for access to the SMGF and it has therefore been agreed that 50% of a technician grade C would be supported in 2000-2002. The technician will assist the coordinator with cloning work and the supervision and training of visiting researchers.

The host research group has made an application to the Joint Infrastructure Fund. If successful, the application would enhance the laboratory facilities available to the SMGF and expand the DNA analysis equipment.

5. Summary of Performance Information

(i) Numbers of Proposals Supported

SMGF received 15 applications from 13 PIs in 10 different UK HEIs during October 1998 – March 2000. Unsuitable or potentially weak proposals were discouraged at an early stage in the application process, and all others were accepted by the Steering Committee. 12 projects have now been completed.

Three projects are still ongoing but at an early stage. A microsatellite library is being prepared in each case, and in each case one user will require future access to the Facility.

Just two small projects required access only (for work performed by Facility staff).

Applications Received						
$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	Reject
1	6	6	3	0	0	0

The cost of projects according to science area was as follows:

ESTB		ASTB		MSTB		TFSTB		EOEG		SBASG	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	3.1	3.1	96.9	97.1	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

(ii) Classification and Cost of Projects

The distribution of science projects according to NERC ENRIs was as follows:

Biodiversity		Env.Risk/ Hazard		Global Change		Nat.Resource Management		Pollution & Waste		Other	
%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k	%	£k
96.8	97.0	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	Nil	Nil

(iii) Output - Calendar Year 1999

Eight publications (including two PhD theses) have appeared so far. There is inevitably a lag between use of a new Facility and published output, but at least two more papers have been submitted and many more papers and theses are in preparation.

	EO	Marine	T/F	Arch	Earth	Atmos
No. Pubs	0	0	8	0	0	0

(iv) *Targets & Milestones*

In the period under report SMGF users were allocated 10% of the available time on the Facility's Applied Biosystems 377 DNA analyser. Users indicated a high level of satisfaction with the Facility.

(vi) *Finance FY 1998/99*

Full Cash Cost	Unit Cost (per user month)	Recurrent Alloc	Capital Expend	Revenue
£49.7k	£2.069k	£37.2k	£12.5k	Nil

(vi) *Finance FY 1999/2000*

Full Cash Cost	Unit Cost (@36 user months pa)	Recurrent Alloc	Capital Expend	Revenue
£79.3k	£1.748k	£62.9k	£16.3k	Nil

(vi) *Training*

Training was provided to 14 visiting researchers (9 PhD students, 4 Postdoctoral Research Associates and 1 Research Technician).

7. Service Management/Staff

The SMGF is currently staffed as follows:

Science Coordinator RAIB@ 100% FTA

8. Further Information

If required, more information can be found in the detailed annexes from which the above items were extracted. These are available from Services & Facilities on request.